

Comprehending the role of Big Data in developing countries:
the case of financial industry in Egypt

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Abstract

This study examines the relevance and importance of Big Data (BD) in developing countries' financial industries using Egypt's banking sector as an example. In many contemporary societies and their businesses, information is increasingly becoming the most significant resource and the basis for competition. Hence, BD is unsurprisingly becoming an essential asset for many sectors, including financial services in general and the banking sector in particular. There is also evidence suggesting that globally, the finance industry – especially the banking sector- is beginning to tap into BD's potential. Its impact extends from better customer services to regulatory enforcement, monitoring, risk prevention, and fraud detection. However, in emerging economies such as Egypt, BD is in its infancy. Consequently, there is minimal research literature on the role and extent of BD within the banking sector. The aim of this study is, therefore, by using the Egyptian banking sector as an example, to explore and then showcase the emerging role and impact of BD with/in the financial industry in the developing countries, which will help explain the extent of BD and uncover the gap by using a substantive theory. Therefore, to support the argument made in this study, appropriate empirical evidence is collected from diverse stakeholder groups in an Egyptian bank, using the Constructivist Grounded Theory method. This qualitative research, therefore, produced extensive evidence resulting in further new insight into how stakeholders construct the concept of BD, frame the ways harnessing BD can be managed with a further suggestion to future research and assess the application and sustainability of BD in the broader financial industry across the developing world.

Keywords: Big Data, constructivist grounded theory, financial services, banking, developing countries, Egypt.

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“I will give thanks to you, Lord, with all my heart; I will tell of all your wonderful deeds.” Psalm 9:1

“From the bottom of my heart, thank you, Lord, for being there for me when I needed you. Your help and support made a huge difference.

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“True wisdom comes to each of us when we realise how little we understand about life, ourselves, and the world around us.” Socrates

Author's Declaration

I hereby declare that the materials contained in this thesis have not been previously submitted for a degree in this or any other university. I further declare that this thesis is solely based on my research. Finally, I declare that all information in this research has been obtained and presented following academic rules and ethical conduct.

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Acronyms & Abbreviations

Acronym	Meaning
3Vs	Volume, Variety and Velocity
BD	Big Data
BDA	Big Data Analytics
IDC	The International Data Corporation
DGI	Data Governance Institute
IT	Information Technology
AI	Artificial Intelligence
ML	Machine Learning
IoT	The Internet of Things
5G	The Fifth-Generation Technology standard for Cellular Networks
ATM	Automated Teller Machine
Fintech	Financial Technology
DMs	Data Management System
GT	Grounded Theory
GGT	Glaserian Grounded-Theory
SGT	Straussian Grounded-Theory
CGT	Constructivist Grounded Theory
EFSA	Egyptian Financial Supervisory Authority
CBE	Central Bank of Egypt
KYC	Know Your Customer
CRM	Customer Relationship Management
LMIC	Lower and Middle Income
LEDC	Less Economically Developed Countries
GDP	Gross Domestic Product
UN	The United Nations
GNI	Gross National Income
CAPMAS	Central Agency for Public Mobilisation and Statistics
UNFPA	United Nations Population Fund
KM	Knowledge Management
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
CSFs	Critical Success Factors
RBT	Resource-Based Theory
GDPR	The General Data Protection Regulation
DPA	Data Protection Act

Awards, Presentations and Publications

Awards

I was awarded a prize for the content and clarity of my research intention in January 2020, knowledge exchange symposium, University of Wales Trinity Saint David London (UWTSD).

Conferences and Poster Presentations

- Oral & Poster presentation at the knowledge exchange event held at UWTSD, London
- AI & Big Data Expo Global, London
- Oral & Poster presentation at the stem village, Scotland
- Oral presentation at Global Knowledge Exchange Network (GKEN), Online

Publications (work in progress)

- Constructivist Grounded Theory: An Example of a Study of Big Data
- Opportunities and Limiting Factors of Big Data in Financial Industry: A Review
- Big Data Potentials: A Risk Management Approach

1 Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 A Glance on the Thesis

This study examines Big Data's (BD) emerging role in the financial industry in developing countries by using the Egyptian banking sector as an example to help illustrate the phenomenon of BD and address the research questions by generating a substantive theory. This included the role and position of BD, as observed on an everyday basis in Egypt's chosen banking sector. The approach was an in-depth investigation study by engaging with the main stakeholders (i.e. Executives, IT Facilitators, Regulators, Customers) and scrutinising the stakeholders' understanding, perceptions, and attitudes relating to BD regarding opportunities, challenges, implications, and limitations. Thus, this research is outlined in six chapters:

Chapter 1 is an introductory chapter focusing on the research's intention, background, context, and the aims and objectives are briefly presented. It also addresses the problematic situation and articulating the research questions the study is seeking to answer.

Chapter 2 analyses and summarises relevant literature applicable to BD concept, BD benefits to business, BD and banking, BD and finance in developed countries, BD and Bank in Egypt.

Chapter 3 discusses the research methodology, detailing the research design based on the chosen method (i.e. Constructivist Grounded Theory) and describing how the data was gathered during the three-month field research.

Chapter 4 reports the data analysis and findings by stating the wealth of information collected regarding BD's use in/with the banking sector and how the several stakeholder groups practice BD and relate to it.

Chapter 5 demonstrates the collection and analysis of the empirical evidence gathered from the main stakeholders concerning BD's use with/in various financial sectors.

Chapter 6 draws upon the entire thesis to summarise the research contributions of this study and discusses the results using the theoretical model's assessment criteria. This chapter also identifies the research limitations encountered and also provides a direction for future research.

1.2 Intentions of Research

The author of this study intends to make two forms of contribution with this DBA thesis:

- 1- To propose implementing this study's outcomes in the selected industry and banks, the Egyptian Ministry of Finance, and the EFSA.
- 2- To contribute to the body of knowledge regarding BD's relevance and appropriateness to the banking sector, finance, and broader society.

1.3 Dimensions, Evolution, and Challenges of BD

A large and growing body of literature highlights BD's relevance, leading to a combination of diverse philosophical understandings across various fields and, at times, with the absence of a consistent meaning (Custers *et al.*, 2017; Motamarri *et al.*, 2017). In addition, a substantial body of studies has also been written on BD as a discipline that has arisen in the last few decades. It has commonly been assumed that BD is a phenomenon that can entirely change every aspect of culture and industry (Bhaduri *et al.*, 2016; Mikalef *et al.*, 2020).

Congruently, on the one hand, it is thought that BD would change every business, from the way retail and financial services operate extending to the broader fields in the public health data to include medication cancer research (Saggi *et al.*, 2018). On the other hand, some scholars believe that BD is a trend that will eventually disappear (Arunachalam *et al.*, 2017). Regardless of the above thoughts, BD is increasingly sought across many industries as it is believed to help an organisation achieve its business goal and offering a competitive edge. Notwithstanding, there is still a lack of clarity and a continuous debate on what BD means.

Therefore, this section's principal purpose is to clarify BD's meaning and value, leading to our understanding of its origin and designate a definition adopted for this research. Several attempts have been made on the historical developments in BD. It has commonly been assumed that BD was initiated in 1944 in a survey conducted by Gil Press that traced the development of data history in 32 events from 1944 to 2013 and established into BD. Press (2013) claimed in his article (A Very Short History of Big Data) that 'information explosion' is the thin line of data development and BD. Since Press (2013) reviewed BD's events up to 2013, many relevant BD events have occurred. However, BD may be well-thought-out as a complementary essence of data explosion (Delen, 2014).

Even though the BD term is well known, one criticism of BD's literature is that there is no agreement about its connotation. For example, many data scientists suggest that BD extract, transform, and load datasets (Bauer, 2016; Trabucchi *et al.*, 2019). BD's basic description is based on BD's key characteristics, but this explanation's critical problem is that it discarded BD's other attributes (Zomaya and Sakr, 2017). Given that, the following section provides a comprehensive analysis of the historical development of BD definition.

To date, there is no consensus about the BD definition. Notably, there is a degree of uncertainty around the word 'Big', reflecting the data volume (Hariri, Fredericks and Bowers, 2019). Nevertheless, from the evolutionary perception, the size of BD is constantly evolving. Therefore, it is believed that BD is ill-defined and has a moderately vague definition, showing a need to be unambiguous about what is meant by BD (De Mauro *et al.*, 2016).

Furthermore, even though data management has progressed significantly since the 1800s, advancements have been made in recent years, making data management more efficiently attainable (Rehman *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, the following section briefly illustrates the primary industrial revolution that evolved the BD definition to continue the argument about BD's meaning.

In 1989, Berners-Lee invented the World Wide Web (www), and knowledge exchange was the original intention (Lee *et al.*, 2001).

In 2001, Doug Laney articulated data management's first 3Vs (Volume, Velocity and Variety) (Press, 2013).

In 2005, BD was mentioned for the first time by Roger Magoulas. BD refers to massive data that cannot be managed through traditional business tools (Marr, 2015).

In 2006, The first open-source programme (Hadoop) was created by Yahoo to handle such gigantic data (Bessani *et al.*, 2010).

In 2010, Eric Schmidt argued that the data volume produced by the entire globe between the beginning of humanity and 2003, surprisingly is the same amount of data generated in two days, was five exabytes (Rusu, 2016).

Nowadays, BD's era has begun; BD refers to collecting and analysing smart data in ways that were not possible in the past. However, constructing the BD growth, a vast amount of data is emerging from the Internet of things (IoT) and the ability to store and analyse various data types, such as structured, semi-structured and unstructured (Ahmed *et al.*, 2019).

Another practical consequence, Statista (2016), reported that the number of internet-connected devices would reach 74.44 billion devices by 2025, which implies that there would be enormous growth in the amount and the variety of data. By contrast, Marr (2017) asserts that raw BD has great concealed business value; however, the critical challenge is to extract that value. Similarly, Trabucchi *et al.* (2019) assume that the amount of data is not essential; the insights of this data can be used as an added value. Notwithstanding, the next chapter explores BD's origin and sheds light on how BD's definition has developed in the last decades.

1.3.1 BD Challenges

Current empirical and theoretical studies have distinguished the business value challenge from BD, technical and primarily organisational challenges (Sharma *et al.*, 2020). According to Carlsson *et al.* (2018), BD lacks in comprehension and recognition, and corporations fail to know what BD is and what

requirements are needed to adopt the systems, and results show a waste in several resources and time when companies do not have the necessary knowledge to use it.

Furthermore, According to Marr (2016), converting BD into desirable insights is the principal challenge for any organisation. Many companies, however, failed to have the required systems and external data to achieve their goals. Several researchers have recognised BD cost as one of an organisation's main challenges when adopting the BD approach (Pugna *et al.*, 2019). Although there are various open-source frameworks, BD adoption involves many expenses, such as BD solution development, maintenance, new hardware, services, and electricity (Baig *et al.*, 2019).

Additionally, Schaeffer *et al.* (2018) argued that an organisation could mislead the right BD technology because of the misperception caused by the available number of BD technologies on the market. Finally, Nwokeji *et al.* (2019) highlighted the skills shortages as a present real problem. Firms need to find individuals with diverse skills who can be involved with the business, distinguish the issues, and then use cases to solve them.

While Bagha *et al.* (2019) alleged that it is not about the data volume, as described previously, but about the results' accuracy. The difficulty of managing data quality, as BD comes from multiple sources in diverse formats, leading to data integration problems. Additionally, Dawei *et al.* (2018) demonstrated that data security is quite a vast issue, while there is a remarkable development on the BD technologies, security features, yet still deserted.

By drawing on the concept of anonymity, Raj *et al.* (2018) have shown that, as BD development continues, these three BD issues (data security, data insight, and data privacy) remain the priority items for regulators. While authors caution about BD risks and challenges, others highlighted the business opportunities and advantages of using BD solutions (Raj *et al.*, 2018; Pugna *et al.*, 2019).

Comprehensibly, it has been suggested that firms should focus on BD processes and insights that could bring about economic value and gain a competitive advantage (Del Vecchio *et al.*, 2018). However, as mentioned

before, there are many challenges associated with the implementation of BD. A survey conducted by Ge *et al.* (2018) has shown that many difficulties are linked to BD adoption in an organisation.

Therefore, the study has identified two core challenges: technology and infrastructure challenges where BD rely on computing for network hardware, cloud storage and a fast internet connection, on the one hand, organisation culture change, where BD compound infrastructure depends on complex analytics methods that employees and managers cannot comprehend which generates change resistance that prevents the implementation process.

Recent evidence suggests that employees and managers dealing with BD systems tend to understate the possible outcomes, infrastructure difficulty and analysis practices of utilising BD (Lunde *et al.*, 2019). To do so, Mills (2019) highlights the need for organisational culture change by drawing employees' and managers' attention to the BD capabilities that will change an organisation to be a big-data culture organisation and cropping BD added-value can be possible.

1.4 BD within the Financial Services Industry

According to Altavilla *et al.* (2020), financial sectors and banking worldwide determine new and advanced approaches, integrating BD into all their processes for the best productivity. Moreover, it is believed that financial innovations are one of the fastest evolving disruptions to the banking industry, generating vast volumes of data every second from services such as peer to peer lending, cryptocurrency, wealth management, and mobile payments, and many platforms (Van Loo, 2018).

Evidence suggests that the use of internal and external data is increasing to make timely and relevant decisions. According to Stasinakis *et al.* (2020), trillions of data are transmitted among financial service businesses. As a result, the financial services industry has given BD more consideration because information plays an essential role in the ever-growing financial services market. Furthermore, BD has played a crucial role by giving valuable insights to improve overall experiences and overcome challenges in the banking

industry. Hassani *et al.* (2018) draw attention to five ways BD is changing financial services: Analyse risk, leveraging customer data, transforming organisational culture, creating transparency, and algorithmic trading.

Subsequently, the BD advancement that expanded around the 21st century has found convergence with the banking sector, given the valuable data accumulated over many decades. According to Laney (2001), Volume, diversity, and velocity are the three pillars of BD, and here is how banks react to them: Banks generate terabytes of data every day.

Thus, the volume is the amount of space required to keep it. Banks have to deal with enormous volumes of diverse data on and off the clock; diversity is the many types of data processed. For the quantities on which today's banks operate, dealing with 1000+ transactions is not a hypothetical figure; velocity is the rate at which original data are added to the database (Aasritha *et al.*, 2020).

Nevertheless, Perera *et al.* (2020) assert that these 3Vs are ineffective without value. The advantage for banks relates to the real-time use of the BD research findings and business decisions. These statistics have exposed the money transfer dynamics, helped deter many incidents and fraud and used to describe customers' behaviour (Kaisler *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, Óskarsdóttir *et al.* (2019) illustrated how banks would benefit expressively from BD by collecting valuable data quickly and efficiently converting it into concrete gains for the banks and customers.

Moreover, According to Badarau *et al.* (2020), the BD investment approach has two critical components: obtaining and understanding the data and utilising the appropriate methods and technologies to scrutinise those data. BD is explained as a structured, semi-structured and unstructured vast amount of data that overwhelms business daily. However, it is interesting how BD perspectives enhance decision-making and emerging market patterns in prospects (Gepp *et al.*, 2018). Therefore, the main business aim of BD is to turn the generated data into actionable insights.

In the past few years, many debates emerged regarding BD's advantages and disadvantages in the financial services industry. Several proponents believe that BD is the advanced epistemology in science and the next arena for rivalry, efficiency, and profitability (Lipworth *et al.*, 2017). In essence, Alharthi *et al.* (2017) argued that BD could alter working and living and people's banking. In contrast, Redman (2014) maintains that data could not speak for BD; therefore, the media is exaggerated and misinformed. The next chapter will further debate the potential and challenges of using BD in financial services.

1.5 Setting the Scene

The Egyptian banking sector was the focus of the research's fieldwork. The history of the banking sector started in 1836 when the Egyptian currency was issued. Evidence suggests that a new chapter of Egypt's banking industry is currently arising from the 4th industrial revolution (El-Dyasty, 2017). According to the Global Competitiveness Index (2020), Egypt is ranked 82nd among 140 countries worldwide, advancing 20 places than in 2015. This ranking is grounded on the attainments in administrative and economic fields, and it shows the country ability to compete economically.

In the digital economy era, digital banking with leveraging BD would enable a higher ranking for Egypt in the future. Therefore, the Egyptian Government (EG) and the Central Bank of Egypt (CBE) are making substantial progress with focusing on enhancing the banking model; 1 Billion EGP was allocated to fund innovation and investment in talents and start-ups (Weforum, 2019). Furthermore, BD would enhance efficiency and productivity and maximise Egypt's banking market's strategic advantage and digital platforms.

BD's need to derive intelligence moves at an equivalent and even faster pace as BD is concerned. Contrary to traditional datasets such as the daily stock process, Bagha *et al.* (2019) shed light on new datasets that are often more extensive in volume, variability, and velocity. Alternative datasets comprise data generated by individuals such as product reviews, search trends, and social media activities; data generated by sensors such as ship locations,

satellite images, car traffic; and business processes such as commercial transactions, credit cards, and company data.

Therefore, the data generated from various sources require improved utilisation of current and innovative technologies to attain, organise, assimilate and analyse in an interchange strategy (Zhang *et al.*, 2019). However, information assets require sophisticated, profitable types of information analytics for improved analysis and proactive decisions. BD is used to describe large data pieces that are practically too large to capture, store, manage, or analyse through traditional tools.

Accordingly, this thesis focuses on investigating the emerging role of BD in Egypt's banking sector. Hence, the bank under consideration is a bank in Egypt. Identity was shielded to avoid confidential information slipping out and henceforth referred to as XYZ Bank in this research.

XYZ bank has been in operation for the last 20 years, and the bank is a leading north, west and central African banking and financing group. In addition to its banking operations, the bank provides a wide variety of financial services through many subsidiaries: insurance, investment, personal financing, fast lending, leasing, factoring, stock exchange, asset management and market consulting services. As technology advances, data availability has augmented exponentially as well as the number of transactions.

1.6 Problematising the Egyptian Financial Sector

In recent years, data overgrows, to a certain degree, due to the exponential growth of the Internet of Things (IoT) devices such as wireless sensor networks 5G mobile, intelligent devices, cameras, microphones, and radio-frequency identification (RFID). For example, a recent study by Smallridge *et al.* (2020) shows that banks have large volumes of consumer data such as ATM deposits and withdrawals, point of sale transactions, electronic orders, and user profile data obtained from the Know Your Customer system (KYC). However, due to their silo, product-oriented organisations and banks struggle to exploit such lavish data sets.

Similarly, according to Dente *et al.* (2020), the growth in global payment volumes fuelled by e-commerce and mobile payments is a critical cause of this data explosion. Thus, while there is no evidence on how the global COVID-19 pandemic and the resulting economic slowdown could affect the global payments market; however, it is crucial to signify how this global pandemic affected the financial services industry.

Before the crisis, the banking sector's digital services tools and products increased at a diffident rate. For example, Economist (2020) reported that 50% of US banking customers occasionally used mobile application services with a low satisfaction level than branch interactions. However, the same report article also highlighted that online banking registration rose by 200%, leading to a marked increase in mobile banking traffic by 85% in the USA. The digital change occurred almost overnight as the pandemic shut down banks, given that this global pandemic has altered the way people banking.

In the same vein, Marous (2020) claims that banks and credit unions have slowed the spread of the virus by preventing the need for most in-person services; hence, the banking industry has helped consumers stay safe and manage the effects of an economic recession. In addition, building a new digital experience played an essential role in helping customers regulate their budget, manage debt, and effectively use new government programs.

Nevertheless, Bensley *et al.* (2020) believe that customers quickly switched to digital platforms because of the global crisis; however, the digital transformation is not complete, neither for banks nor consumers. To deliver better solutions tailored to their unique needs, the customer expects companies to incorporate data insights. Therefore, financial institutions need to keep moving according to their consumer agenda and embrace digital innovation through new technologies and data advanced analytics to backing enhanced money management, simple engagement and proactive recommendations.

On the other hand, some evidence suggests that banks are subjected to digital disruptions from within and beyond their business models, contributing to innovations in services, products, sales and delivery channels, and business

models. Furthermore, competition with FinTech companies uses BD technologies for digital financial services. For example, Fintech's recent progress in delivering automated digital investing advice using their collected customer profile information shows that FinTech can turn BD into innovative and convincing consumer services. Unless banks can easily offer comparable services, these Fintech firms will likely lose substantial revenue (Tatuev *et al.*, 2020).

1.6.1 Core Problems

BD has been seen as the new oil in the digital economy by amplifying businesses' value creation; this statement portrays BD's importance (Tam *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, as Mikalef *et al.* (2020) pointed out, customers request more first-class, customer-centric, low-cost services through various platforms. Therefore, to offer such personalised services, in-depth holistic knowledge of customers is needed. It can only be done by exploiting all available consumers' data using BD techniques.

Globally, the financial services industry is beginning to harness internal and external resources data to derive interest across various functional realms, ranging from sentiment analysis, regulatory enforcement monitoring, commodity cross-selling, effective risk control, financial fraud monitoring, and much more (Hassani *et al.*, 2018). According to Aasritha *et al.* (2020), extracting the correct information quickly and with low cost from data allows banks to harvest the BD potentials.

As a result, BD is emerging as an instrument for the private sector, governments, and non-government organisations (NGOs) to enhance social and health systems, the environment, and economies (Singh *et al.*, 2019). Hassani *et al.* (2018) pointed out that the banking industry is beginning to reap the BD potential globally. However, BD deployment is in its infancy stage in developing countries (Ali *et al.*, 2016).

Egypt's banking sector has invested heavily in data storage and management systems such as data warehouses and market intelligence for more than a decade. Therefore, questions arise concerning BD's underlying motivations in

this regard. The rapid expansion of BD is driven by several interconnected factors that have resulted in a massive increase of data and the need to make sense of it. So, the following is a brief report on the motivation drivers behind adopting BD in banking:

Technological Evolution: For many years, customer analysis has been around (Smallridge *et al.*, 2020). However, recent evidence suggests that the exponential growth of the IoT users would further erupt the volume of consumer data, resulting in new, persistent data sources, even though consumers do not communicate with the bank or the insurer (Aasritha, Hemavathi and Sujatha, 2020). Also, the adoption of Open Architectures (OA) encourages banks to gather valuable insights from data collected from competitors about their customers (Hernández-Nieves *et al.*, 2020).

Exploit Opportunities: According to Wei (2020), One of the most data-driven sectors in the digital economy is banking. So, BD's influence on the financial industry is unlikely to be overestimated. In Egypt, banks strive to captivate their global competitors, but there is plenty of room for improvement (CBE, 2020).

Given that the banking sector is witnessing unprecedented growth in daily data volume, financial institutions are expediting their efforts to grow revenues with BD. Moreover, with BD evolving, opportunities and challenges are emerging. Deliberations on the BD benefits to banks are acknowledged; therefore, overcoming the BD challenges is crucial. Research at Capgemini (2018) has shown that organisational data silos are the single biggest obstacle to BD performance (Hassani *et al.*, 2018). In essence, Roumeliotis (2019) has identified some considerable uncertainties, including a lack of technical knowledge, high BD costs, and a lack of policy attention on BD.

Lack of Knowledge: BD is at an early stage across sectors overall and predominantly in the banking sector. Nevertheless, several IoT and BD conferences have been held in Egypt. For example, in 2014, the World Bank Community held a conference called Egypt: BD and Urban Mobility, and in 2019, the first world conference on IoT: Technology and future were held in

Cairo, the International Data Corporation (IDC) on Tuesday, 18 June 2019, and the International Conference on Creative Developments in Communications and Computers on 2020 (Saxena, 2018).

Highly Competitive Environment: Leveraging BD in the banking industry in Egypt is in its infancy stage. As data (Volume, velocity and variety) continue to develop, so does the opportunities for banking in Egypt, but the essential part is to cultivate the value of these data to improve overall performance and gain a competitive advantage. Egyptian banks prefer to utilise olden techniques and not current technologies when developing a marketing strategy, resulting in several strategic disadvantages (El Banna and Labib, 2019).

The primary problem in this research is that although many studies have been conducted on BD focusing on its opportunities in the banking sector, as far as Egypt is concerned, no or few inquiries have been conducted on BD's relevance in Egypt's banking sector (Khashaba, 2019).

This implies that diverse perspectives on the role of BD and its impact on Egyptian banks should be comprehended to move away from traditional approaches and toward BD-solutions based on new technologies so that the data gathered by banks can be used for previously unimaginable insights into any aspect of their industry. Thus, it creates opportunities for banks to develop, battle fraud, and boost operating performance. Consequently, this study adds to our understanding of the role and relevance of BD in financial services in developing countries in many critical areas.

The aim of this study is, therefore, by using the Egyptian banking sector as an example, to explore and then showcase the emerging role and impact of BD with/in the financial industry in the developing countries, which will help explain the extent of BD and uncover the gap by using a substantive theory.

This problem situation, therefore, generates the research questions that are addressed in this study:

1. What is the academic and industry-based current state of knowledge about BD's role and impact on the banking and finance sector?
2. How is BD constructed by stakeholders in the banking sector in Egypt?
3. What lessons have been learnt from investment in BD in Egypt's banking sector over the last decade?

Table 1-1 Summary the research objectives and questions

Purpose	Research Objectives and Questions	Related-Questions	Data Source
Identify	<p>Objective:</p> <p>To critically review the academic and industry-based current state of knowledge about BD's role and impact on the banking and finance sector.</p> <p>Question:</p> <p>What is the academic and industry-based current state of knowledge about BD's role and impact on the banking and finance sector?</p>	<p>What are the dimensions, evolution, impact, and challenges of the BD?</p> <p>What are the outcome and advantages of BD in business?</p> <p>What are the role and impact of BD in the banking sector?</p> <p>What are the drivers and constraints of using BD in banking?</p> <p>How has BD been used in the financial industry in the developing world?</p>	<p>Academic and industrial-based literature review.</p>
Assess	<p>Objective:</p> <p>To comprehend how BD is constructed by actors of the banking industry of Egypt.</p> <p>Question:</p> <p>How is BD constructed by stakeholders in the banking sector in Egypt?</p>	<p>What is the implication of BD on Business?</p> <p>How BD impacts the banking sector?</p> <p>What are the motivations and drivers for using BD in banking?</p> <p>What are the opportunities and constraints for using BD in the banking sector?</p>	<p>Questionnaire of the stakeholder groups</p>

Develop	<p>Objective:</p> <p>To discuss the lessons learnt from investments in BD in Egypt's banking industry.</p> <p>Question:</p> <p>What lessons have been learnt from investment in BD in Egypt's banking sector over the last decade?</p>	<p>What is BD being used in the banking industry in Egypt?</p> <p>What is the importance of the use of BD in the banking industry in Egypt?</p> <p>What are the challenges and opportunities with BD in the banking sector?</p>	<p>Academic and industrial-based literature review.</p> <p>Questionnaire</p>
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Source: Researcher

Figure 1-1 Researcher Mind-Mapping

Source: Researcher

2 Chapter Two: Literature Review

2.1 Introduction

The initial literature search identified what had been published in the literature on BD and its impact on business. At that time, the researcher focused on undertaking an overall evaluation of the current literature, not a thorough analysis. Intending to do so, the author started to shape introductory theoretical sensitivity to the subject area, defined gaps in knowledge and determined a legitimate need to undertake the study (Timonen *et al.*, 2018).

By drawing on the concept of Grounded Theory methodology (GT), Charmaz (2006) has shown that several grounded theorists purposely postpone this form of preliminary literature review and pause for data collection and interpretation to avoid preconceived ideas. However, in preparation for the Ethics Committee review, a preliminary literature appraisal was required to determine the study proposal's research problem. Therefore, the researcher agreed with the view of methodically GT, which concede that a preliminary literature review would augment work readiness, considering continuous reflectivity prohibits preconceived theories from being put into reality (Bryant *et al.*, 2019).

Existing literature on BD in Egypt's banking industry also stated that other studies did not address research questions to check the research originality. Although this study is organised accordingly in subsequent chapters, the GT study is not a linear procedure. Thus, the literature discussed in this chapter aggregates publications collected during the entire research project period throughout the initial, ongoing and revised literature searches. Although during those later searches, the concepts and themes discussed in the literature were chosen later in the compilation and review of data, it was proposed that to keep the theory formulation oriented and dependent on data would be necessary (Glaser, 2007).

Furthermore, given the ongoing growth of BD approaches, publications from 2015 onwards are the subject of the literature review addressed in this section. Similarly, BD's financial sector's increasing interest surpassed this study's scope of academic publications; therefore, industry-based literature such as

conferences, annual reports, and white papers was included in this study. Empirical data notice and functional implementation of the BD provided by industry experts have become necessary in the theoretical literature.

Consequently, the purpose of this chapter is to critically review the current literature on the role and influence of BD on the banking and financial sectors. Fred *et al.* (2008) recommend that funnel writing techniques produce a reasonable analogy for the literature review's shape. Therefore, this chapter presents general information first, then specific information examined last. The chapter is organised in five themes: Defining and Exploring BD; Business Impact of BD; Role of BD in Banking, BD and Finance in Developing Countries, BD and Banking in Egypt, and Research Gaps.

Figure 2-1 The funnel structure for this chapter

Source: Based on Fred *et al.* (2008) notion

2.2 Defining and Exploring BD

To capture BD's essence and propose a comprehensive definition, tracing BD origin and history are crucial. Many studies have been conducted on the history and developments of BD. Based on Rider's work (Rider, 1944), Gil Press (2013) provided a thorough brief of BD's history starting from 1944. The article covered BD's evolution between 1944 and 2013; it illustrated 32 events related to BD

developments. The article also highlighted the blurred line between the exponential increase of data and the development of BD. The report of Gil Press (2013) covered both data science and BD evolution; to this point, data science is well-thought-out as a matching connotation to BD. Since then, there have been many relevant BD events.

In contrast to the review of Gil Press, Bernard Marr (2015) stressed the importance of BD's historical foundation, wherein diverse approaches to capture. Furthermore, Marr (2015) traced BD origin back to 18,000 BCE: the longest span of BD historical reviews, and claimed that BD was first cast in 1989 in an article presented by Erik Larson in The Washington Post. In the same vein, by contrast to Gil Press's review, Ohlhorst (2012) believed that in the 19th century, statistics was a real issue, and the first use of BD could be traced to 1880 when the 10th US survey was held.

In comparison, Lohr (2013) claims that it is not about the volume of generated data but the various modern approaches. Therefore, the object of exploring the origin of BD is not merely to locate an early reference to the first use of the word but to locate the first use of the BD that implies its present connotation.

Based on the previous argument, Cox *et al.* (1997) considered the first nominators of BD term that reflect today's connotation because they gave a comparatively synopsis of connotation of BD. Thus, Cox *et al.* (1997, p. 1) stated:

“Data sets are generally quite large, taxing the capacities of main memory, local disk and even remote disk. We call this the problem of BD. When data sets do not fit in main memory (in core), or when they do not fit even on a local disk.” (Cox *et al.*, 1997, p. 1)

Evidence suggests that even though the term BD has become widespread, there is no universal agreement about what it means. Therefore, to eliminate the ambiguity of the BD definition and make the concept more accurate and meaningful, Copi *et al.* (1998) approaches are used for investigating and understanding the functions of BD definition, so grounded on Irving Cohen and McMahon's approaches, first, the lexical meaning of BD is extracted through

investigating the historical definition from an evolutionary viewpoint. After that, to add more attributes to the BD terminology, a stipulative meaning is examined to extend the BD term based on its motivation.

2.2.1 The Lexical Meaning of BD

Gartner's interpretation (3Vs): Since 1979, several characteristics have been added to BD. The most cited and adopted three data traits, “volume, velocity, and variety”, which Gartner assimilated in 2004. 3Vs, the term was the first cast in a white paper by Douglas Laney in 2001 (Laney, 2001).

Because of the surging of e-commerce activities, Laney (2001) noted that data had augmented three dimensions: Volume, speed, and data generation types. Moreover, 3Vs have been extensively viewed as BD's common traits (Mahdavinejad *et al.*, 2018; Saggi *et al.*, 2018; Ma *et al.*, 2020).

IBM's definition (4Vs): Veracity, as another attribute which IBM added. 4Vs: Volume refers to the data voluminous; velocity signifies the scrutiny of data flowing; variety denotes the diverse data types; and veracity means data quality (Al-Sai *et al.*, 2019).

Yuri Demchenko's (5Vs): Yuri proposed the 5Vs BD definition by adding the value dimension to IBM's BD definition (Demchenko *et al.*, 2013).

Microsoft's definition (6Vs): Like IBM, three more attributes to Laney's 3Vs attribute variability, veracity, and visibility, to make the most value of a business.

Therefore, to articulate the aspects of data, there have been many additional Vs. Although these definitions were data-oriented, Marr (2015a) argued that they failed to articulate what BD is associated with the essence of business. So, to understand the BD meaning, it is essential to illuminate what data is. According to Trabucchi *et al.* (2019), data is everything within the universe, and everything people do in daily life enhances the data generation process.

Smartphones and intelligent gadgets generate big data from users' behaviours, e.g., listening to music, running, shopping, and a shortlist to be prolonged to every moment in everyday life.

The data is then analysed to search for actionable intelligence, generating new data that leads to a continuous data production chain. Trabucchi *et al.* (2019) found that the main reason for capturing these data is to add a little value for decision-makers and provide innovative solutions for business problems. Notwithstanding, the above definitions offered one characteristic of BD; a comprehensive definition could become complicated.

Figure 2-2 BD definitions

Source: Buyya *et al.* (2016)

2.2.2 The Stipulative Meaning of BD

Lynn *et al.* (2015) demonstrated that BD's principle is to advance: Hindsight, the emerging patterns from historical data insight: comprehending the issues; and foresight, the accurate forecast for the future in a profitable means. Nevertheless, many definitions have abandoned such relevant BD characteristics. To a certain extent, Whitaker (2018) echoed the above conclusion and argued that many BD definitions focus only on either data

aspects or single-issue. Therefore, it is crucial to consider all characteristics from different aspects to reflect all characteristics of BD.

BD (3Vs): This is the first BD definition that referred to Laney (2001), “3Vs: *volume, velocity, and variety*”. This BD definition was widely cited in 2001 (Bhaduri *et al.*, 2016; Hassani, Huang *et al.*, 2018; Azmoodeh *et al.*, 2019). After that, it extended to several Vs such as IBM’s 4Vs, Yuri Demchenko’s 5Vs, Microsoft 6Vs, and up to 11 Vs (Dalla *et al.*, 2018).

BD (Technology): This is a technology-oriented development definition, such as MapReduce, resilient datasets (Spark), and NoSQL (Dawei, Anzi and Gen, 2018).

BD (Application): This definition highlights the diverse applications of BD. Connolly *et al.* (2013) looked for data hindsight, focusing on analysing observation data, transactions, and interactions. Nevertheless, Devlin *et al.* (2012) distinguished BD as an application of the data process; machine-generated and human-sourced data.

BD (Signal): The concept is application-oriented, although it emphasises timing rather than data types. It looks for a new pattern signal in datasets (Härdle *et al.*, 2018).

BD (Opportunity): This definition highlights BD potentials opportunities by using new technologies to analyse the archived data ignored due to technology limitations (Kitchin, 2014).

BD (Metaphor): This definition elevates BD to a new level by considering BD as an extension of the human thinking process rather than an analytics tool (Japkowicz and Stefanowski, 2016).

BD (A New Term For Traditional Data Analytics): This definition uses the BD term to replace the traditional data analytics terms such as Business Intelligence (BI) and Data Mining (DM) (Singh *et al.*, 2020).

Notwithstanding, whereas there are many studies on BD, there is no agreement on BD’s concept. Notably, there is a degree of uncertainty around the word ‘Big’,

emphasising the data volume (Bunnik *et al.*, 2016). However, from the evolutionary perception, the size of BD is constantly evolving. Furht *et al.* (2016) reported that BD is ill-defined and has a pretty vague definition; this shows a need to be unambiguous about what is meant by BD. Even though data management has progressed expressively since the 1800s, advancements have been made in recent years, making data management more efficiently attainable.

BD Characteristics: In 2001, Douglas Laney published a white paper where the 3Vs definition acknowledged that data has fully-fledged in three dimensions: Volume; reflects data volume, speed; reflects data speed and diversity; reflects the variety of data formats (Laney, 2001).

Consequently, veracity (suggests reliability of data sources) was added by IBM 4Vs definition of BD. Similarly, in Microsoft 6Vs, two more Vs were added; variability (refers to the dataset's complication) and visibility (underlines all data details to the decision-making process). However, in 2013 the dimension value was added to update the IBM from 4Vs to 5Vs (Fahad Akhtar, 2018). According to Singh *et al.* (2019), more dimensions were added later to articulate BD's aspect and based on the data-oriented characterisations. Therefore, seeking a better solution to the business or research problem is the primary justification for using BD.

Nevertheless, Raj *et al.* (2018) assert that regardless of the high volume, fast velocity, wide variety are unnecessary. What matters is the added value given to the decision-maker by BD data-driven analysis. It has commonly been assumed that BD is a challenge because of the cost of extracting this value.

However, the emerging pattern of the above evolution of BD definition suffers from severe limitations by describing specific matters from only one characteristic of BD. There is some evidence to suggest that there is a need to be explicit about quite what is meant by the word BD, and a comprehensive BD definition can become multifaceted; So, Popper (2005) used rational reconstruction technique to solve this issue, the following table highlights the

most common BD definitions from the motives behind processes, practice, and decision.

Table 2-1 Summary of seven BD definitions

No	Type of BD	Description
1	3Vs	Volume, velocity and variety – White paper by Douglas Laney in 2001 (Laney, 2001)
2	Technology	It was adapted by new technology development like (MapReduce, RDD and Spark) (Sahal <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
3	Application	Applications differed based on BD forms, system data, human-sourced data, and machine-generated data (Isik, 2018).
4	Signals	The application-oriented definition focuses on a new signal pattern in the datasets (Cheng <i>et al.</i> , 2018).
5	Opportunity	It highlights the potential opportunities by returning to the same datasets when new technology is released—BD utilising ignored data as technology limitations (Marda, 2018).
6	Metaphor	BD is seen as an extension of human thinking (Gupta <i>et al.</i> , 2018).
7	New Terminology	Business intelligence (BI), data mining, and traditional data analysis tools were all replaced by BD as a new nomenclature. (Quinto, 2018).

Source: Researcher

The previous review of seven BD meanings throughout the last four decades; however, as argued by (Yu *et al.*, 2020), it needs to be clear about the notion of the word BD entails, especially in the banking sector. Hence, this study leans toward adopting the BD opportunity definition. Therefore, to clearly understand this approach, the following section discusses Making Sense of BD.

2.2.3 Making Sense of BD

It has been reported that two primary data sources contribute to creating BD: Machine-generated, which can generate data produced by devices and programmes. For example, the data generated by the point of sale, location (Balas *et al.*, 2019); However, human interaction with the systems generates Human-generated data like cell phones, digital devices, and online services (Lopez *et al.*, 2018).

BD generated from different sources represented diverse data types. Thus, this section highlights the various data types that are analysed by BD solutions. There are four fundamental data types: Metadata, Structured, Semi-Structured, and Unstructured data (Ravat *et al.*, 2019).

Metadata: Offers structure and characteristics information about data sets crucial for BD processes (storage, processing, and analysis) (Solodovnikova, Niedrite and Niedritis, 2019). Rossetto *et al.* (2019) argue that metadata tracking is significant since it offers raw data during BD processing. Metadata is mostly machine-generated; XML tags and file attributes are examples of metadata.

Structured Data: It is generally believed that the predefined data in a relational database is structured data. Bonetta *et al.* (2019) noted that machines or humans could generate this data from many sources, including companies' applications and internal databases. Due to the nature of this data type, which is natively supported by many databases and applications, it occasionally needs detailed deliberation to storing or analysing the data. Nevertheless, several attempts have been made to increase tension amid the ease of processing structured data than a more challenging analysis of unstructured data (Hatef *et al.*, 2019). Typical data applications contain sales transactions, inventory control, and airline booking system (Li *et al.*, 2018).

On the other hand, the organisations' term "dark data" encompasses operational data but has never been used. While Trajanov *et al.* (2018) argue that not using such data is an untainted detriment to an organisation, Dinesh *et al.* (2018) assert that dark data could optimise business processes, marketing strategy, security and more.

Semi-Structured Data: It has been used to refer to structured data that does not pursue the relational databases' structure models. Tsirogiannis *et al.* (2017) noted that this data is produced mainly by computers or humans. Nevertheless, the layout of semi-structured data requires identifiers for semantic elements and field structures and documents inside the data. According to Mirzaie *et al.* (2019), semi-structured data is generally stored in a

file containing text and has a typical pre-pressing example for semi-structured data (spreadsheets, sensor data).

Unstructured Data: It has been reported as the data stored within the non-rational database, frequently generated from human's activities. Gupta *et al.* (2018) argued that unstructured data make up 80% of any enterprise data. According to Quinto (2018), unstructured data's growth rate is higher than structured data. There are likely many common unstructured data types (text, social media posting, image, audio, and video). Although unstructured data cannot be stored or processed in relational databases, alternatively unstructured data use a non-relational database to process this type of data (Lee, 2017).

So far, this section has reviewed the different types of BD. However, Saggi *et al.* (2018) maintain that the importance of turning this data into actionable insights is arguable and occurs through data analytics. Therefore, the following section explores the different data analytics techniques used to extract meaningful information.

The term data analytics is generally understood as the lifecycle of the data management process. Van Rijmenam *et al.* (2019) reported that the data analytics lifecycle includes collecting, cleaning, forming, storing, data analysis, and data governance. Antons *et al.* (2018) argue that data analytics tools and techniques have been developed to allow data processing through huge data capacities from different sources. However, Rialti, Zollo, *et al.* (2019) acknowledged that generating high-value analytics results upsurges the cost and effort of the BD analytics environment.

In the same vein, according to Kahneman (2011), a business decision can be based on factual data (Slow system) and not merely on intuition (Fast system). Therefore, Deshpande *et al.* (2019) highlighted that to empower data-driven decisions, BD analytics with systematic backing use four analytics categories; descriptive, diagnostic, predictive, and prescriptive. For that, the following section briefly explains the four main BD analytics categories.

The research method that uses past and current data to address incidents that have already occurred is descriptive analytics. Härdle *et al.* (2018) found that it is estimated that 80% of the results generated from analytics are naturally descriptive.

Diagnostic analytics aims to answer the question that emerged from the descriptive analysis using questions that focus on the cause of a phenomenon in the past (Aiello *et al.*, 2019). In other words, diagnostic analytics regulates why something has happened (Liao and Chen, 2019).

Likewise, descriptive analytics, predictive analytics are based on current and historical data. Nonetheless, Doleck *et al.* (2020) concluded that predictive analytics has a different approach to determining future outcomes. It has commonly been assumed that predictions are based on trends, patterns, and exceptions in the current and historical data, leading to opportunities and risks identification (Muthukrishnan *et al.*, 2018; Doleck *et al.*, 2020).

Consequently, prescriptive analytics, according to Deshpande *et al.* (2019), the results of predictive analytics predefine their purpose as to improve processes and structures of the systems through prescribing action based on predictive analytics. In other words, what should an organisation do base on a knowledgeable estimation of the future? Though Lepenioti *et al.* (2020) argue that prescriptive analytics is the furthestmost effective in creating value from data insights, prescriptive analytics move from an analytical to a consultative approach. It is believed that it provides more valuable outcomes compared to the other types of analytics.

So far, this section sheds light on the types of data and how an organisation could leverage the data insights and has highlighted that an organisation should engage in all four data analytics types. Notwithstanding, Ghasemaghaei *et al.* (2019) maintain that it is not about the data volume; it is about the data quality, which raises an argument about the data governance standards as deliberated in the next section.

Data Governance: The data standards emerged from the recent developments in BD sources. The investigation of Sivarajah *et al.* (2017) has

shown that as the organisations grow, the data correlated with them increases exponentially, posing several challenges related to their data, leading to a considerable challenge. This challenge heightened the need for quality control measures to guarantee that data sources abide by the data standards (Pugna *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, Khan *et al.* (2019) argued that in addition to the BD characteristics (significant volumes, variety of formats and high velocity), other dimensions occurred from storing and processing BD such as security, ethics, policies and governance.

Concerning governance, there are many definitions of data governance. For example, Akhtar (2018) concludes that information governance is a framework of decision rights and accountability that inspires desirable behaviour to use, archive, delete, store, create, and evaluate information in order to certify an organisation's efficient and effective use of information in order to achieve its goals. Correspondingly, Data Governance Institute (2020) explains that data-related systems' transparency and policy rights are data governance.

So, Al-Badi *et al.* (2018) outlined BD governance as part of holistic data governance, representing data's optimisation, secrecy, monetisation, and profitability strategy. Recent evidence suggests that BD technology and skillsets differ from those used with traditional data (Dawei *et al.*, 2018). Yamada *et al.* (2017) proposed a high-level BD governance framework containing three critical BD dimensions: information governance and industries. Subsequently, A survey conducted by Ge *et al.* (2018) has shown that organisations need to start with a BD governance framework to confirm integration, administration, data access, usage and possession of BD. Therefore, Companies need to develop their current information governance programme to comprise BD.

This section highlights the diverse applications and categories where BD is utilised. The following table shows some BD applications in different industries.

Table 2-2 Summary of BD application in diverse industries

Industry	BD application
Government	Public services, tax, social security, environmental protection, energy, power investigation (Bauer, 2016; Dalla <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Lim <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Education	Students 'performance tracking, guidance, real-time feedback, learning materials improving, student assessment (B <i>et al.</i> , 2018; Muthukrishnan, Yasin and Govindasamy 2018, Pugna, Duşescu and Stanila 2019)
Healthcare	Diseases prediction, medical cost reduction, efficient drug analysis, preventive care improvement, eradicate diseases risk factors (Trajanov <i>et al.</i> 2017; Saggi <i>et al.</i> 2018, Liao <i>et al.</i> , 2019)
Transportation	Routes forecasting, congestion management, better fare management, intelligent transportation systems, intelligent route planning, traffic control, transportation technological improvement, competitive fares and responsive fare response (Arputhamary <i>et al.</i> , 2015; Karthik <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Moshirpour <i>et al.</i> , 2017)
Retail	Tailored Products, digital data storage, customer satisfaction, customer forecasting (Hill <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Nikolopoulos <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Entertainment	Target audience, content management systems, content performance assessment (Liao <i>et al.</i> 2019; Ziegler, 2019)
Energy	Analysing consumer usage and behaviour, energy security and climate change data management, smart metering (Janssen <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Ge <i>et al.</i> , 2018)
Industrial	Utility consumption analysis, text and graphical analysis (Karthik <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Kim, 2018; Lea, 2018)
Financial Services	Risk management, cost reduction, customer statistics adjustment, debit cards, credit cards, competitor's analysis, business analysis, customer behaviour analysis, fraud detection, target markets (Denyes <i>et al.</i> , 2016, Moshirpour <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Siddiqui <i>et al.</i> , 2017; Mcwaters <i>et al.</i> , 2018)

Source: Researcher

Table 2.2 shows an overview of how diverse businesses have responded to the call of leveraging BD in different ways. For example, while manufacturing is streamlining operations by recording and refining equipment calibration, retailers collect as much data about consumers to effectively fulfil their changing needs (Trabucchi *et al.*, 2019). In the same vein, every industry learns how to reap the BD potentials, which urges the need to find innovative methods of collecting, storing, analysing, and interpreting data. Rehman *et al.* (2019) argue that organisations provide more innovative services and products and improve their performance using BD solutions. The following section describes BD's business

impact, motivates and drives organisations across different industries to adopt BD to deliver value in diverse areas.

2.3 Business Impact of BD

BD refers to large, diverse data sets that, when analysed computationally, possibly will show trends, patterns and correlations, particularly regarding human behaviour and interactions (Fu *et al.*, 2020). So, this section discusses how BD impacts business and why it is essential.

Corporations, private agencies, governments, police, and political parties eventually spend time and money leveraging data power. Today, there is a widespread perception that data has become the new currency, which can yield dividends, if processed, mined, and analysed appropriately (Pugna *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, organisations need to invest in transforming their data asset into money using BD development methods. At the same time, it is crucial to see how businesses can use analytics or BD resources. However, it may be risky in the sense that companies may not be adequately prepared for the use of BD solutions (Hammer *et al.*, 2017; Mirzaie *et al.*, 2019).

Thus, it is vital to recognise how data is becoming essential in shifting the course of action for various departments. For example, law enforcement authorities use data to forecast crime and develop prevention strategies (Hårdle *et al.*, 2018). It is used by political parties to win election campaigns. Sporting coaches use data to grasp opponents' strategies; it is not about data volume but about seeing what is in the data and making knowledgeable decisions about shaping businesses and life (Marr, 2016).

Moreover, data has become the guiding torch for companies that have lost their way in recent years to digital disruption. It is the only weapon that can battle its way against start-ups. According to Schaeffer *et al.* (2020), BD embracing companies can bound the curve ahead of their rivals, as firms can cross-sell and upsell to their clients efficiently, harnessing the power of BD analytics. Using social networks, SMS banking, communication to offer 24/7 on-the-go banking services is an example of enterprise-led data-driven decision making (Hassani *et al.*, 2018).

In essence, a look into the complexities of the market, BD could provide companies with a suitable collection of insights into their data, synchronising well with their staff, partners, and clients. According to Bonderud (2019), by 2021, the internet users reach 4.8 billion users and 5G; hence, IoT will play a significant role as the world enters the multi-zettabytes. Companies, particularly the new-age companies that are 100 per cent tech-driven, have started leveraging BD to take advantage early. This move gives organisations an advantage edge (Lambrecht *et al.*, 2015). Analytical, prescriptive, and preventive insights are much more robust in coping with any scenario, whether good, bad or worse, as their decisions are not guided by emotions but made using evidence.

Moreover, Schaeffer *et al.* (2020) appraised that BD is increasingly becoming a core component of an organisation's strategy, mainly because it is all about innovation, discovering new insights about consumers, operations or the market. As a result, BD is increasingly seen as a fundamental building block of competitive advantage; if a business does have the data and the resources, equipment and culture to exploit it and produce innovative products and services, all of its competitors would be severely disadvantaged (Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019).

There should be ample debate on whether all types of data are helpful or not. Nevertheless, most experts would tell that business performance factors are deep inside the Internet's free domains (Moshirpour *et al.*, 2017).

In essence, BD is being used extensively by various companies to outperform competitors. Business is adopting data-centric strategies to overcome the competition, from existing companies to start-ups (Lin *et al.*, 2020). The use of suitable analytical instruments is what is most required to access those abilities. These resources would discover data for the growth of companies (Gepp *et al.*, 2018).

Data could influence industries and, if properly processed and evaluated, can deliver unprecedented results. Computer, Internet and mobile data have been implemented by BD, both within and outside the organisation, by those

responsible for the transition to complement their operational data and provide the basis for historical and forward-looking perspectives (Pugna *et al.*, 2019).

Furthermore, According to Moshirpour *et al.* (2017), data means money for all the world's largest online corporations – Google, Amazon or Facebook—who otherwise will cease to exist in the digital economy era. Google, Amazon, and Facebook have been mining data for decades to provide more critical advertisements and tests. There is always a competition between them to learn what the consumer wants and needs before claiming it. In short, data has been their source of revenue.

Therefore, BD has received considerable attention because of its impact on decision-making. However, while many firms have invested or planned to invest in BD, few organisations successfully generated value from it (Palanisamy *et al.*, 2017; Pugna *et al.*, 2019). Furthermore, Trabucchi *et al.* (2019) noted that by using BD, corporations strive to fulfil the required conditions necessary for enhancing corporate efficiency, resulting in a reduction in the number of organisations preparing to invest in BD. However, there is a specific link between BD and organisational efficiency and organisational capabilities (Graham, 2017; Thirathon *et al.*, 2017).

Additionally, Fosso Wamba *et al.* (2015) argument relied too heavily on BD's relevance to performance management. It concluded that BD could provide more detailed performance measurement, business processes automation, better forecasting, and customer insights. Also, in research findings that 140 senior IT specialists empirically validated, Ghasemaghahi (2018) noticed that when companies use BD, corporate performance is best, but this is not the case with businesses that do not employ BD. However, the study found that BD has no significant impact on organisational success in the managerial position of analytical skillset.

Furthermore, in the age of the digital economy, BD has significantly influenced conventional ways of operating a business. For example, BD skills have typically been thought to enable managers to be aware of the status of supply chain systems, internal procedures, and customer behaviour (Srivastava *et al.*,

2015). In this way, managers can manage decision-making processes based on the most appropriate strategy to be applied (Joseph *et al.*, 2018; Thorstad and Wolff, 2018; Osman, 2019).

BD solutions have also been used to discover knowledge for performance optimisation, manage risk, and improve business outcomes (Raguseo, 2018). In terms of BD evolving potential for an enterprise, it is noticeable that studies on BD systems and related organisational capacities are needed (Van Rijmenam *et al.*, 2019). According to Arunachalam *et al.* (2017), transform data into insights, organisational performance, and decisions management. However, many scholars believe that maybe only BD systems can manage the complexity of data sets formed by heterogeneous data (Saggi *et al.*, 2018; Akter *et al.*, 2019; Mirzaie *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, BD capabilities are underway to obtain attention concurrently from relevant literature (Akter *et al.*, 2016; Philip, 2018; Côte-Real, Ruivo and Oliveira, 2020).

According to Wang *et al.* (2018), Institutions could encourage managerial capabilities to utilise BD solutions. Consequently, there is some evidence to suggest that BD is linked to organisational performance when it comes to flexibility and agility (Ghasemaghahi *et al.*, 2015; Gunasekaran *et al.*, 2017). With such capabilities, an organisation might be able to gain a competitive advantage. Moreover, it has been reported that BD was pragmatically influenced by value creation processes (Shirazi *et al.*, 2018; Sigala, Rahimi *et al.*, 2019).

Concerning Knowledge Management (KM), there is a connection between data, information and knowledge. Understating this critical distinction is crucial in information flows and managing knowledge (Ge *et al.*, 2018). BD incessantly influences tacit knowledge with its characteristics and offers a valuable and influential instrument for decision success. So, KM systems and agility differentiates the data-driven business from those that have not harnessed the power of data (Ghasemaghahi *et al.*, 2015).

Many organisations are adopting BD analytics for knowledge discovery. For example, Sivarajah *et al.* (2017) described BD analytics as investigating

datasets to explore patterns, correlations, and predictions. Data mining, machine learning, and predictive analytics are advanced analytic tools employed by BD analytics. Also, many industries have conducted BD analytics. For example, the Google flu service that detects flu eruptions can decrease influenza (Rothman, 2018). Other industries like insurance, retail, healthcare can experience productive outcomes. Additionally, BD analytics allows an organisation to improve innovation, where firms correctly know what innovation will succeed and invest in and understand consumer behaviour and needs. Consequently, companies will be more able to identify the most profitable customers (Hilbert, 2016; Rothman, 2018; Urbinati *et al.*, 2019).

Moreover, the increasing interest in BD led many organisations to develop BD analytics capability (BDAC), to improve organisational performance. With the increasing volume of data, efficiently utilising this data became crucial. However, managers are experiencing challenges to convert this data into valuable information. Actionable knowledge has gained increasing importance from research and practical viewpoint, as converting BD into wisdom requires a knowledge creation framework (Motamarri *et al.*, 2017). Erl *et al.* (2016) proposed the DIKW pyramid to illustrate a wise knowledge creation integration.

Figure 2-3 The knowledge creation pyramid (DIKW)

Source: Erl *et al.* (2016, p. 45)

BD has altered the sophisticated way of running a business, particularly management science. Simultaneously, the synthesis within the literature

delivers more profound intuitions on achieving value over BD implementation. There is, however, a shortage of academic and scientific data to assess the relevance of BD to the business (Akter *et al.*, 2016, 2019; Arunachalam *et al.*, 2017). Since BD can transform the whole business process, it is crucial to understand the impact of BD. Furthermore, BD has become the focus of organisations and academics research because of its potential, particularly in creating business value (Shirazi *et al.*, 2018; Trabucchi *et al.*, 2019). More recent attention has focused on providing BD capabilities of changing rivalry through transforming processes, facilitating innovation, and releasing innovative organisation capabilities and value (Halaweh, 2015; Pugna *et al.*, 2019).

Current research by Olteanu *et al.* (2019) shows that 50% of respondents report an essential change in their business, reducing costs by 49% and creating new avenues for innovation by 44%, by investing in BD analytics in 2018 is 5.3 billion USD expecting increasing to be 19.4 billion by 2026. According to Goh and Arenas (2020), BD can generate exceptional value for the public sector, economy, productivity and competitiveness.

Additionally, Van Rijmenam *et al.* (2019) emphasised that BD can improve performance metrics and enhance firm operations, transforming decision-making. On the other hand, few empirical and academic studies have evaluated BD's actual potential. Therefore, despite the extant interest in BD, big potential adopters are stressed to comprehend the BD concept and create value for the business (Osman, 2019).

In the internet of things (IoT) and 5G era, intelligently joining people, processes, data and things to handle such exponential data growth, the information technology industry has incessantly advanced tools and models (Balas *et al.*, 2019). Hence, plenty of platforms exist to analyse BD, which targets the volume of data and its speed as crucial for the timely decision-making process (Ge *et al.*, 2018).

Even so, much of the recent BD analytics literature makes a significant contribution to data value extraction, since there are many modern BD storage

and analysis techniques, finding the right tools is a challenge (Mikalef *et al.*, 2018; Shirazi *et al.*, 2018; Trabucchi *et al.*, 2019). Another challenge is training IT personnel to gain the skills they need to operate with equipment. For example, Furht *et al.* (2016) recommended no traditional BD architecture review when selecting the correct methods. However, though choices rely on the data to be examined, the new open-source systems are a diverse analysis area (Tchagna Kouanou *et al.*, 2018).

2.3.1 Business Drivers for BD

Data proliferates in every business because of the rapid expansion of cloud computing and the internet. As a result, BD has been considered an innovation developed over the past decade (Trabucchi *et al.*, 2019). Nonetheless, there is a limited understating of how organisations can bring about economic and social value by leveraging BD (Van Rijmenam *et al.*, 2019).

Erl *et al.* (2016) indicated three factors: BD creation consumers' primary drivers, automation, and monetisation. Consumers, the rapid rise in information level has created a new type of consumers. These consumers are more connected by using social media to bring together and organise opinions from others. The digital world has become more personalised by tracking the online users' social media behaviour and search engines to provide personalised content (Shinde *et al.*, 2015). Notwithstanding, according to Sedunov (2020), there is a fair amount of data about customers generated by applications and social networks. The data can be organised and analysed to modify customer experiences more personalised and making self-service friendlier.

In the past decade, marketing and sales have benefited from internet-driven automation. Moreover, this automation has provided great control to the users and a tremendous amount of buyer behaviour information to the product, sales, and marketing organisations (Gökalp *et al.*, 2017). Concerning monetisation, Urbinati *et al.* (2019) highlighted a new trend in the marketplace that has been established, in which collection and selling consumer information and experience from one industry to other industries occur.

On the other hand, Akter *et al.* (2019) identified three reasons for business justifications to starting the BD initiative. Firstly, data-driven innovation: where organisations can learn from customers to drive innovation through those uber data indicators. Secondly, data-driven decision-making uses science to back the decision, whether discovering the best direction to authenticating the existing route and approximating the success/failure in the current strategy. Thirdly, data-driven discovery: comprehending hidden data insights that were not noticeable through traditional methods by providing a data discovery mechanism (Bhaduri *et al.*, 2016; Medtronic, 2019).

Additionally, by drawing on the concept of competitive advantage, Alharthi, Krotov and Bowman (2017) have shown that businesses could build sustainable capabilities to add to their competitive edge with a proper data-driven strategy. Also, a business can launch a secondary source of income by selling these capabilities to other industries. Finally, in terms of sustainable processes as a driver of BD adoption, it is evident that BD using measurable statistical models reduces risks (Gandomi *et al.*, 2015; Verma *et al.*, 2017).

A Strategic Approach to BD: Decision-making process has three levels within BD: operational, tactical, and strategic. An organisation needs to reflect on how BD can contribute to all decision-making process levels. These data-driven decisions can vary as short-term, medium-term, and long-term (Farah, 2016). Unhelkar (2017) asserts that BD can be used strategically to augment collaboration within the firm and harvest data insights beyond its boundaries to create business value. Moreover, based on various sources, the author outlines the many methods for extracting BD value, a fundamental strategic approach for transforming persons, corporate processes, and innovations.

Also, BD adoption, as with any strategic change, is probable to be realised as a series of incremental changes allied with the general organisational approach. This incremental approach requires persistence and constancy to take advantage of the innovative opportunities that occurred from the BD application (Côte *et al.*, 2020). Furthermore, Wang *et al.* (2016) discussed BD implementation success when workers and senior management see tangible business and financial advantages. Finally, BD promises to utilise corporate

decision-making to necessitate a strategic solution to the BD implementation (Alharthi *et al.*, 2017). However, this strategic approach to adopting BD means to convert hidden potential from dynamically changing data into dynamic business value (Shinn *et al.*, 2017).

2.3.2 Opportunities and Challenges of BD

Opportunities: Managers will gain insights into the decision-making process, as it is widely assumed that BD is predisposed to offer good results for all potential barriers. Zomaya *et al.* (2017) contended that BD is helpful for the performance management of business processes and could influence internal organisational operations. Coherently, BD may also improve workforce utilisation and offer managers better monitoring of each employee's performance (Dawei *et al.*, 2017; Raj *et al.*, 2018; Côte *et al.*, 2020). Moreover, BD possibly impacts an organisation's ability to recognise novel opportunities and advance explorations capabilities, proving that BD prompts competitiveness (Sarkar, 2015; Bhaduri and Fogarty, 2016; D. P. Mehta and Sahni).

Various arguments have been concerning BD challenges and opportunities during the past few years (Yang *et al.*, 2017). In terms of BD opportunities, recent evidence suggests that data generated from both humans and machines have become embedded in the contemporary being's life, changing our way of living and working (Tunguz *et al.*, 2016; Duan *et al.*, 2019). Nevertheless, Rialti *et al.* (2019) argue that data would be the next frontier for productivity and competition, while Özdemir *et al.* (2018) assert that data would be the new science epistemologies. Additionally, Siddiqui *et al.* (2017) defend the view that BD will be a foundation of new economies innovation and value. So, conclude that the large datasets of human behaviour can transform designing cities, performing research, and fighting diseases.

Furthermore, most government organisations and businesses use extensive data to advance what they do and how they do it (Bauer, 2016). Several studies investigating BD have delivered tangible value (Unhelkar, 2017; Saggi *et al.*, 2018; Liao *et al.*, 2019; Mahmoud *et al.*, 2019). Organisations across traditional

and online industries are using BD solutions to deliver value in diverse areas. For example, governments are employing BD to foil terrorists, companies also leverage BD potential to predict consumer behaviours, and corporates use BD to enhance organisational performance and use BD for better decisions in manufacturing, sports, research, and health care (Thirathon *et al.*, 2017). So far, several studies have linked the new storage capabilities and real-time data discovery with business operations deeper insights (Olson *et al.*, 2018; Saggi *et al.*, 2018; Trabucchi *et al.*, 2019).

Likewise, concerning the BD business value, Wang *et al.* (2016) suggested that BD is at the high ends of both business difficulty and value. While Furht *et al.* (2016) assumed that BD analytics is the critical path to business value, Pugna *et al.* (2019) emphasised that discovering new business opportunities comes through data exploration, which leads to new facts about a business, such as customer insights, and costs root causes and new customer base segments.

A study that sets out to determine the organisational benefits from embarking on BD utilisation, Fuller (2017) found that using BD would accumulate many business benefits such as decision-making improvement and enhanced business performance to advance collaboration integrating understandings on recognised business opportunities. Others emphasised the new business opportunities arising from BD embarking; Chedrawi *et al.* (2018) are a proponent of the possibilities that emerge from unstructured data mining, such as contact machine-to-machine, audio pictures, and movies.

Challenges: Several scholars believe that BD is profitable for business and society (Kunst, 2015; Raj *et al.*, 2018; Saggi *et al.*, 2018). Nonetheless, it fetches challenges to the scientific communities. For example, despite developing AI and ML algorithms and intelligent tools, evidence suggests that the existing traditional systems cannot manage BD (Duan *et al.*, 2019). On the other hand, different businesses seek to change to data-driven business by collecting as much data as likely to achieve their changing desires more efficiently, despite leveraging BD insights with significant challenges (Bauer, 2016).

As explained earlier, much of the current literature on BD requires particular attention to BD's main three characteristics (volume, velocity, and variety), identified by Laney (2001) as the root of several challenges that businesses encounter in BD initiatives. Sivarajah *et al.* (2017) reported that data storage costs are getting cheaper day by day, allowing individuals and businesses to store more and more data alongside intelligent devices, which are great BD contributors. Besides, it has commonly been assumed that data is increasing faster by the day. Many data sources create different data types due to the legacy information systems that emerge as a challenge (Kunst, 2015; Bühlmann *et al.*, 2016; Zomaya *et al.*, 2017).

Current empirical and theoretical studies have distinguished BD's business value challenge as technical and organisational (Sivarajah *et al.*, 2017). A lack of awareness and acknowledgement of the potential for BD could be absent. Corporations fail to know what BD and what setup is needed to adopt the systems. Results show that waste of many resources and time on a method companies do not have the necessary knowledge on how to use it (Tunguz *et al.*, 2016).

In essence, According to Marr (2016), converting BD into the needed insights is the principal challenge for an organisation. However, many companies failed to have the required systems and external data (Bunnik *et al.*, 2016a). In addition, several researchers have reported that BD cost is one of the main challenges for an organisation when adopting the BD approach. Although there are various open-source frameworks, BD adoption involves many expenses, such as BD solution development, maintenance, new hardware, services, and electricity (Thirathon *et al.*, 2017).

Furthermore, Olson (2018) argued that an organisation could mislead the right BD technology because of the misperception caused by the available number of BD technologies on the market. Most importantly, Ge *et al.* (2018) claimed that skills shortages present a real problem. Therefore, firms need to find individuals with diverse skills who can be involved with the business, recognise the problems, and then determine use cases to solve them.

As explained earlier, it is not about the data is voluminous. However, it is about the quality of the data. Bagha *et al.* (2019) pointed out the difficulty of managing data quality. BD comes from different sources in various formats, leading to data integration problems (Saggi *et al.*, 2018). Additionally, Liu *et al.* (2017) claimed that data security is quite a huge issue, while there is a remarkable development on the BD technologies, security features. However, they are still deserted. By drawing on the concept of anonymity, Raj *et al.* (2018) have shown that, as BD development continues, so do these three BD issues (data security, data discrimination, and data privacy) remain the regulators' priority items. While scholars caution about BD risks and challenges, others highlighted the business opportunities and advantage of using BD solutions (Kunst, 2015, Raj *et al.*, 2018, Pugna *et al.*, 2019).

Comprehensibly, it has been suggested that firms should emphasise BD processes and get insights that could bring about economic value and gain a competitive advantage (Del Vecchio *et al.*, 2017). However, as mentioned before, there are many challenges associated with implementing the organisational challenges section. For example, Ge, Bangui *et al.* (2018) conducted a survey highlighting the difficulties of BD adoption in an organisation. The first problems they identified were technology and infrastructure, where BD rely on computing for network hardware, cloud storage and fast internet connection. Another is the organisational culture change, where BD compound infrastructure depends on complex analytics methods that employees and managers cannot comprehend, generating change resistance that prevents the implementation process (Tunguz *et al.*, 2016).

Finally, recent evidence suggests that employees and managers dealing with BD systems should understate the possible outcomes, infrastructure difficulty, and analysis of utilising BD. To do so, Global FinTech Report (2017) highlights the need for organisation culture change by drawing employees' and managers' attention to the BD capabilities that will result in changing a traditional organisation to a big-data culture organisation so that harvesting BD added-value can be possible (Price Waterhouse Coopers, 2017).

2.3.3 Criticisms of BD

BD has been extensively discussed in various industries, and it is often regarded as one of the most critical technological advances: introducing digital computers in the 1970s, the Internet in the 1990s, and social media networks 2000s (Lin *et al.*, 2020). There has been a steady and persistent growth pattern in the number of dedicated arenas in academia: journals, seminars or conferences, projects and journals on the subject.

BD has many future advantages; it offers new insights into customer behaviour and demonstrates that the company would function more efficiently, predict potential developments, and much more (Surbakti *et al.*, 2020). However, many firms adopt BD without being adequately trained and run right into a pitfall. Here are the eight most popular BD drawbacks:

Algorithms Raising Ethical Concerns: Recent evidence suggests that algorithms drive critical decisions such as which patients are seen or offered insurance. However, algorithmic conclusions are partial and erroneous to guarantee that algorithms promote sound choices in an analysis concerned with creators and consumers of algorithms. Martin (2019) highlighted two factors: First, ignoring or promoting errors is immoral, although errors are unintended. Second, developers can willingly accept responsibility for the algorithm's function in a decision by building opaque algorithms that are difficult to comprehend or regulate in usage.

Not having a Specific Data Purpose: Many businesses tend to invest in BD ventures without a definite end target in mind. Companies follow the BD propaganda and continue to collect information without knowing what to do until it has been obtained (Urbinati *et al.*, 2019). The result is hence market loss and consumption of energy, money, and human capital. Before building data, storing or purchasing expensive BI tools, the business needs to consider what to do with BD (Yadegaridehkordi *et al.*, 2020).

Moreover, Datafication has been discussed in terms of its implications on individuals, organisations, and society. Several attempts have been made to generally absent from such analysis is any evaluation of data itself. As a result,

Jones (2019) examined many generally held ideas about data in general and BD in particular. The ramifications of this dataset reconceptualization are thoroughly addressed. There is a difference between the data concept as recorded and data in practice as used. The latter, usually a small and unrepresentative percentage of the former, will significantly impact ratification outcomes.

Only look at their business data: Various businesses do not look through their data, and extracting BDs from other sources will add value. For example, data from social media, online material, and service suppliers may bring valuable insights from external channels to the internal perspective to offer new perspectives (Scholz, 2017).

Not Using the Proper Tools: Many organisations are still using Microsoft Excel as their data warehouse. Unfortunately, the system is anything but efficient, as it consumes many time and resources (Dalla and Kenett, 2018). In addition, Chae (2019) argues that most spreadsheets have bugs, so it takes much time to sort them out. As a result, entire meetings may be missed in analysing the information and testing their authenticity.

On the other hand, it has been asserted that the industry's quick expansion and embrace of BD have pushed the conversation to famous venues, requiring the academic press to catch up. Gandomi and Haider (2015) attempt to provide a more thorough description of BD that includes its distinct and distinguishing traits and a consolidated explanation of BD that combines practitioner and academic definitions. The article focuses on analytics for unstructured data, which makes up 95 per cent of BD.

Therefore, Gandomi and Haider (2015) emphasised the importance of building adequate and fast analytical tools to exploit vast amounts of diverse data in unstructured text, audio, and video forms. The study also emphasises the importance of developing new predictive analytics techniques for large volumes of structured data. In practice, statistical techniques were developed to infer from sample data. The heterogeneity, noise, and massive amount of extensive

structured data, on the other hand, need the creation of computationally efficient methods to avoid severe data hazards such as false correlation.

Not Having the Right Skills: Even when businesses got the infrastructure and the data, there is another problem that organisations do not have the correct data specialists or data scientists. For example, it is essential to provide skilled experts with the exact knowledge to analyse it when building a data warehouse. Mousavidin and Hasani (2019) found that it is also essential to ensure reliable reports. The data scientist is in high demand right now, so most businesses are waiting for a polymath superhero to come in and fix all their business intelligence challenges in one fell jump. The challenge is to get the best teams that complement each other, if possible. It means that the company is agile enough to overcome challenges (Ghasemaghahi, 2020).

Not Complying with Privacy Regulations: BD has many potential advantages but also risks and enticements. Therefore, data must be handled with reverence for privacy. There are all kinds of laws and regulations for these reasons, such as the recently imposed GDPR rules. Therefore, treating and storing personal data should be handled cautiously and comply with all laws and regulations (Wang *et al.*, 2019).

Misinterpretation and Confirmation Bias: When doing research, there may be a tendency to look for results that support the business's search for an answer and leave out anything that does not fit in with preconceived notions. This effect is known as confirmation bias (Mikalef *et al.*, 2020). It is possible to analyse without finding a detailed response. Much of the qualified data processing is done by refuting a conclusion using the so-called null hypothesis. Using BD is about making decisions based on evidence and results, not on emotions and opinions. That is the road to growth and becoming a knowledgeable enterprise (Mertens and Recker, 2020).

Furthermore, the BD era has arrived, and specialists are clamouring for access to the vast amounts of data generated by and about people, things, and connections. According to research by Boyd and Crawford (2012), Various parties disagree on the advantages and disadvantages of analysing genetic

sequences, social media activities, health data, phone records, government data, and other digital footprints left by people. Some believe that, given the emergence of BD as a socio-technical phenomenon, a critical examination of underlying assumptions and biases is required. For that, Boyd and Crawford (2012) offered six provocations to kick off talks about BD, which is a cultural, technical, and philosophical phenomenon based on the intersection of technology, analysis, and mythology that has spawned a variety of utopian and dystopian discourses.

No Measures to Quantify Success: Getting goal-driven metrics is crucial for every BD initiative. Many organisations can now identify actionable data lessons, as they have not set concrete goals from the outset. According to Surbakti *et al.* (2020), although specific metrics are attractive to developers, executive staff have little to no interest. Executive metrics are primarily revenue-driven or business-driven, and this would be held in mind by BD modelling and visualisation.

So far, the business impact of BD has been explored in this section from several business viewpoints. This debate will extend in the next section on BD's use in the financial services sector and what lessons have been learned from BD's use over the last few decades.

2.4 BD in the Financial Industry

As mentioned in the previous chapter, Banking is oversupplied with internal structured data and, evermore, unstructured external data. Voluminous data has increased from exabytes to zettabytes; likewise, data velocity has also changed (Hasan, Popp and Oláh, 2020). In addition, businesses deal with live-streaming updates that generate real-time reports (Sigala *et al.*, 2019). However, this data is essential as a source of valuable insights that can lead to an innovative business decision (Marr, 2015b).

Consequently, the growth of BD significance affects the banking industry. Banking managers convey rising concern about the exponential increase in online-only banks and technological changes. However, it has been reported that there is an excellent deal for positive change in the future (Chedrawi *et al.*,

2018). Therefore, it is essential to learn more about the role of technology in the banking industry.

Both retail and commercial banks with physical branches offer valued financial services to business patrons and customers. However, banks struggle to contend with online-only banks that continue to win market share by providing similar services with higher saving rates and low fees (Silva, 2018). Furthermore, online-only banks offer self-service features through mobile applications, successfully broadening their customer appeal among newer generations (Van, 2018).

In 2016, in a survey conducted by PwC, 81% of the respondents, as banking executives, were concerned about technological change speed. Notably, in the FinTech industry, Peer-to-peer lending is rising exponentially, lending front rather than conventional bank lending that seeks to cope with by offering limited loan networks (Price Waterhouse Coopers, 2017). Furthermore, FinTech refers to speeding financial services, predominantly online-only and mobile companies (Giudici, 2018). PwC global report in 2017 has reported that Fintech is the critical disruption in the banking industry, estimating that over the next five years, 82% (this percentage is diverse from country to country) of businesses expect to have a partnership with FinTech firms.

Furthermore, BD is expected to become of cumulative position to central banks in the years ahead (Erb, 2017). In an article published by the Bank of England, the institution articulates the importance of BD capabilities in developing the inductive analytical approach to complement the traditional deductive approach. The article then concluded that it is vital for central banks to comprehend BD capabilities to change how they operate and the economic structure in ways that might impact employment, economic growth, and financial and monetary stability (Yuan *et al.*, 2020).

Correspondingly, BD solutions have crossed the threshold to the mainstream of central banks and their policymaking. For example, in a survey of 52 worldwide central banks conducted by Glass (2018), more than 60% of the respondents said that there is no clear structure for data governance, which

corroborates with the ideas of Saxena (2018), who suggested that BD plays a progressively important role in guiding and policymaking processes. Another notable result was that 80% of respondents indicated that their central banks focused the BD budget on hardware and software over security and human capital.

The report also states that enough quality is seen as the most significant challenge in collecting and processing data. As a result, new technology has to be adopted that replaces a self-developed platform, Excel and data-based applications reported by less than 40%. Additionally, the most exciting finding was that central banks realise the benefits of BD to monetary policy.

Region	% of respondents	Economic classification	% of respondents
Europe	46	Emerging market	42
Americas	21	Industrial	27
Africa	17	Developing	21
Asia	6	Transition	10
Middle East	6		
Oceania	4		
Total respondents	52	Total respondents	52

Percentages in some tables may not total 100 due to rounding.

Figure 2-4 Profile of respondents

Source: Glass (2018)

2.4.1 Drivers of BD Adoption in Banking

As explained in the last section, the factors that resulted in BD's recent rise create the need to drive value, understand customer behaviour better, improve performance, and gain a competitive advantage. Therefore, this section discusses the drivers to adopting BD in banking: operational cost reduction pressure: banks are forced to advance business efficiency to decrease operational cost because of the low-interest rate and the exceeding rivalry. BD insights can drive this efficiency (Chedrawi *et al.*, 2018).

A considerable volume of data is generated from technology developments: data stream evolved from the IoT devices, biometric authentication technology,

open architectures (APIs) customers data stored and provided by rivals (Côte *et al.*, 2020). Duan, Edwards and Dwivedi (2019) reported that technology development allows massive data processing at low cost and in real-time, such as cloud solution, event streaming, NoSQL, ML, and data visualisation.

Siddiqui and Qureshi (2017) highlighted that changing customer behaviour wherein the digitised world customer interacts with banks more digitally allows banks to collect more data about their customers such as locations, internet browsing history, and social media communications. Therefore, banks need to interact more with their customers on social media to gain insights and personalised services. Moreover, according to Chedrawi *et al.* (2018), BD's new rivalry level is reinforced; thus, banks need to deliver quickly and personalised services similar to what is provided by Fintech firms, which are already using BD and offering automated digital services.

Sarrocchio *et al.* (2016) noted that the banking sector is under regulatory pressure, as banks are forced to gather more data in a regulated manner to deliver regulatory reports required by regulators and central banks.

Lastly, Cyber-Security: Banks must use a fraud detection engine to prevent ever-increasing cyber and financial crimes. This raises the burden of risk-based authentication to protect customer data and contact networks, leveraging customer experience analytics to spot anomalies in consumer activities (Ge *et al.*, 2018; Balas *et al.*, 2019). After highlighting the drivers to BD utilisation in the banking industry, the following sub-section describes the various frameworks for BD integration in the banking sector.

2.4.2 Frameworks for Integration of BD into Banking

Despite the BD critiques mentioned earlier of bringing BD into banking, BD's ability straightforwardly justifies any risks (Kshetri, 2016b). BD has many. For example, Truong (2016) stated that banks focus on risk management rather than customer data analytics. However, the same study reveals that banks that use consumer data analytics are 4 per cent-point lead over banks using conventional data structures, while banks that use data analytics to understand consumer behaviour is 12 per cent.

Also, leveraging BD in a cumulative wallet, market share growth, and customer retention segment optimises customer data value (Tunguz and Bien, 2016; Keighley, 2017). Furthermore, BD helps banks target different micro-segments of consumers, past purchasing behaviour, sentiment analysis, Customer Relationship Management (CRM) demographics and social media, which advances customer experience and loyalty, leading to profitability (Vijaya and Neelanarayanan, 2015; Anshari *et al.*, 2019).

Moreover, By 2025, Patrizio (2018) estimated reaching 175 zettabytes of data worldwide, unlocking high chances of leveraging data across multiple fields. According to Siddiqui and Qureshi (2017), digital banking helps the banks reconsider enough data, get the best out of the data, and keep ahead of rivalry. As a result, investment in BD solutions is expected to cross USD 260 billion by 2022, with banking as the largest BD investor in all market domains.

Ultimately, it is essential to highlight some of BD's advantages in the banking industry. Though BD's primary objective in banking is to enhance customer's experience, new priorities include a broader target market, enhanced risk management and security, improved efficiency, and more effective and automated internal processes (Hassani *et al.*, 2018).

2.4.3 Benefits of BD in Banking

More banking possibilities exist out of the exponential growth in data volume created from social networking and online activities. Many scholarships suggest that the data produced from these activities are primarily unstructured data that could be used as an asset by corporate banks to establish several strategies, such as prioritisation of costs, different pricing policies, and management of working capital (Denyes *et al.*, 2016; Shirazi and Mohammadi, 2018). Here are some potentials of BD in banking:

Customer Retention and Procurement: Customer Relationship Management (CRM) is an inclusive mechanism and approach that, by attracting, retaining and associating with discerning customers, brings value to employers and the Bank (Bouchard *et al.*, 2014). Banks sit at the centre of most commercial operations, producing a complete kind of customer data. For that

reason, banks need to protect, maintain and validate data. The critical aim for banking is to improve customer service, and as a result, BD has been used to find new conducts to provide more value, communicate in another articulated manner, and provide practical strategies to avoid customer's dissatisfaction.

A banks survey conducted by Sathi (2017) showed that 84% of the directors surveyed agreed that customers will need a more personalised experience, and the ability to provide customers with the need can increase annual revenue by 18%. While there is an exponential growth in the sheer number of customer-related data collected, four out of five customers believe that sharing their data with their banks will result in quick and improved services (Mirzaie *et al.*, 2019). Accordingly, Shirazi and Mohammadi (2018) argue that consumer behaviour data insights can improve customer experience. American Express used such a strategy, relying on traditional statistical models to avoid consumer attrition.

Bensley *et al.* (2020) estimated that banks invest an average of 8 per cent of the overall budget on marketing, and the data-driven decision could save up to 15-20 per cent of the marketing budget. In this context, an opportunity to use BD in banking arises to make more money by highly targeted advertisement campaigns, recognising problems, and finding the excellent way to overcome, enhance, and understand customer wants and needs (Holland *et al.*, 2020).

Additionally, Patwardhan *et al.* (2018) found that it is essential for banks to collect valued customer behaviour information to create an accurate customer profile to provide efficient, personalised service and enhanced customer satisfaction. Verhoef (2016) reported that Barclays used a social listening approach to gather and evaluate social networks' customer-friendly social insights.

Better Identification of Threats and Fraud: Banks are analysing vast volumes of data to divulge possible hazards. Also, while AI and BD were used to identify fraud by JP Morgan, Citibank invests in ML and predictive models to minimise financial risk and spot fraudulent acts in online banking (Authority, 2018).

Improved Management Efficiency: BD enables real-time data analytics and offers insights into branch performance indicators; in other words, it provides excellent visibility of the daily activities of banks that include the opportunity to address problems proactively (Wu and Lin, 2017). BNP Paribas used branch success measures based on staff productivity and effectiveness, customer retention and growth, and reported and addressed problems efficiently in real-time (Urbinati *et al.*, 2019).

Optimisation and Automation of Internal Processes: Banks use BD with AI and ML to reduce operating costs and improve performance. Furthermore, if McKinsey & Co findings are correct, 30 per cent of all bank processes can be automated by BD technology, which eradicates human factors resulting in significant cost savings and reduces the risk of failure (Lee and Di, 2017). Besides, it is assumed that automation dramatically reduces human error; for instance, JP Morgan relies on AI and ML to process billions of transactions to improve commercial loan agreements and algorithmic trading processes. This resulted in reduced document review time and speed maximisation at ideal trading equity rates resulting in substantial corporate savings (Begenau *et al.*, 2018).

BD provides better management strategies and the potential of turning banks into a constructive competitive business. BD solutions gain awareness of the competitive market climate through real-time perspectives that help improve decision making (Chedrawi *et al.*, 2018). Information visualisation allows executives to access insights generated by BD analytics in real-time, allowing them to make better information-based decisions (Cady, 2017). Several studies have investigated these possibilities (Bhaduri and Fogarty, 2016; Pugna *et al.*, 2019). Rumson and Hallett (2019) noted that corporates would use information services to focus their decisions on verifiable economic transactions.

According to Sarrocco *et al.* (2016), valuable low-cost knowledge has to be collected, converted and loaded into a static model in sophisticated data management systems, which is time consuming compared to BD's latest technology which generates insights at a much lower cost. BD technologies allow corporate banking to evaluate scenarios, produce real-time predictions at

reduced costs and then translate into valuable financial reporting details that the regulator needs (Hassani *et al.*, 2018).

2.4.4 Challenges of BD in the Banking Sector

This subsection continues to address some of the critical problems that the banking industry is facing. The 3Vs that characterise the BD properties are volume, velocity, and variety. Sheppard *et al.* (2018) showed that 70 per cent of global banking directors stress the importance of a consumer-centric strategy that involves intense concern for customer needs. Although 37 per cent of customers are optimistic that banks understand their needs, banks are stressed to take advantage of data volume. A limited amount of this data was, however, used to enhance customer service.

The wide variety of generated (structured and unstructured) data suggests that handling large amounts of data silos referred to by the overused but ambiguous term BD is one of the leading bank challenges (Siddiqui and Qureshi, 2017). BD marks the next stage for growth, creativity and competitiveness. According to Côte *et al.* (2019), the banking industry is switching to BD for successful decisions. However, BD's ambiguity poses several roadblocks for implementing BD application in banks, as detailed below.

Managing Data Consistency: Banks cannot cope with the sheer volume of data and its varied formats. Separating valid data from worthless data is a challenge, even though the proportion of potentially valuable data suggests that there is still a significant amount of useless data to be analysed. As a result, a new technological framework is needed to leverage technology that has been deemed obsolete (dark data), but the precision of the data is where BD's greatest strength resides (Sharma and Klein, 2020).

Data quality characteristics represent authenticity, precision, reasonableness, completeness, and timeliness reported, made available and calculated in a transparent manner (Bouveret, 2018). Nevertheless, while BD has introduced additional challenges to data quality, Lewis *et al.* (2018) observed that banks need to develop data quality criteria, including business guidance, data quality characteristics, reporting, cleaning, and data profiles, to capture reliable data.

Furthermore, Sarrocco *et al.* (2016) concluded that solving this problem requires upholding three main facets of data management: data verification, analysis of the application of this data in decision making, data storage and protection.

Organisational Culture: BD provides the possibility of turning banking into a more productive and competitive sector. However, as many banks are trying to solve a specific market issue or problem-driven by using insight and expertise (Dargam *et al.*, 2018), the broad data pool created and evaluated to make smarter decisions has become the foundation of banking competitiveness. Therefore, Chedrawi *et al.* (2018) assert that banks need to apply a paradigm shift to gain a competitive edge by embracing the data-driven culture and investing more in data processing, storage, and analysis familiar regulatory settings.

Nevertheless, information technology (IT) shifts from a cost centre to a benefit row by perceiving data as a commodity that may help access new markets, attract new consumers, or develop new goods. Absorptive capability refers to a company's readiness to adopt and employ new technology to achieve operational goals. The favourable relationship between absorption potential and BD acceptability, on the other hand, is disputed (Philip, 2018; Trabucchi and Buganza, 2019).

Privacy and Security Concerns: BD's untold ability provides crucial measures for banks to push forward; however, significant data abuse is likely. Nevertheless, according to Insight (2021) ISACA international, only 38 per cent of companies worldwide are equipped to deal with data leakage and security threats, and cybersecurity remains on the banking industry as the most significant issue (Karthik *et al.*, 2017).

Additionally, BD analytics tools and approaches will help banks use capital efficiently and at the same time offer quality service (Emmanuel, 2017). However, the privacy problem arose from the amount of data that banks are gathering and storing about their customers, such as locations, income, marital status, how many children they have, that presumably would allow the

consumer to believe that banks will benefit from it (Collmann and Matei, 2016; Kshetri, 2016a; Ziegler, 2019).

Regulatory Problems: Data security laws are getting stricter. Implementation of the General Data Protection Policy (GDPR) and the Data Protection Act (DPA) in the UK significantly cap the industry worldwide. Most banks still follow conventional data-management practices. Nonetheless, BD has vast legal issues (Voigt and Bussche, 2017; Tamò-Larrieux, 2019). Regardless of the rising effect of legislation, banks are judiciously continuing regardless of uncertainties. El-Seoud *et al.* (2017) contended that regulatory standards form the data processing strategy of banks. Nevertheless, BaFin (2018) emphasised how policymakers will determine if the accurate perception of BD's capacity for customers' desires alters the existing supervisory structure or if the new one is sufficient.

Skills Shortfall: Kshetri *et al.* (2017) noted that research is complementary to data, so learning how to interpret and analyse data is essential to generate value from BD insights (knowledge discovery) that required data skills such as mathematical, programming, econometrics, data visualisation skills, and subject-matter understanding. However, there is a significant deficit in this modern skill set that needs a new strategy for handling the workplace (Günther *et al.*, 2017).

Legacy Infrastructure: According to Ge *et al.* (2018), data storage, BD networks, and legacy data structures account for nearly 9 per cent of the operating profits of banks, primarily processing and analysing data in real-time. While cloud storage technologies lowered the processing data cost, banks still use their traditional data management to store and age consumer data dated 20-30 years ago (Vivek, 2017). Therefore, banks still use their conventional data processing, which cannot keep up with the increasing workload. According to Price Waterhouse Coopers (2017), 92 per cent of the world's largest banks also depend on IBM mainframes, instead of 8 per cent embracing FinTech that draws on customer-centric and agile.

In comparison, advanced techniques such as repeat data to be processed are projected to be eight times more in the warehouse, raising the expense of handling the data. On the other hand, to evaluate these data soil banks, it is important to select between accessible open sources that require expertise set to tackle or high-cost BD management systems that need qualified data scientists to extract data value (Imran *et al.*, 2017).

Finally, more cost-effective high-speed computing systems are needed, speed is essential, real-time data processing is critical for digital multi-channel consumers, and the real-time availability and pricing of necessary on-time data feeds (Rahman and Iverson, 2015; Truong, 2016). As a result, banking faces the task of growing transaction volumes or comprehensively reforming its schemes (Hassani *et al.*, 2018).

2.4.5 Future Impact of BD on Banking

Financial innovations, such as blockchain and FinTech, influence banks and initiate business disruption (Browne and MD, 2015; Shirazi and Mohammadi, 2018). It is believed that banks have undergone extensive digital alteration. However, the true extent of the digital transformation can be realised by quick switching, instantaneous applications, better transparency, and personalised experience (Chedrawi *et al.*, 2018). Moreover, Pejić Bach *et al.* (2019) claim that banks fail to keep up with the rapid digital transition speed; many banks have progressed in the front layer through applications and portals. However, the other layers in the scheme must support it—also, the enormous amount of data is overstored without the exemplary architecture in place. Digital architecture means advanced and real-time and sustainability, which will require automation with the ability to self-learning and maintain pace (Sarrocchio *et al.*, 2016).

Furthermore, BD and IoT empower organisations to gather and process data in innovative ways to transform business and government services. The IoT refers to objects and devices which collect and convey data through the internet (Balas *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, Côte *et al.* (2020) Affirm that both systems can be used together to understand the total value of BD and IoT in providing data

collection tools and BD analytics applications and knowledge on how improved decision management strategic advantage can be used with those data.

Providentially, abundant technology such as BD, AI, and ML may profoundly influence the banking industry by now exist and is presently experiencing a revolution in its own right (Information Commissioner's Office, 2017).

One of these technologies is Cognitive Computing Systems (CCS) which use a simple interface to bank customers and employees by taking a large amount of structured and unstructured information. Zomaya and Sakr (2017) reported the CCS ability to reason, understand, and learn; in other words, it makes hypotheses, arguments, and recommendations (simulate human thought using self-learning algorithms) that serve as a guide for improved sympathetic of the world around us. According to IBM (2017), CCS can dramatically transform how banking uses personalised interaction and unique customer experiences and convert personal banking, wealth management, and trading.

The previous sections showed many examples of BD applications in banking. However, BD's determined potential in the banking industry is still harnessed (Kshetri, 2016b). While 62% of banks executives agreed that BD is crucial for business success, 31% report struggling with getting enough business value from their data (Sarrocco *et al.*, 2016). Thus, banks find it essential to adopt data-driven strategies to stay pertinent and competitive, and BD can augment and cultivate business (Chedrawi *et al.*, 2018). A mutual censure about regulation is that it continuously intervals behind novelties and is archaic when it comes into law (Quinn and Quinn, 2018).

So far, this research has explained BD and its impact on business in general, particularly initiations, potential and challenges of using BD in banking. Consequently, prominent BD in banking in developing economies will be discussed in the next section.

2.5 BD and Finance in Developing Countries: Policy Aspects

BD has been correlated with the term 'new oil' in the modern economy, given its role in growing businesses' value development; this assertion demonstrates

BD's significance (Saxena, 2018). Furthermore, BD offers to use not only data that has been gathered in the banking industry but also the unknown potential uncovered by BD analytics. According to (Kshetri, 2016a), extracting the correct information from data quickly and at a low cost enables banks to reap BD's potential.

Globally, the banking sector is beginning to harvest the promise of BD. Nonetheless, BD application areas are progressively increasing in developing economies. BD is also emerging to improve financial, health, climate and economies for the private sector, governments, and nongovernmental organisations (NGOs) (Goswami *et al.*, 2018).

Therefore, this section discusses the current state of using BD in developing economies. According to the World Bank Group, developing economies report lower and middle income (LMIC) and include less economically developed countries (LEDC) (Goldberg, 2019).

Although there is no explicit agreement on which countries fit this category, development can be measured by human or economic factors. Generally, developing countries have low to medium living standards due to not attaining a remarkable degree of development relative to their population. There is an association between high population and low income, a statistical index such as income per person (per capita), Gross Domestic Product (GDP) per capita, life expectancy and freedom index, and other indices used to measure a country. Baabdullah *et al.* (2019) explained that a reference point could be made by comparing the nation's GDP; however, any country can claim developing according to the United Nations (UN).

Also, there are shared traits of developing countries: for example, high level of pollution, energy deficiency, low level of harmless admission water, a high number of road traffic accidents, low education levels, corruption and others. In 2016, the World Bank clustered the countries according to their Gross National Input (GNI) per capita into four categories: Low-Income countries: from USD 995 or below; Lower Middle-Income States: from USD 996 to 3895. It should be remembered that several scholars opposed the phrase 'developing

countries' since 'outdated,' as it might mean that these nations are inferior to those that are developed. However, in this investigation, emerging economies are used to consider the degree to which BD is used to establish and enhance these traditional properties (Fernholz, 2016).

In 2019, it was reported that globally, there are more than 5.112 billion mobile users with a penetration rate of 67% and 4.388 billion internet users with a penetration rate of 57% (Kemp, 2019). Presently, BD deployment in developing economies is the babyhood stage of development. In some developing countries, the complete absence of a digital footprint renders the relevance of BD. LMIC countries account for 97% of those who live without mobile broadband, and 90% do have coverage but do not use mobile internet. For example, the number of internet users in the Maldives is 0.37 million, Fiji is 0.55 million, Rwanda is 3.72 million, Zambia 7.25 million, Ethiopia is 16.44 million, Egypt 49.23 million, and Nigeria is 111.63 (Baabdullah *et al.*, 2019).

Similarly, several BD applications have been used for different purposes in developing economies. For instance, in Haiti, mining Twitter and online news reports were used to designate the spread of illnesses with a lead time of two weeks (Raj and Aithal, 2018). Research in Serbia indicated a significant link between drinking coffee and farm incomes, as farmers who drink morning coffee are more likely to be more active than those who do not (Raj and Aithal, 2018). In Kenya, mobile phone transaction data help the government enhance supply allocation for infrastructural development.

Moreover, since many developed nations do not have accurate data, real-time market profiling has been employed in many countries to resolve socio-economic difficulties. For example, early indicators are examined in social media networks like Facebook and Twitter to identify rising unemployment and malaria infection rates (Kshetri, 2016a).

On the other hand, many factors may positively or negatively affect BD adoption in developing countries, such as technology-related, competition and regulatory. Evidence indicates that BD adoption is positively linked to an absorption ability defined as an aptitude for distinguishing and practising new

knowledge and applying it to profitable purposes (Saggi and Jain, 2018; Liao and Chen, 2019). Furthermore, environmental uncertainty negatively impacts BD adoption (Mehta and Sahni, 2018). However, it is thought that regulatory support positively influences BD adoption decisions (Lim *et al.*, 2018).

In India: According to Siddiqui and Qureshi (2017), demonetisation-to-digitisation accelerated the fast growth of e-commerce and e-banking. Thus, India's government promoted digitisation for a cashless society, though motivating and educating people to use e-banking was challenging. Furthermore, over 1.7 billion using mobile phones are presently accepted from the conventional financial system. While the Indian government's digitisation policy considerably drives BD to open an enormous opportunity for Indian banking, very few banks observed across customer relationships in a way that could offer business opportunities.

In essence, BaFin (2018) claims that the digitisation resulted in an increase in Automated Teller Machin (ATM), more use of debit and credit cards as a replacement of cash, a rapid increase in paying utility bills and transfer money and more significant usage of online and phone banking. However, fewer than 50% of Indian banks check external consumer data, such as online activity and social media interactions (Chedrawi *et al.*, 2018).

In Nigeria: Ogunleye (2015) reported that five of the largest banks have been using text mining applied to unstructured data generated from social media (Twitter and Facebook) to assist digital marketing and decision making. However, research conducted in commercial banks in Turkey by Dinesh *et al.* (2018) investigated that the evidence gained from macro-financial data were used to classify deposit pricing and factors to achieve strategic deposit pricing. Likewise, in a study conducted in an actual data set of Ziraat bank in Turkey and a set of Canadian banks, data management methods help regulatory executives evaluate branch performance and trigger early cautionary for failing banks (Tunguz and Bien, 2016).

In Kenya: A cross-sectional survey of 1065 organisations by Saxena (2018) suggests that information technology significantly affects

nongovernmental organisations' financial management systems. As a result, firms had capitalised on information management schemes, which lowered administrative budgets.

Similarly, in another application of BD, Baabdullah *et al.* (2019), a cross-sectional study of Saudi bank clients was conducted to test the key factors predicting online banking use and its effect on customer retention and loyalty. Empirical studies have demonstrated that crucial variables such as price value, service efficiency, motivation, product consistency, habit, success expectations and supporting conditions substantially affect actual consumer conduct.

Nevertheless, in Sri Lanka, a structured questionnaire was carried out to classify the main factors determining BD's adoption in 30 financial service companies. The results argue a significant negative correlation between environmental instability, sophistication and organisational purpose to implement BD technology (Mahesh *et al.*, 2018).

So far, this section highlighted the impact of using BD applications across several industries in some developing economies. Therefore, the following section discusses the current use of BD in Egyptian banking and highlights the lessons learnt from utilising BD in the last decade.

2.6 BD and Banking in Egypt

BD is still in its infancy throughout businesses, particularly in the banking industry. Furthermore, even though just a few studies have looked at the impact of BD on banking organisational efficiency, there are no or few scholarships reported on BD deterrents in Egypt. Though there have been several IoT and BD conferences held in Egypt, for example, in 2014, the world bank group organised a conference under the title of Egypt: BD and Urban Mobility, and in 2019 was also the first world conference on IoT: Application and Future was held in Cairo, on 18 June 2019, at the International Data Corporation (IDC) and 2020 International Conference on Innovative Technology and Software Trends (Saxena, 2018).

As discussed in the previous section, BD undertaken in the developing economies is in its infancy stage; according to a list of per capita nominal GDP for countries published by the World Bank (2018) and International Monetary Fund, Egypt comes in 127,128 positions with a GDP of 2,549 and 2,573. Furthermore, the International Monetary Fund (IMF) (Nasr, 2006) noted that the present account deficit is expected to continue below 3% GDP, and the public debt ratio is likely to decline markedly by 2023.

Khashaba (2019) intended to identify new data societies in Egypt and discuss the challenges of developing and implementing processes to support growth objectives and achieve the desired outcome for decision-makers. Moreover, policymaking contributes to sustainable development and improves human lives.

Correspondingly, the report argues that to deliver agenda 2030 aimed at sustainable development and in Egypt vision 2030, achieving these ambitious targets is critical. Furthermore, the robust corporation amid COMAS and UNFPA, the Data Ecosystem, has been synthesized to promote Egypt's sustainable development. The study also highlights the ground and data situation using a national asset that can add value. However, the study highlights some challenges, such as the obsolete regulatory system, the lack of a national statistical strategy and more.

2.6.1 The Banking Landscape in Egypt

Historically, the banking sector evolution in Egypt started in 1836, after the issuance of the Egyptian currency. In the 1970s, the open-door policy made the Egyptian banking sector broaden noticeably. As a part of this strategy, the aim was outward-looking growth with a current position for the private sector to support economic performance (Hemdani, 2017). Banking legislation was enacted in 1975 to meet the new policy (Legislation 120/1075) specifying the form and character of all banks into three categories of banks: Commercial banks, specialist banks, and investment and corporate banks.

Like many emerging market economies, El-Dyasty (2017) noted that the Egyptian authorities started undertaking significant banking reform toward a

more liberal structure in the 1990s. Therefore, to resolve the banking industry's stability and the uncertainties inherent in the new framework, the law strengthens bank legislation and supervision based on international standards, focusing on prudential banking regulation. However, it is crucial to highlight that the banking sectors practices are either influenced or underpinned by Sharia Banking Laws. This is likely also to be the status of all banks in the Middle East.

After that, a new set of listing rules was implemented in February 2014, aiming to promote new business offerings and enhance market transparency and minority rights. As a result, the Central Bank of Egypt (CBE) announced in 2018 that there were 40 banks listed as the commercial, non-commercial, private and public sectors.

Although there are a few specialised banks including real estate and agriculture, 40% of the banking sector is dominated by three central public-sector banks: Bank Masr, Egypt's National Bank, and Banque Du Caire, with all banks being subject to CBE supervision. Nevertheless, there are special clauses in agreement and statute for Nasr Social Bank, National Investment Banks, and The Arab International Bank (Saxena, 2018).

The provision of banking services, on the other hand, is of low quality for financial intermediation, which is reflected in limited access to financial services for small organisations and households, oversized non-performing loans, and high transaction fees. According to Nasr (2006), this could be attributed partly to the dominance of public-sector banks, consisting of a new relatively untested regulatory and supervisory structure and an ongoing organisational and institutional restructuring process.

Nevertheless, public-sector banks running the banking sector have lagged behind inefficiency, slow development and innovation, and limited scope and volume of services and products offered compared to their private counterparts. However, public-sector banks have been subject to structural and organisational reform with modest changes in the banking system's inefficiency.

Data Protection in Egypt: In 2011, after the Arab Spring that caused uncertainty and turbulence to the economy, Egypt, toward stability, attempted

to be an attractive investment market. Hence, the country needs to understand that data is valuable to businesses and the government to boost the Egyptian economy and improve national security. While there was no legislation regarding data protection, the Egyptian constitution in 2014 contained two provisions regarding this matter.

However, realising the importance of data protection and cybersecurity in June 2019, the Egyptian parliament approved the first data protection regulations to protect data and privacy (Narendra, 2019).

Additionally, data is collected, stored, and processed increases many legal concerns, mostly privacy issues. According to Statista (2019), Egypt's number of internet users is 50.7 million, more than half of the population, and this exponential increase makes Egyptians precious data for many beneficiaries, such as businesses and the government. However, due to the low-security awareness and the absence of privacy and cyber regulation, Egyptian users are vulnerable to all types of cyberattacks. In the same vein, Human Rights Watch (2018) reported that Egypt ranked high in cybercrime and financial crimes such as money laundering, fraud, and corruption which costs the economy approximately 388 billion USD.

2.6.2 BD Investment in Egyptian Banking: Lesson Learnt

BD is characterised as an exhaustive collection of data, which is difficult to process by advanced data processing systems because of the complexity and volume. Furthermore, BD comes from different sources, including mobile banking transactions, cell phone call logs, social media messages, online searches, and more. However, what is vital is to transform the data into actionable knowledge (Dalla Valle and Kenett, 2018; Demoulin and Coussement, 2020; Line *et al.*, 2020).

In addition, BD, together with digital channels and other tools, would boost efficiency and enhance Egypt's banking sector's competitive advantage. According to the Global Competitiveness Index (2018), out of 140 countries worldwide, Egypt ranks 93rd, compared to 119th in 2015. Nonetheless, in the

future, digital banking with BD, AI, and IoT leveraging would allow for a higher ranking for Egypt (Weforum, 2019).

Therefore, the Egyptian Government and the CBE are making substantial strides in improving the banking model, allocating 1 trillion EGP to finance creativity and investment in talent and start-ups (CBE, 2019).

Due to the lack of academic literature, this section provides empirical evidence of how BD has been used in Egypt's banking sector through the annual reports published by banks since 2015. However, in 2015, Commercial International Bank (CIB) introduced BD's concept to Egypt's banking industry and claimed to be the first bank in Egypt to have an advanced analytics and data management team to harness BD for its benefits customers (CIB, 2015).

Correspondingly, CIB Bank views data as an asset that can be used as a new strategy solution that contributes to improvements in the banking sector. CIB (2017) report argues that creating an exclusive customer experience can transform this data volume into valuable insights. However, moving from descriptive to predictive analytics is a challenge; therefore, developing infrastructure for advanced BD analytics by investing in human and information technology is crucial for the bank to demonstrate transformation.

Notwithstanding, the CIB (2018) reported the first sign to reap BD benefits and adopt a data-driven strategy focusing on a customer-centric approach. The bank contends that augmented decision-making optimises operational processes, reduces transaction costs and processing times, customer retention, and innovative services and products to fulfil customer needs.

Furthermore, the bank crops the ongoing investment in BD analytics by establishing a novel anomaly detection model to detect risk incidents and fraud. Additionally, to take advantage of technology's continuing investments, the bank investigates the blockchain potential to transform Egypt's banking industry (CIB, 2018).

Similarly, Emirates NBD bank uses the BD management tool to process internal and external bank data sources. NBD claims that enhancing customer

experience can be attainable by harnessing BD. According to its annual report (NBD, 2018), the bank now has a fully automated and accessible system that can rapidly determine actionable insights. On the other hand, In March 2018, HSBC bank has launched a Global Social Network Analytics platform to fight financial crime such as terrorism and human trafficking financing and money laundering with BD analytics.

In 2018, HSBC (2018) noted devoting the bank to have the first trade finance transaction on Blockchain. However, HSBC argues that sustaining the current progression rate requires more digital and banking skills talent, which is the main challenge in the banking sector.

Moreover, according to Bloomberg (2019), Banque Du Caire has redefined digital customer experience by initiating the end-to-end digital transformation project to bring cutting-edge banking services (Bloomberg, 2019).

Consequently, a report of Blom bank (2017) portrays the fact that technology trend such as BD, cloud computing, and IoT continually influences the banking sector, therefore having the right technology enable to run business in a predictable way to ultimately fulfil customer demands and expectations, while optimising cost and increase revenues. Therefore, in 2017, Blom bank adopted the digital transformation paradigm to enable digital transformation while concentrating on customer-centricity and agility to adopt the digital trends that enable the bank to provide their customers with a rich, innovative digital experience.

In addition, Faisal Islamic Bank of Egypt is developing a data classification policy using data loss prevention (DLP) technology to secure sensitive data (Islamic, 2018). On the contrary, Attijariwafa bank group (2017) sheds light on the significance of harnessing digital technology's full potential for its customers' benefit. In 2017, the group had adapted its information and embrace a new robust IT infrastructure to redefine customer experience in the new digital era. Furthermore, as a result of investing in digital transformation, the Group could personalise its clients' experience while improving employees' expertise and security (Attijariwafa, 2017).

Notwithstanding, while a few banks in Egypt adopted the BD approach, numerous banks plan to harvest BD insights and integrate them within the 4th industrial revolution. The current state of BD in Egypt and the lessons learned from investing in it, and the potential aim of investing in digital transformation were addressed in this section. The following section sheds light on the research gaps.

2.7 Research Gaps

A research gap is described as an extent to which inadequate evidence bounds the aptitude to grasp a question's deduction (Fred *et al.*, 2008). Similarly, the missing parts of the research literature are the field that has not yet been recognised or is under-explored, which may be due to the sample size, form, location or population, method of testing, compilation or interpretation of results, or other variables or conditions of research (Marczyk *et al.*, 2005). This research aims to understand BD's role and its potentials in the financial services industry in Egypt. Therefore, this section comprehensively identifies the gaps in both aspects of the literature, knowledge and methodology.

2.7.1 Theoretical Gap

Vast transformative forces such as economics, empowerment of millennials, digital natives, demographics, and regulatory requirements are restructuring the way people communicate, learn, and do business as technology is to profoundly impact the banking industry in Egypt with trends such as BD, IoT, Blockchain, mobile and cloud computing, and social media (Balas *et al.*, 2019).

Therefore, in the age of the 4th industrial revolution, implementing and adapting a digital transformation strategy like using BD insights is crucial to prevent disruption, while the 5th industrial revolution is just around the corner, where AI and ML would help increase the efficiency of human labour and Blockchain will help provide access to banking block (Rothman, 2018; Liao and Chen, 2019). However, since most BD studies rely mainly on technological problems, there is a lack of theoretical and analytical study on how BD can be used in the Egyptian banking sector to enhance operational efficiency and competitive advantage.

Traditionally, the banking sector in Egypt has based its organisational operations on structured data. However, the data generated from various semi-structured and unstructured data sources could cultivate the BD potential with BD's help (Hale and Lopez, 2017; Chedrawi *et al.*, 2018; Pérez-Martín, Pérez-Torregrosa and Vaca, 2018). Moreover, recent studies demonstrate that such data may improve decision-making (Cockcroft, 2016; Hilbert, 2016; Yadegaridehkordi *et al.*, 2018; Liao and Chen, 2019). Notwithstanding, examinations about what degree research on BD application in the banking industry has advanced remain unexplored.

Nevertheless, only a few scholarships worldwide have extensively studied BD's value and its effect on the banking industry from an operational viewpoint (Motamarri *et al.*, 2017; Thirathon *et al.*, 2017; Pugna, Duțescu and Stănilă, 2019).

To date, very few papers on BD applications have been published in the context of Egypt; however, no or few published studies on the holistic role of BD in the banking sector has been published, suggesting that there is a lack of academic base on the determinants or implementation of BD in the banking industry. However, previous academic scholars have carried out few observational studies and published them by commercial banks (Attijariwafa, 2017; Bank, 2018; CIB, 2018; Islamic, 2018; AAIB, 2020).

Furthermore, while recent analytical and theoretical research on BD has focused on technological issues, theory-driven research on BD's function in the banking sector. This research suggests a systematic study that thoroughly defines BD's role and applications from a banking standpoint in Egypt. As a result, it is critical to consider BD's significance in the market from a broader viewpoint.

2.7.2 Methodological Gap

While many banks in developing economies have made BD adoption one of the top priorities of their business strategy, whichever planning to capitalise or invest profoundly in information technology, few distinguish how to harvest its value. Furthermore, whether or not BD has a substantial positive influence on

the organisation was not yet answered evidently in extant theory (Del Vecchio *et al.*, 2017; Günther *et al.*, 2017; Acharya *et al.*, 2018; Côte-Real, Ruivo and Oliveira, 2020).

More importantly, determining the impact of BD on enhancing organisational performance is challenging. Furthermore, there have been very few empirical research studies to assess the actual potential of BD in terms of its impact on organisational performance (Oracle, 2015; IBM, 2016, 2017; Erb *et al.*, 2017; Erraissi *et al.*, 2017; Sathi, 2017; Barton, 2018; Chessell *et al.*, 2018).

Correspondingly, the methodology gap has emerged because of the lack of theoretical-driven researches, whereas different methodological approaches have been adopted by academia, such as qualitative, quantitative, or mixed methods (Espinosa and Armour, 2016; El-Kassar and Singh, 2017; Chen *et al.*, 2018).

In particular, relatively little research on BD in banking has used the Grounded Theory (GT) approach in developing economies. However, no or few studies has been conducted to evaluate the significance of BD in Egypt's financial services using such a scientific approach, implying a methodological gap.

GT approach consists of three crucial elements: concepts, categories and propositions. This approach intends to generate or discover a substantive theory about a specific phenomenon from the data gathered (Strauss and Corbin, 1997; Gray, 2015). GT focuses on observing the concept it describes and is then created and validated by rigorous data collection and analysis specific to that theory (Fred *et al.*, 2008). Moreover, to verify and assess the authenticity of the study's gathered data and results, four testing requirements are notable in GT. These are the authenticity of constructs, internal validity, external validity, and reliability (Bryant, 2017).

Therefore, this study's aim and objectives lean more toward the GT methodology for a few reasons justified in detail in the next chapter. Firstly, a valuable tool embedded in GT helps verify, validate, and ensure the study is robust; this is known as the triangulation method.

Unlike the phenomenological research design, the GT approach focuses on discovering and developing a theory on the study's subject. On the other hand, the phenomenological research design is the in-depth understanding of the concept or phenomenon being explored in the study through the stakeholders' experiences (Ranjit Kumar, 2011).

The previously stated theoretical and methodological gaps explain BD's use and effect in banking in Egypt. Therefore, this study contribution is three-fold. First, the thesis would lead to a broader empirical knowledge that has not yet been explored in BD science by examining BD's role in Egypt as a developing economy, thus bridging the theoretical gap.

Secondly, the study generates a substantive theory to understand BD's role and impact and its direct and indirect impact on organisational performance in banking. In addition, this study bridges the methodological gap by redefining the methodological approach to understanding BD and providing new empirical evidence that would enrich the current literature. Thirdly, the study provides practical recommendations to the banking sector in Egypt.

This section addressed the research gaps as well as the theoretical and methodological flaws that this study addressed. In addition, this study uses the Egyptian banking sector as an example to better understand the role of BD and its impact on/in the financial industry in developed countries and better describe the BD phenomenon and bridge the knowledge gap by establishing a substantive theory. As a consequence, the following research questions were addressed in this study:

- 1- What is the academic and industry-based current state of knowledge about BD's role and impact on the banking and finance sector?
- 2- How is BD constructed by stakeholders in the banking sector in Egypt?
- 3- What lessons have been learnt from investment in BD in Egypt's banking sector over the last decade?

2.8 Summary

In conclusion, this chapter has summarised the current academic and industry-based BD body of knowledge using the funnel method. Five topics were discussed: defining and exploring BD, the business impact of BD, the role of BD in banking, BD and finance in developed countries, BD and banking in Egypt.

According to the literature, BD plays an essential role in the banking industry and may give potential answers to numerous banking challenges. However, there is a dearth of the theoretical groundwork for a more accurate understanding of Egypt's BD phenomena. As a result, we identified theoretical as well as methodological gaps in the literature. This research's methodology will be discussed in the next chapter.

3 Chapter Three: Methodology: Grounded Theory

3.1 Introduction

This chapter discusses the research approach concerning research objectives and questions outlined in chapter 1. This chapter, therefore, consists of three sections. The first section outlines the methodological approach, ending with the implications for this study through Crotty's research design elements. The second section then provides more discussion of the option of the suitable study design, GT methodology and procedures, justification for selecting CGT, role of researcher, research area, CGT methodological procedures, data collection, access to this study, design of research interviews, selection of interviewees, conceptual framework, and data analysis process. Finally, the third part will briefly discuss the quality of this research, the criteria for GT study quality, piloting, and, finally, a summary of the chapter.

3.2 Methodological Approach

Business management studies have continually sought to broaden the knowledge of research results using the appropriate approach. As a result, the number of studies investigating BD's importance to businesses using qualitative case study methods has grown gradually over the last decade (Braganza *et al.*, 2017; Riche *et al.*, 2019). However, very few researchers used the GT in BD application (Berente and Seidel, 2014; Pugna *et al.*, 2019).

Nonetheless, in a research study, establishing the appropriate methodology can be considered a challenge. Furthermore, recognise the most appropriate methodology to establish credibility and ensure that the research objectives are met (Ranjit Kumar, 2011). On the other hand, Crotty (2000) claims that even though there is a confusing array of theoretical viewpoints and methodologies, their terminology is inconsistent and opposed.

Saunders *et al.* (2007) pointed out that the researcher studies theoretical foundations addressing data collection and analysis and concludes the research questions. Similarly, Crotty (2000) suggests that it is essential to have theoretical and methodological consistency between the research approach

and research questions. Four research design elements were proposed by Crotty (2000): epistemology, theoretical perspectives, methodology, and methods, and it points out that a relationship occurs between the adopted researcher's epistemology, theoretical perspective, and methodology. Also, Crotty (2000) has excluded ontology from the context, arguing that both ontology and epistemology are mutually based, and it is hard to discern between them when addressing research problems conceptually. Similarly, Creswell (2013) research framework was based on Crotty's four research fundamentals.

Additionally, Creswell (2013) indicates that these four research elements are central to the research method's decision-making, whether it is likely to be qualitative, quantitative or combined, depending mainly on the researcher's initial role on the essence of information. This chapter thus discusses the research design used concerning the research objectives and questions alluded to in the introduction chapter and adopts Crotty's research design elements' language. Figure 3-1 demonstrates the interrelationship between research epistemology, theoretical perspectives, methodology and methods.

Figure 3-1 The interrelationship of research design elements

Source: Researcher based on Crotty's (2000) research design

3.2.1 Research Philosophy

Research philosophy echoes how the researcher views the world; adopting the correct philosophy emphasises the preparation and execution of study (Goulding, 2002). In essence, Marczyk *et al.* (2005) noted that philosophy is the paradigm that reflects significant assumptions about the world view, which guide the researcher. Furthermore, Denzin and Lincoln (2002) argue that paradigms are three characteristics: Ontology, Epistemology and Methodology. Finally, Cameron (2009) points out that philosophy makes the awareness of the nature of reality.

Two paradigms are central, contrasting ontology and epistemology (Singh and Estefan, 2018). First, the study paradigm has been described by Kuhn (1962, p. 43):

“The set of common beliefs and agreements shared between scientists about how problems should be understood and addressed.” Kuhn (1962, p. 43)

Researchers' ontology and epistemology give a complete understanding of how to view knowledge, while methodological strategies are used to discover it (Singh and Estefan, 2018). It was suggested that recognising the philosophical perspective would improve scientific excellence and add to the study's originality (Kincaid, 1996). Various studies have clarified the research paradigm, and the three most prevalent paradigms have been identified: positivists, constructivists and pragmatists (Cameron, 2009).

Table 3-1 Summary of the research design elements

Paradigm	Ontology What is reality?	Epistemology How can knowledge be discovered?	Theoretical Standpoint What strategy should be used to achieve understanding?	Methodology What steps should be taken in order to gain knowledge?	Methods To obtain knowledge, what methods or strategies should be used?
Positivists	There is one reality.	Reality can be measured through reliable and valid tools.	Positivism, Post-positivism	Survey, Experimental	Quantitative, Sampling, Statistical analysis, Questionnaire, Interview, and Focus group.
Constructivists	There is no single reality.	It is necessary to interpret reality by exploring the essential significance of events and actions.	Interpretivism Phenomenology Symbolic interactionism	Ethnography GT Phenomenological research Heuristic inquiry Action research Discourse analysis	Qualitative Interview, Observation Case study
Pragmatists	The reality, perceived in the light of its utility, is continuously discussed.	The most excellent method is one that solves problems.	Deweyan pragmatism Research through design	Action Research Mixed methods research	Combination of any method.

Source: Researcher based on (Creswell, 2013)

A more detailed description of each paradigm is given in the table above. Guba and Lincoln (1982, p. 37) described ontology as "*The nature of reality or the study of being*" (Crotty, 2000). According to Crotty (2000), ontology is the difference between reality and its perceived view. Also, ontology is a philosophy that explains the essence of existence by analysing the nature of reality. In other words, ontology is learning how reality influences the behaviour of people. Accordingly, Scotland (2012) claims that individuals define reality differently, according to individual experiences.

Furthermore, Crotty (2000) found that an exact epistemological status is implied from an ontological position and vice versa. Principally, three philosophical positions exist Objectivism, Constructivism, and Pragmatism which originates an ontological worldview (Kincaid, 1996). The Objectivist perspective makes the consciousness of a social phenomenon in place of its assistances to study the diverse meanings of social phenomena on social actors. In other words, objectivism teaches how a social phenomenon influences various persons (Cameron, 2009). Constructivism, on the other hand, articulates the contradiction in what objectivism enunciates. It notes that social actors are responsible for creating social phenomena (Guba and Lincoln, 1982). However, pragmatism is more of a realistic approach that can use positivism and constructivism to find answers to challenges through examination (Wertz *et al.*, 2011).

On the other hand, epistemology offers a philosophical framework for deciding what forms of experience are likely to be and how to verify that it is appropriate and accurate (Gray, 2015). Crotty (2000, p. 8) defines Epistemology as "*how we know what we know*". Many scholars believe that Epistemology addresses the facts by finding adequate knowledge (Wertz *et al.*, 2011; Scotland, 2012; Robbins, 2016). Lincoln and Guba (1990) describe epistemology as what and how it is possible to know. In the same vein, Ranjit Kumar (2011) suggests that epistemology is significant to define adequate knowledge about the study's field. It helps define what knowledge is and determines its foundations and restrictions.

Correspondingly, three philosophical positions relate to epistemology: Positivism, Critical realism, and Interpretivism. Positivist is about finding clarification to calculate the universe's possible understanding from an empirical point of view. It also tends towards a deductive approach, creating research questions and theories that can be evaluated employing a quantitative approach (Kuhn, 1962). It is commonly assumed that case study and survey research methods frequently accompany a positivist approach; nevertheless, a case study can be used with other research standpoints (Cameron, 2009).

Critical realism is similar to positivism, while Kincaid (1996) argues that realism articulates that scientific methods are indecorous; Strang (2015) claims that the researcher's social reality is independent. In other words, it presumes that a study is a political act and that critical theorists are scholars pursuing a critical approach. Nevertheless, an action research method is regularly used with a critical approach (Martinez-Vargas, 2018).

Crotty (2000) suggests that choosing the best research method is influenced by the researcher's personal views. Creswell (2014), on the other hand, takes a broader view, suggesting that disclosing the study's methods is a powerful tool for improving the credibility of social scientific research. Thus, this study adopts the interpretive paradigm since the writer assumes that humans construct information and interpretation. In addition, there is no single reality, but by finding the true nature of events and actions, reality can be understood.

3.2.2 Research Approach

Crotty (2000) asserts that many theoretical perspectives can potentially emerge from an ontological and epistemological stance. Positivists and post-positivists, for example, have an overarching objectivist ontology, whereby both can contribute to several disciplines, such as survey testing, experimental research, and some versions of GT. It is believed that constructivism was substituted with the interpretive approach (Goulding, 2002).

In the literature, the interpretive approach is frequently attributed to 'verstehen', the concept of understating something in its context by Max Weber, who argues that Interpretivism is what people participate in the social life understand about

their own and others' actions (Brocki and Wearden, 2006). It also helps to gain and change cultural reality by learning about concepts and valuables.

Gummesson (2003) indicates that all study is interpretive, while Leimeister (2010) retains interpretivism as the empirical interpretation that is essentially committed to the human context. However, social concepts, such as language, can also analyse truth: Morse (2009) argues that Interpretivists reject the objective perspective of the world and reconstruct their reality by relying on their topics' view of the world.

As a result, the findings are thoroughly tied to the setting of the study. On the contrary, while positivists have confidence that society shapes the individual and prefers quantitative scientific methods, Interpretivists trust that individuals shape society and prefer humanistic qualitative methods (Wertz *et al.*, 2011).

Interpretivism and positivism, on the other hand, both have significant flaws. For example, Charmaz (2006) asserted that in the end, the researcher could not replicate the participants' experiences or be separated from the phenomenon under study. The latter point has been highlighted by Holloway (1997), who argued that it is unbearable to attain impartiality and independence, given that the values of participants and researcher are continuously present. Weber (2009), however, claimed that all social research is inherently biased.

To determine where the study is based, a researcher might need a top-down or bottom-up approach. If the researcher agrees on a research topic in a bottom-up approach, then which methods, techniques, and theoretical viewpoint, the top-down approach, on the contrary, determines the research model, epistemology, methodology, then methods. Thus, each research will have different study paradigms (Crotty, 2000; Creswell and Poth, 2017).

Deductive: The deductive method (top-down) aims to find the explanation that begins the inquiry through scientific inference, and the primary purpose is to answer or even no answers to research questions that can range from claims to educated conjecture (Fisher and Buglear, 2010). Besides, searching the theories for the research questions in the deductive method

contributes to the compilation of evidence that finally supports or denies the research query (Charmaz and Belgrave, 2019).

Figure 3-2 Deductive approach

Source: Burney (2008)

Inductive: On the opposite, it is possible to use the inductive approach (Bottom-up) to create a new hypothesis, which means no reasoning about existing theory (Gray, 2004). Strauss and Corbin (2002) emphasised that the study hierarchy begins from the research question to analysis, then explanation, in an inductive way. Next, there is the analysis and the results that the new theory ultimately generates.

Figure 3-3 Inductive approach

Source: Burney (2008)

Antwi and Hamza (2015) concluded that the deductive approach starts from general to abstract and concludes with specific outcomes. Although deductive research uses scientific reasoning, Soiferman (2010) argues that the theory states that the investigation can be subjective, suggesting that subjectivity would significantly affect the development of the study hypothesis. For that, Krauss (2005) pointed out that the deductive method's subjectivity makes it inductive. However, Rips (1994) argues that the limitation of deductive reasoning excludes the occurred unforeseen factors throughout the theory's development.

On the contrary, the inductive method proceeds from a specific observation and concludes a general theory. However, Simon (1996) argues that inductive reasoning enables hesitation about more compound variables, debating the initial conclusion. Furthermore, it is believed that the inductive approach originated from observations that are the underpinning for knowledge development (Jorgensen, 2015).

Abductive Approach (Mix): Abductive approach is set to address limitations related to an inductive and deductive approach. Inductive reasoning is criticised because of the lack of empirical data to enable theory-building (Charmaz and Belgrave, 2019). Similarly, a deductive approach is appraised for the absence of clarity in how theory can be tested by articulating hypotheses (Hyde, 2000). Therefore, abductive reasoning overcomes these limitations by adopting a pragmatist standpoint (Bryant *et al.*, 2012).

Moreover, according to Tomiyama *et al.* (2003), the abductive approach can be intuitive and creative. For example, Abductive reasoning was adopted by Einstein's work that involved a creative leap of visualisation and imagination (Thought Experiment). Nevertheless, Einstein's conclusions about space-time seem to have been accurate so far and continue to be proved experientially (Stein, 1968). Nevertheless, one major drawback of this approach is that it is characterised by a lack of completeness in either evidence, explanation or both, along with the practice challenge (Svennevig, 2001).

The author of this thesis has defined BD and the research scope as the banking industry in Egypt, considering the existence of the research focus; thus, interpretivism was considered the most appropriate research viewpoint as interpretivism takes the research work to an understanding of the application of BD in the banking industry and offers realistic advice to academia and banks. Furthermore, while this research does not verify existing theory through hypotheses or experiments that exclude the positivist perspective (Wertz et al., 2011), this study intends to generate a substantive theory through an abductive approach. Therefore, the results of the data analysis are grounded in the study context.

3.2.3 Research Strategy

The methodology is the approach that contributes to the collection of particular techniques (Crotty, 2000). To date, various research strategies have been developed and introduced as clear guidance on conducting research (Cassell *et al.*, 2018). Saunders *et al.* (2007), the research approach is the overarching plan that explains how the researcher can react to research questions.

Likewise, Bryman (2016) highlighted that the study strategy is a universal path for research conduct. By drawing on the concept of research strategy, Yin (2015) has shown that to achieve research objectives and answer the research questions, and research strategies may be extended irrespective of the research intent in all research studies. Finally, Blaikie (2007) shines a light on research strategies to connect the investigator and data collection and study methodology.

Business management research has consistently tried to increase the consistency and quantity of study outcomes over the past decade by applying a proper technique. However, several strategies have been used: experiment, survey, case study, action research, and GT (Collis and Hussey, 2013; Robert K Yin, 2016). Furthermore, Creswell and Creswell (2018) present a comprehensive portrayal of various research strategies. Therefore, a brief overview of various research methodologies is given in this section.

Experiment Research: This methodology objectively explores the direct influence of the theory on a group of individuals, as well as the group of individuals who are not influenced by the phenomenon (Fred *et al.*, 2008).

Survey Study: Survey method is linked with a deductive approach that uses questionnaires to collect data from a broad population (Gray, 2015). However, while this method captures productive and reliable data from a broad population, choosing a diverse population is essential for this research approach (Glaser and Strauss, 1967).

Case Study: Case study architecture is commonly used; this design requires the latest problem to be analysed in its scenery (Lincoln and Guba, 1990). Notably, this approach is used when the population is heterogeneous and the context is not apparent. Data collection will be achieved by looking at people's behaviour, interviewing people, considering settings, and checking for information. Also, the criteria of the chosen cases are based on their relation to the post-research topic.

However, the case study approach's simplicity has been criticised as it may lack rigour in sampling, data collection, and interpretation (Marczyk *et al.*, 2005). While Yin (2015) appraised the case study for producing a considerable amount of data, Denscombe (2008) highlights the case study method's descriptive nature. However, the case study technique's importance cannot be undervalued since it is perceived to be one of the most commonly used methods in business studies (Yin, 2001; Cassell *et al.*, 2018).

Grounded Theory (GT): Constructs a theory after explaining and predicting the action (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). According to Strauss and Corbin (2002), The primary concern of participants and how it can be addressed by analysing persons and interactions is analysed by the GT process. Besides, the use of the collected data produces a theory, so explaining the GT and its use for this study is given in this report's remainder. The next sub-section addresses the approach of GT in depth.

3.3 Establishing a Methodological Connection: Grounded Theory

GT is a systematic approach by methodological data collection and analysis related to the construction of theory. Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss also established the GT method (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). The Discovery Book of GT was published in 1967. That laid the basis for GT, described as:

“A general method of analysis linked with data collection that uses a systematically applied set of methods, to generate an inductive theory about the substantive area”. (Glaser, 1992, p.16)

According to Charmaz (2006), GT's primary aim is to discover the participants' vital problem and address it by constantly comparing data at a cumulative concept level. Similarly, the theory produced was defined as a general trend of understating that the research results were better clarified.

Nevertheless, GT has developed, and the contradictions between the two GT early pioneers led to the rise of two GT models, beginning from a fundamental system specification in the GT Glaser discovery book, often alluded to as the Glaserian GT or the classic GT Glaser version, versus the developing theory outside empirical work and then testing it as a separate initiative (Glaser and Strauss, 1967).

Following that, GT was broadly cited by an inductively based version of qualitative research. Finally, Strauss and Corbin's book *Fundamentals of Qualitative Research: GT Procedures and Strategies* was published in 1990 and considers the realistic edition of GT, also called Straussian GT version (Strauss and Corbin, 1997).

In 1992, Glaser passionately refuted Strauss and Corbin for doing something other than GT, focusing on a full conceptual explanation from the researcher's viewpoint rather than that of the participants. Then, as an afterthought, it became necessary to state clearly which version of GT is used in research (Heath and Cowley, 2004).

GT was recognised to have Glaserian proponents, who claim to be purer in their approach and believe in being more data-led in their analyses. On the other hand, Straussian proponents (those who wish for a more structured and directed qualitative analysis method) (Heath and Cowley, 2004). The subsequent significant GT development was Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT), by Kathy Charmaz (2000). Since then, The CGT edition has been continuously developed, focusing on rationality and abduction (Charmaz, 2006).

At this point, following Strauss' death in December 1996, the author would view the Strauss and Corbin version of GT as inactive at best, while Corbin continued to refine the theory. In its place, the CGT version by Charmaz is now probably the most widely used because Charmaz establishes how GT is a methodology adequately flexible to encompass a range of theoretical perspectives (Singh and Estefan, 2018).

There is a significant deliberation about the method, even amongst its originators and those that fall into each camp (Glaser, Strauss and Corbin, Charmaz) (Timonen *et al.*, 2018). While Glaser still adheres to the idea that the researcher's role can be minimised to discover GT in the data (Glaser and Strauss, 1967), constructivists stress that the investigator's effect on the testing process is unavoidable (Charmaz, 2006). The debate extended to the place of the literature review in GT. A retreat from the classic GT recommends avoiding the literature review until developing the theory with the agreement backup.

While Straus and Corbin (1994) suggest that knowing the literature is crucial to critique it concerning what the researcher is observing consciously, on the other hand, Thornberg *et al.* (2014) highlighted that prior principles and experiences fundamentally limit any attempt to be critical of the own researcher thinking. Nonetheless, since it is difficult to escape our understanding of the world, the research viewpoint is hard to conceive any better solution than vital self-awareness.

Furthermore, the theoretical sampling process aims to achieve theoretical saturation through an iterative data collection and analysis method, open-ended sampling approach, opportunistic interviews and then refining the sampling strategy (Goulding, 2002). However, there is a high debate on the viability and practicality of theoretical sampling and the pursuit of theoretical saturation (Boyчук *et al.*, 2004). Overall, according to Bryant (2017), GT is not merely a method for analysing interview data, but it informs all aspects of the research design.

GT is a research methodology that relates to business researchers (Goulding, 2002). Charmaz and Belgrave (2019) pointed out that GT allows the researcher to consider, create and use real-world facts about people involved. However, conducting educational and practical research using GT theory is not simple. When deciding on using the GT approach, a researcher must be aware of the different approaches of GT and which research approach matches the research aim, determining that the resulting theory is advantageous and useful.

GT methodology is a productive step in developing a particular phenomenon (Wertz *et al.*, 2011). According to Thompson and Smith (2009), there are three GT perspectives: Glaser, Straus and Corbin, and Charmaz, each having its strengths and weaknesses. These approaches have philosophical and methodological similarities and differences that can lead to selecting the most proper GT version for a specific research situation.

However, the GT approach's choice is subject to the researcher's philosophical perspective and understating the three GT approaches' philosophical foundations. Schreiber and Stern (2001) suggest that an adequate reflection on the three GT methods is essential to make an informed methodological collection that fits the researcher's philosophical perspective, empirical questions, and research priorities. After that, to help select the most appropriate method for this review, the methodological orientation of the three iterations of GT is clarified here.

3.3.1 Classic GT

It is believed that the Glaser GT version is a positivist and objectivist inductive passive approach. Therefore, Glaser (2007) was disadvantaged in having any philosophical orientation accompanying the GT theory perspective. In its place, Glaser (2007) argues that the research question with a specific context would shape any philosophical research dimensions. Nevertheless, Kennedy and Thornburg (2018) outlined that the researcher's Glaser refusal to adopt a philosophical perspective was critiqued as naïve, as the Glaser GT version is grounded on the positivist position.

Furthermore, Glaser positioned the researcher as a distant observer (objectivist). The other GT views were dismissed because they stigma the emerging theory (Glaser and Holton, 2004). Therefore, the researcher rejected the classic GT version as it may take years to advance a theory because of the abstract nature of people, place, and time outside of versatile DBA study.

3.3.2 Strauss and Corbin GT

GT version (Procedural Approach) like Glaser, an original philosophical viewpoint has not been formulated. The GT method, however, suggests a more postpositivist interpretation. Strauss and Corbin maintain the GT objectivist perspective, whereas admitting the opportunity of various standpoints on identifiable and external reality (Subjectivism) (Singh and Estefan, 2018).

Furthermore, the theory acknowledged the unavoidable influence of researchers. Nevertheless, Strauss and Corbin took a rigorous approach to lead GT studies to reduce participants' subconscious biases and maintain extreme objectivity (Corbin and Strauss, 2008). The author of this thesis even dismissed the Strauss and Corbin GT version since it opposes the scholar's philosophical stance (Interpretivism).

3.3.3 Constructivist GT

Charmaz's CGT version (interpretive and constructed approach) signifies moving from objectivism to a constructivist-Interpretivist position, in which truth is a function of a given phenomenon's perception of human activity. Thus,

Charmaz (2006) took a discrete role from the other two GT viewpoints as it assisted researchers during data collection and interpretation; therefore, Charmaz viewed the study as a collaborative activity for the interviewer and interviewee (Thornberg *et al.*, 2014). Therefore, this theory suggests constructing a theory with contributors and testing the field to decide if research members and other information handlers make sense of the theory (Abductive Approach).

Moreover, the Charmaz GT approach reflects present knowledge, such as existing literature and researchers' previous personal and professional experiences (Charmaz, 2006). However, Charmaz's conception of GT has been extensively criticised by Glaser and Strauss (1967), claiming that it is corrupt and pointlessly change to GT (Glaser and Holton, 2004).

3.4 The Rationale for Selecting the GT

The motivation for GT to be selected as the methodological approach for this study depends on several factors. Firstly, adequate institutional funding, along with a valuable tradition of using it to investigate individual and social phenomena, was one of the main factors strongly supporting the selection of GT for this study (Singh and Estefan, 2018).

Secondly, the reasons for choosing GT over other applicable methods, such as case study, are the phenomenon being examined, BD, the scope of this study, and the banking industry in Egypt. The adoption of GT to investigate BD could bridge the methodological gap in developing economies.

Thirdly, GT is valuable when studying a relatively new area in which there has been limited research. Creswell (2013) argues that researchers should adopt GT if there is very little research or information regarding a subject area. Correspondingly, Schreiber and Stern (2001) indicate that GT is sufficient for experiments in environments with initial differences in knowledge, and a new perspective may be helpful.

Due to the lack of theoretical and methodological data, GT was chosen because of the research sector's uniqueness in emerging economies, as previously identified in the literature review. Finally, the researcher contends that the GT strategy suits this study because GT focuses on theory generation as it grounds or evolves a theory within the context in which the phenomenon under study occurs (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). The section on research design, GT strengths and limitations and its variants will be addressed in depth.

Table 3-2 Summary of GT and justification of CGT approach

Approach	Overview of main characteristics	Recognition for regulating in or out of this research
<p>Glaserian</p> <p>Classic GT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Developed by Barney Glaser and Anselm Strauss. • Focus on constructing new theories, essential social structures, theoretical family coding, and critical categories. • It contains basic theoretical strategies. • Some scholars refer to it as a GT objectivist and a form of positivist study (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Although reading classical grounded theoretical publications was dismissed, it helped the researcher improve analytical sensitivity and extend his understanding of grounded theoretical science since it was not compatible with its conceptual positioning.
<p>Straussian</p> <p>GT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They were created by Anselm Strauss, whom Juliet and Corbin later co-published. • Outline of coding approaches applied to data • Storyline theoretical integration is an explanatory method for conceptualisation. • Initially, the approach was not explored, but the more recent iterations consider symbolic interactionism and pragmatism (Strauss and Corbin, 1997). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • As they were consistent with a CGT approach, some instruments and techniques were borrowed from Straussian GT. In addition, there were some similarities to the researcher's philosophical stance, but the constructivist-based theory was much more concerned with the researcher's ontology and epistemology. Therefore, Strauss's GT was refused.
<p>CGT</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Presented by Kathy Charmaz. • The goal is to create a theory to describe the phenomenon being observed from the participants' perspective. • Versatile in data processing and the final technique is a reference rather than a prescriptive process. • The philosophic positioning of relativism and constructivism is clearly stated (Bryant <i>et al.</i>, 2012). 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • This approach was selected as the primary approach; constructivist GT resonated most with the researcher's philosophical positioning

Source: Researcher

3.5 Researcher's Position

This sub-section provides a background of the researcher. This research is carried out using an interpretive approach and adopted the CGT methodology. Therefore, it is essential to highlight the investigator's role in interpreting the phenomenon under study (Wertz *et al.*, 2011).

In 2012, I completed a B.Sc. in Information Technology and Computing, The Open University, Walton Hall, England. I was motivated by my interest in data analytics to take many elective data science courses. After this, I started my career as an IT manager in the private jet market. I was introduced to the importance of data and how the enterprise reaps its insights.

There was a great deal to raise market visibility at the end of my job. In 2014, at the University of Hertfordshire, UK, I studied for my Master's Degree in Business Analysis and Consultancy. I was introduced to market study in the first semester of my Master's degree. However, I was more interested in the area where I researched and solved search engine optimisation problems as part of my graduation thesis: the personalisation of search engines (A case study of E-tourism- TUI Group UK).

In 2018, I was admitted to a Doctor of Business Administration (DBA) on my excellent academic background and research ability. As part of my doctoral degree, I have started this study in 2019, focused on my BD passion as it will be my future profession as a data scientist.

I chose this career using my previous education and experience in data management and my current business administration study. In addition, the banking industry was selected for this study because of my academic and professional background, finance and investment diploma and consultancy, and CMI certified business management consultant.

Furthermore, Egypt was selected for this study as my home country and considered one of the developing economies; this research will also make a genuine contribution to the body of knowledge.

I also directly performed all data collection by interviews and interpretation, with regular input from my supervisor and industry experts, to preserve consistency in developing the research process.

3.6 Research Design

Examining the associated discussion about BD's efficacy and relevance in Egypt's banking industry, covered in Chapter 2, revealed theoretical and methodological shortcomings. Concurrently, the study's nature, which comprehends the significant data phenomenon, is founded on the interpretivism philosophical stance of the researchers. Crotty (2000) argues that the researcher's distinct ontological and epistemological objectives dictate the suitable data collection and interpretation strategy. Moreover, Bell (2014) emphasised that a case study method is ideal for lone researchers since it allows for in-depth exploration of one aspect of an issue in a short amount of time.

GT study is a systematic process that attempts to build up a cycle and action or interaction about a substantive theme (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). To address the research questions and accomplish the ultimate objective of this research; thus, the CGT is the most appropriate methodology that can be used effectively in generating a substantive theory with intensive, open-ended and semi-structured interviews data collection methods (Charmaz and Belgrave, 2019).

This study employs abductive reasoning with a pragmatic approach to do this. Nonetheless, reservations about abductive reasoning are primarily concerned with a lack of completeness in either evidence, explanation, or both, as well as the practice challenge of drawing a disputed conclusion; however, the likelihood of drawing an incorrect conclusion can be reduced by increasing the number of observations (Svennevig, 2001). To conclude, objectivity is a fundamental part of this study to produce practical contributions while generating decent academic work.

Figure 3-4 The adopted paradigm for this research

Source: Researcher

The methodological processes of CGT are based entirely on the Glaser and Strauss, 1967 standard GT. Thus, the iterative process starts with selecting the most appropriate data-collection method, typically intensive interviews (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). Moreover, to simplify and fill out major categories resulting from the data, the gathered data is then coded where the theories become apparent, which is noted in memos, as theoretical sampling is used.

The iteration process proceeds until no further properties of the groups, known as theoretical saturation, emerge during the data collection process (Strauss and Corbin, 1994). Therefore, to guarantee the data is also not coerced into codes, the researcher uses codes in categories, categories into concepts, and guides further data collection, memo writing methods, and continuous comparison during this process (Charmaz, 2006).

Moreover, the methodological procedures adopted by Charmaz (2006) stresses researcher-centered approaches are advocated, data collection is regarded as a sequence of identical iterative cycles, theory should be focused

on data, and purposeful sampling and constant techniques should be encouraged. Moreover, Glaser (2007) noted that different interview research methods explain Glaser and Charmaz GT differences. Although Glaser described GT interviewing as passive listening, Charmaz stresses using extended, in-depth interviews that involve active listening (Boychuk *et al.*, 2004).

Bryant *et al.* (2012) asserted that the philosophical positioning supports the researcher in positioning the research among current scholarship and knowledge. Therefore, applied characteristics of CGT approaches should align with the researcher philosophical inclinations, data processing, analytical styles, and the envisioned usage of constructing a theory. Charmaz's (2000) approach was selected rigorously for this research, as it recognises the value of the embedded researcher, enabling the full engagement and involvement of the researcher in the local context (Robbins, 2016).

Furthermore, this study required reviewing the literature systematically in the BD application in Egypt. Grounding the interview questions on the literature builds the first place for the interview plans, which then progresses during consequent interviews, allowing prop and re-interview until reaching theoretical saturation, leading to identifying new knowledge and following theories.

3.7 Overview of the Fieldwork Procedure

GT is a systematic procedure to build a theory to explain a process. The research problem should represent the interests of the study participants and, therefore, should not be preconceived. (Glaser, 2007). Wertz *et al.* (2011) accurately expose the researchers' crucial concerns; the authors also suggested that they refrain from articulating a study issue in advance.

The study questions are, however, mandatory for a general field of interest to be chosen. Therefore, this thesis looks at BD as a science subject, owing to the growing relevance of BD in business management study. In addition, Glaser & Strauss (1967) emphasised the necessary speed of reading the literature to describe preconceived concepts that may not be applicable.

On the other hand, Strauss and Corbin (1994) consider using early-stage literature to stimulate theoretical sensitivity.

Given that, a minor literature review was held to a minimum at the outset, following the guidance of Glaser and Charmaz, only enough to collect sufficient details on BD from grasping the basic vocabulary and evidence as a preparation to communicate with the participants during interviews. After that, in the same substantive area of the study after the initial theory, a central narrowed literature review is further contrasted with the new data produced by theoretical sampling (Charmaz, 2006; Glaser, 2007).

Figure 3-4 The CGT approach research process for this study

Source: Researcher based on Charmaz (2006)

The conceptual framework describes how the researcher will proceed in the early stages of the investigation. The scholar's concern is then highlighted by the philosophical framework, which broadens the study direction. On the other hand, it might adopt a model from previous research to fit the needs of the inquiry. On the one hand, the researcher will describe the interactions of the many structures that must be investigated from the conceptual framework of the study's direction. Miles *et al.* (1994) articulated a conceptual framework that:

“Lays out the key factors, constructs, or variables, and presumes relationships among them.” (Miles *et al.*, 1994, p. 440)

However, using such a definition in GT studies defeats its very purpose. The following section describes the process of formulating the conceptual framework for this study. It justifies the reason for including it in this chapter rather than the literature review chapter.

The researcher is supposed to be reflexive about pre-conceptions, and on the other hand, researchers are not supposed to let a preconceived conceptual framework guide the research. However, Charmaz (2006) is somewhat ambiguous about this issue, as it is unclear where the sensitising concept stops and preconceived goals start. So, the researcher needs to be cautious about the degree to which preconceived goals influence GT research (Glaser and Strauss, 1967).

A few broad supervisory or sensitising concepts are allowable; however, working from a fully established conceptual framework would not fit any GT version, let alone a constructivist one. The core principle of GT is generating abstract concepts/constructs/theory from 'data', and this generative process should not be count too much on preconceptions (Charmaz, 2006). However, the researcher considers loose definitions of the conceptual/theoretical framework. The following section describes the process of formulating the conceptual framework for this study.

Figure 3-6 Illustrate the study's conceptual framework

Source: Researcher

The conceptual framework presented above depicts the cause and effect linkages between BD drivers, opportunities, Egypt's banking industry, and the four primary stakeholder groups concerning social, economic, and environmental factors.

3.8 Identifying Stakeholder Participants

To select the participants started with a stakeholder's analysis in the banking industry in Egypt. The results identified five stakeholders; then, four main stakeholders were recruited in the data collection process (Regulators, Employees, IT Facilitators, Customers) (Keighley, 2017; Urbinati *et al.*, 2019).

Table 3-3 Stakeholder groups in the banking industry in Egypt

No	Stakeholders	The Role
1	Shareholders and Investors	The influence of shareholders is decided by relevant legislation and the exercise of corporate governance by the Bank. The Bank is trying to grow its market share and contact its shareholders transparently and openly.
2	Executives	Collaborate with clients to form the Bank's standing, maintain the growth from its resources, and ensure the Bank's strategy and business missions.
	IT Facilitators	Technology has played an essential role in banks and IT facilities' functioning, from the storage, acquisition, compilation, sorting, review, and provision of information to meet customers' requirements.
3	Customers (Corporate customers, Retail customers)	Customers use the products offered by the bank. The stability of the bank depends on their expectations. Enterprises that significantly subsidize the national GDP have accounts opened with the bank.
4	Society (local communities)	The social and environmental spheres in which the banks work is connected to the local society.
5	Regulators The Egyptian Financial Supervisory Authority (EFSA)	The government is a critical collaborator and a bank client, distinguished by its institutions and businesses with a participating stake.

Source: Researcher, adapted from annual Reports of CIB (2016) and Attijariwafa (2017)

3.9 Observing and Interviewing Informants

GT approach aims to determine the foremost concern from the participants' perspectives and resolve that concern. Therefore, the researcher's task is to observe the participants so that the study's structured social life emerges.

This section aims to explain (a) who is involved in this research, (b) how the participants were chosen and (c) how many candidates have participated in this study.

Based on the emerging principle, data collection in GT is driven by the theoretical sampling method, an ongoing technique that promotes and determines what data is to be collected next. Thus, ethnographic method-informed CGT data collection methods seek to produce from the gathered data philosophical principle.

The CGT emphasises gathering primary data of the same ethnographic framework, similar to the ethnographic method (going to the real world of the participants), Participant contribution, the active quest for rich data, uninterrupted insights, active contact with participants and knowledge, spending time with participants and building confidence, getting close to the action) (Robbins, 2016).

According to Charmaz (2006), There are two sets of data: interviews: intense, but not interrogative, interviews, primarily open-ended questions, room for participants to express their insights and knowledge, and vigorously engage in dialogue; observations: deciding on what to observe, participate in the daily routine without interruption, and take extensive field notes. So far, this section highlights the data collection process intended for this study.

Design of Research Interviews: This sub-section discusses the method of designing BD study interview questions learned from a minor literature review: the development of the BD phenomenon, the alignment of BD with main operational variables, and the advantages and disadvantages of using BD in the banking sector.

The study interview with executives and IT facilitators comprises approximately twenty open-ended questions, split into four parts. The interviews with the Consumers and Regulators consisted of approximately ten open-ended questions, representing the participant's familiarity with the BD definition. The researcher adopted Kvale (1996) recommendations on several questions, such as familiarisation, elaboration, indirect questioning, and overt questioning. Interpreting issues were deemed to be primarily critical. Therefore, to minimise the possibility of bias and misunderstanding, the contributors were asked to explain their responses, if possible.

Data would then be obtained over three months by semi-structured interviews. A brief of the research was submitted via e-mail for acceptance of the involvement. Open-ended, face-to-face interviews with the four stakeholders were held. The interviews are mainly conversation-driven and are approximately 45 minutes long and focus on the interviewees' experience with BD application, significantly the benefits and challenges of using BD and strategies used to overcome them.

The abductive approach directed the subsequent interview questions, which were changed by how the data was analysed, and original concepts and categories focused on the evolving codes. In other words, questions were changed as the data collection progressed to focus on the crucial issues presented in the interviews. In the next part, we will go through how we choose interviewees.

Recruiting the Study Participants: Participants are chosen to inform research questions better and improve their comprehension of the underlying phenomenon. The use of purposive sampling is a well-established approach in qualitative research (Silverman, 2013). Therefore, to conduct a qualitative analysis, the research should strive to choose applicants that meet criteria that will deliver a sample that would yield the research's knowledge to accomplish the research's purpose. There are several techniques within the purposive sampling domain (Thornberg *et al.*, 2014).

Random purposive sampling was employed in this study because the researcher purposively identified the potential participants. The criteria for selection was to choose who is benefiting from (beneficial) or affected by (victim) the use of BD in the banking industry. The selection of these particular stakeholders' group was to embark on the empirical evidence selection (interviews), based on the stakeholders' group: Experience – the perception of BD in better organisational performance (by each stakeholders group); Preference for the mode of BD used by the financial sector workers; Views on the ministry of finance in Egypt; The use of BD in the financial industry; BD standards and staff training; and Development of BD application skills.

How many participate in this study: Decisions about data were determined using theoretical consideration, representative and randomness. In GT research, while considering time and resource constraints, the researcher should stay in the field until the point of theoretical saturation has been reached (Singh and Estefan, 2018). Achieving theoretical saturation is approaching a point where new data does not require a categorization change, using a frequent contrast of categories with data (abductive inference) that varies from conventional saturation in qualitative data processing (Tomiyama *et al.*, 2003).

Therefore, the researcher was unable to determine how many participants would be selected from the population but aimed at conducting interviews between 30-40 participants from the pre-identified stakeholders' group, that would avoid the saturation of researcher preconception and let the perception of the participants emerge (Thornberg *et al.*, 2014).

3.10 Data Analysis Method

This thesis adopted the CGT method; data processing and interpretation procedures, including evaluating the data's fundamental nature, reducing the data to abstract concepts, and summarising the data. In this process, the researcher followed Charmaz's (2000) recommendations: applying multiple interpretations of the data, being flexible when looking for answers and leads, the language used for expression, and multiple expressions and realities. This part also illustrates interpreting the data for this research (Wertz *et al.*, 2011). Charmaz(2006) outlined that the data analysis process consists of four main stages: a) Initial coding, b) Focused coding, c) Theoretical coding, and d) Write-up.

Initial Coding: At this point, labels are applied to significant sections of the results. The researcher vigorously interacts with the data by seeking tacit and explicit interpretations, meanings underlying the statements of contributors, and unsubstantiated claims of their statements; categorising sections of the data: actions, occurrences, and processes; utilising gerund modifier and performing line-by-line coding: encoding each line of the document using a

constant method of comparison, contrasting data to codes, data with data and codes to codes (Goulding, 2002).

Focused Coding: Identifying relevant or influential codes and determining their relationship with other codes. Assessment of the initial codes generated: the investigator acknowledges the codes' functional definitions and the codes-related assumptions. Filtering codes: choosing appropriate or prevailing codes, generating categories through grouping the residual codes around the dominant codes, and eventually identifying category trends and gaps when matching the data to the categories (Bryant *et al.*, 2012).

Theoretical Coding: The researcher generates connections amid categories relating them to data to form an abstract description of an action, occurrence, or procedure by combining the categories (focused codes) (Abductive inference). So, the theory of an abstract statement is produced, the initial theory is contrasted further with the latest information gathered from theoretical sampling, and continuous comparison is made until saturation is achieved (Robbins, 2016).

The research used manual coding for close interactions with the data and sustained involvement in the coding process, enabling conscious awareness processing.

Write-Up: In GT analysis methods, the final step is to start writing the principle that accompanies the theoretical overview; this stage occurs due to the processing and theoretical coding of the previous steps. Therefore, this section is presented in full detail in the following findings (Charmaz and Belgrave, 2019).

Figure 3-7 Illustrates the GT Analysis process

Source: Charmaz (2006)

3.11 Appraising GT and the Research Design

This section presents a theoretical discussion of the standards for evaluating the current study's consistency and sheds light on assessing the GT research. Strauss and Corbin (2002) noted that the validity and reliability concepts were substituted by a verification concept that guarantees that the researcher's analysis outcomes are correct from the researcher and the respondents' viewpoint.

In essence, Onwuegbuzie and Johnson (2006) argue that reliability and validity are unsuitable for abridging the issues raised concerning the research quality, favouring legitimation as an alternative. However, despite the apparent conflict

in terminology, the researcher trusts that it is necessary to make a case for data consistency in this study.

According to Lincoln and Guba (1990), triangulation is a qualitative research procedure to report validity questions. Denzin (1978) distinguished three elementary kinds of triangulation: data, investigator and theory. Although Glaser and Strauss (1967) noted that the researcher included it for comprehensiveness and demonstrated the enforcement of triangulation in GT, arguing that triangulation is a qualitative data mechanism that is not necessary for GT as it is incorporated in the GT method.

Data Triangulation: This study employs data triangulation by interviewing four different stakeholders. The selection criteria were explained in the Identifying Stakeholder Participants section as selecting the main groups that either benefit from or being victims of the BD phenomenon (Fusch and Ness, 2015).

GT explains how the world of the participants works (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). Understanding their primary concerns and continual resolution opens up possibilities for participants to understand what is happening in their world (Artinian et al., 2009).

Therefore, under the guidance of theoretical sampling, data were collected and comparatively analysed. Internal consistency was indorsed by the rigorous devotion to the complete set of CGT procedures. The theoretical sampling, constant comparative and memo procedures dealt with research and participant bias(Charmaz, 2006).

Investigator Triangulation: Refers to the use of different assessors (Cameron, 2009). GT does not require mandatorily a third person to authorise the excellence of the analytical procedures and findings. Theoretical sampling, continuous comparison and memos create an ongoing verification method for concepts, categories and properties during the theory's generation (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Strauss and Corbin, 1994).

Therefore, this study's findings were discussed and reviewed with the academic supervision panel and the bank's quality manager, who secured the data access. The feedback provided replicated the assessor's experiences, and on no single point did they differ from the researcher's findings.

Theory Triangulation: It corresponds to several points of view for the analysis of a single data set. The formulation of theory in current literature strengthens the internal legitimacy and theoretical level of creating the theory; the GT aims to produce a logical account of a phenomenon, not an exact explanation (Strang, 2015). Therefore, reliability was attained through a systematic process of theoretical sampling and constant comparison.

According to Glaser (2007), the researcher's preconception can undermine internal consistency. The constant comparative process deals with the preconceptions that establish the reflexivity issue. Therefore, internal consistency should follow if the GT has been completed appropriately.

3.11.1 Evaluation Criteria for GT Research

Bryant *et al.* (2012) noted that grounded theories are not an exact picture or description of the studied world; instead, they are interpretive descriptions. Therefore, Glaser acclaimed that grounded theories should be assessed based on four criteria: Fit, Relevance, Workability and Modifiability (Glaser and Strauss, 1967).

Fit: The most relevant of the four criteria is an evolving theory describing and matching the researchers' perspectives and stakeholder groups not engaged in the theory building. Fit is an external validity attribute that reveals the match amid the ideas and events they present. By constant comparison with new data from a new scenario, GT fit can create correspondence (Goulding, 2002).

Workability: Refers to the theory capacity to identify and clarify the participants' primary concern in the field under review and foresee what is likely to occur. In other words, the principle is a logical description of what occurs in

a functional area, the mechanism by which the main problem is included, and how it is periodically overcome (Glaser, 2007).

Relevance: The GT methodology distinguishes the participants' foremost concerns in a functional area and how they routinely resolve those concerns. Therefore, participants should evaluate the significance of the theory. Relevance is accomplished when the standards of fit and workability are encountered; only when GT is significant to contributors is it grabbed (Glaser and Strauss, 1967; Glaser and Holton, 2004).

Modifiability: Represents the theory's quality to regulate when current data are likened to new data (Strauss and Corbin, 1994). By way of the new data are concerned, it activates theoretical sampling, constant comparison and memo. Thereby, the existing theoretical framework exhibits modifiability that replicates the animated quality of GT. Thus, GT can be tested for developing fit, the main concern conceptual account, and its resolution is the abstractness of time, place and people, modifiable by data emerged from a new situation (Charmaz, 2006), which shed light on the dependability and potential for future development characteristics of GT.

In this way, these criteria will be revisited at the end of this thesis to demonstrate how well the generated theory evaluates against them, in Chapter 6, section 6.2, Evaluation for the Substantive Theory.

3.12 Ethical Issues

The study's author guarantees that this study meets the ethical standard; this research was strictly governed by UWS ethics committee guidance. Moreover, data collection only proceeded after the UWS ethical approval was granted. "Application 8219: Comprehending the role of BD in the banking industry in Egypt, submission 6881, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC. You may now proceed with your study". Therefore, analysis (i.e. name, address, date of birth & contact information) and the participants' personal opinions will remain private and not be released.

Access Consideration: This research would make use of primary and secondary data access. Also, to obtain the primary data by way of performing interviews, access authorisation is mandatory. Therefore, a formal email was sent to bank executives, managers, and customers in Egypt to access permission. The email enclosed a summary of this study and how the collected data would be used. Consequently, traditional access was used in the interview stage, email and phone conversations, and the LinkedIn website to arrange the interviews.

Participants Autonomy: A clear written and oral brief about the resolution of this study, the researcher's contact details, and the collected data used in this research were provided to the contributors before giving their approval.

Confidentiality and Anonymity: The participants' anonymity was highly deliberated. Bank's names and persons' names were encoded during the interview transcription. Also, confidentiality awareness as a declaration was given to the participants before conducting the interview.

Non-Maleficence and Beneficence: During the data collection processes, it was significant for the author to ensure that contributors did not feel threatened emotionally or physically in any way. If any inconvenience, withdrawal, or contributor had any questions, the researcher's contact details were provided to all participants.

Justice and Exhaustiveness: The author of this study ensured that this study is unbiased by any exclusion (culture, ethnicity, disability, religion, gender, age). Therefore, this study followed the impartial selection criteria to ensure that all participants were given a fair chance. Moreover, all the collected data were correspondingly preserved.

Data Protection: The collected data is available only to the researcher and the head of studies. Both captured data from primary and secondary sources are stored on a memory stick encoded and password protected for data storage purposes. As soon as this study is finished, all accumulated data will also be erased.

3.13 Piloting

Aim: The pilot study is used to determine the viability, applicability and practicality of the CGT approach, to explore the four significant stakeholders' group (Executives, Regulators, IT Facilitators, and Customers) efficacy of the data collection method. To define the respondents' primary concern in the practical field and how that concern is addressed, the importance of no preconception and the treatment of leading the study in the banking position was dominant (Glaser, 2007).

Background: BD is a vast volume of structured, semi-structured, and unstructured information which every day overwhelms an enterprise. The amount of data is not, however, significant. Nevertheless, it is notable how BD perspectives are used for improved decision-making and strategic company to trend future opportunities (Gepp *et al.*, 2018).

Organisations are speeding up their attempts to drive value from BD. In comparison, the volume of data handled increases rapidly among enterprises (Del Vecchio *et al.*, 2017). With enormous data growth, opportunities emerge, as well as challenges. Leveraging BD in the banking industry in Egypt is still at the infant stage. As the data 3Vs continue to grow, so do the banking opportunities in Egypt, yet what is essential is driving value from this data for competitive advantage (Côte-Real *et al.*, 2019). Therefore, this study explores BD's importance to the banking industry, particularly to Egypt's commercial banks.

Method: A CGT methodology with a random sample of the four different stakeholders was used in this pilot project. Intensive, open-ended, semi-structured interviews were used to collect the data, driven by the participant's responses through online contact requests (Skype) (Charmaz, 2006). Also, to ensure that the research process would be suitable for attaining the research aim (Robert K. Yin, 2016), the importance of no preconception and handling the difficulty of leading the research in the banking location were dominant to identify.

Results: This pilot study suggested that the CGT approach was a practical, viable approach to investigate the bank's stakeholders' view. It also highlighted the necessary implications for the Egyptian banking industry and its customers, ultimately improving customer satisfaction. This pilot study further affirmed the usefulness of data collection, with the endorsement by participants that data collection occurred without urging the researcher to collect data. The initial pilot study also revealed that the field's solution would ensure valuable quality data by performing open-ended interviews, defining and conceptualising the primary concern.

Issues Identified: This pilot study did not show any actual issues; on the contrary, the study signified the importance of being prepared, caring and thoughtful about the participants as crucial for accomplishment. Nevertheless, issues were still expected, despite meticulous planning of meetings and effective communication with the participants.

For instance, using an online platform for interviews weakened the interview, as participants were not comfortable using digital communication, which affected the flow and depth of the participants' conversations. Human interaction is critical to get the participants' insights, so the researcher decided to collect the data through face-to-face interviews (Bouchard *et al.*, 2014).

Therefore, the researcher had to modify the interview structure by adding a brief intro about BD for each stakeholder group to open the conversation to reduce the meeting tension. Then the researcher proceeds with the main section of the data-collection process.

Conclusion: This pilot study provided a perceptive introduction to CGT methodology. From a learning viewpoint, this study postulates the researcher with an insightful approach to conduct interviews with participants in a fruitful, non-threatening, yet accessible mode. It also suggested that the analytical methodology of the CGT was appropriate to examine stakeholder insights. This pilot study also offered an opportunity to validate the theoretical sampling as a participant selection, data processing, and data analysis technique. Finally, this

pilot study stressed the benefit of being agile and prepared for unexpected problems during the study duration.

3.14 Summary

Theoretical and methodological reasoning for the research approach has been discussed in this chapter. The qualitative character of this research suggests that interpretivism is the best research paradigm for this study. The modelling approach given was abductive. This study is classified as cross-sectional since the researcher gathered the data at a particular moment in time.

Potential data gathering and interpretation approaches were examined, and the researcher concluded that CGT's methodology is the most fitting for this research. Furthermore, GT studies could be an active and adaptable alternative to encompass the scope of study and advance the study's ability to solve problems (Charmaz, 2006).

Intensive, open-ended, semi-structured interviews gathered data following CGT procedures. A minor literature review was accompanied by the first forward data collection method, and the value of the no-preconceived definition was taken into account (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). The chapter also sheds light on selecting the participants' criteria through a stakeholder's analysis that produced the conceptual research framework; purposive sampling was employed in this study.

Likewise, the chapter has clarified how the empirical data is analysed following the CGT guideline to identify its primary concern. The chapter ended with a review of the research quality by qualitative triangulation in fostering a possible real-world benefit and achieving an acceptable level of research quality that supports the researcher's objective of doing much academic work and making a new empirical contribution use of BD. Finally, it outlined the requirements for a GT study's quality. The following section, Chapter 4, reports the study results of CGT data analytics.

4 Chapter Four: Findings-The Views of Stakeholders

4.1 Introduction

This chapter contains the core of the study, offering the primary contribution of this research on the scope and role of Big Data (BD) in developing nations by using Egypt's banking industry as an example.

The comprehensive data collection included 33 intense, open-ended interviews with diverse persons from the major stakeholder groups. This resulted in a large amount of data, which led to a range of conclusions. Thus, this chapter recounts the interviewees' perspectives, representing the many stakeholder groups involved in Egypt's banking industry, and reflects their voices. Respondents were questioned in English going forward; however, many spoke English as a second language; this might be seen in how they responded to inquiries occasionally.

Hence, the chapter portrays the views of:

- 1) The customers
- 2) The Executives
- 3) The IT Facilitators
- 4) The regulators

The research methodology chosen for this research (i.e. Grounded Theory used) is included in this chapter to help answer the research questions. Therefore, this chapter organises the results to demonstrate the relevant categories built into the theory according to the evolving substantive theory.

Moreover, to show the variation and originality of the data, quotations were used to transmit the story's whole meaning as it was told. Hence, minor editing was conducted on the interview transcripts. However, to ensure the original context and concepts are still expressed in the interpreted data, close attention was given as much as possible to maintain the verbatim text.

The chapter thus comprises the following sections: Synthesising the Findings, BD and its Role in Banking and Finance, The Impact of BD on banking and Financial Systems, Investment in BD: lesson learnt, and Summary.

Table 4-1 Shows respondents' background

Interviewee	Age	Gender	Years with the bank	Profession
Customers: C01	35	M	6	Accountant
Customers: C02	33	M	12	Teacher
Customers: C03	42	F	9	Photographer
Customers: C04	32	M	11	Architect
Customers: C05	39	M	3	Jewellery Designer
Customers: C06	50	M	5	Senior Lawyer
Customers: C07	38	F	7	Engineering Consultant
Customers: C08	36	M	10	Marketing Manager
Customers: C09	48	F	13	Petroleum Engineers
Customers: C10	29	M	2	Database Administrator
Employee: E01	34	F	3	Quality Control Manager
Executives: E02	42	M	7	Financial Advisers
Executives: E03	38	M	2	Branch Manager
Executives: E04	37	M	12	Senior Teller
Executives: E05	42	M	9	Audit Manager
Executives: E06	34	F	8	Bank Teller
Executives: E07	39	M	3	Assistant Branch Manager
Executives: E08	26	F	9	Business Banking Officer
Executives: E09	42	M	10	Customer Service Manager
Executives: E10	35	M	4	Internal Auditor
IT-Facilitators: I01	41	M	3	Information Security Manager
IT-Facilitators: I02	38	M	5	Senior Software Engineer
IT-Facilitators: I03	43	M	7	Data Analyst Manager
IT-Facilitators: I04	45	M	2	Database Administrator
IT-Facilitators: I05	43	M	6	Network Engineer
IT-Facilitators: I06	32	M	4	IT Manager
IT-Facilitators: I07	44	M	5	Developer
IT-Facilitators: I08	37	M	7	IT manager
Regulators: R01	45	M	12	Legal Advisor
Regulators: R02	43	M	10	Senior Lawyer
Regulators: R03	37	F	4	Legal Advisor
Regulators: R04	35	M	8	Legal Advisor
Regulators: R05	40	F	1	Legal Consultant

Source: Researcher

4.2 Synthesising the Findings

This section summarises the participants' views regarding BD's role and extent in the Egyptian banking sector. According to Saldaña (2021), there is no single way of presenting qualitative findings. Accordingly, this section synthesises the findings to tell the story.

In comparison, the results explain the emerging substantive theory of how the basic organising phenomenon and the main categories were progressed into a theory. Furthermore, the CGT approach for data analysis is relatively standard: tagged identified patterns in data (Concepts), after that, grouped the emerged concepts into categories, then grouped categories into themes. The full details of labelling and classifications are described in the next chapter, Analysis and Discussion part.

Table 4-2 Summary the broad themes that emerged from the analysis

1- What are the challenges of BD use in the financial services industry in Egypt?			
Theme	Frequency	Meaning	Evidence
Organisational Mindset	200	Thoughts and beliefs form the organisational culture. However, many banks are often guided by personal experience, instincts, SME awareness and customer feedback.	<i>“Organisational culture sets the context for everything the bank does. I believe there are challenges of a data-driven culture on business, especially learning to trust data.” (I07)</i>
Turning data into actionable insights	117	Transform the current data analytics into actionable market insights.	<i>“It is challenging to converting data into something valuable because of many reasons: skills shortage, organisational culture, the digital infrastructure of within the bank.” (E04)</i>
Customer concerns about privacy	97	BD technology has promising applications to provide banks with significant strides ahead, but it still has a giant red flag on privacy and interference.	<i>“There is nothing in Egyptian law that provides levels of privacy protections.” (R03)</i>
Legacy Infrastructure	71	Even though they have moved to cloud technologies, banking systems cannot handle the constant inflow of data necessary for BD.	<i>“Customer data is monitored through the KYC system, and banking systems are often decades old.” (E02)</i>
Regulatory Pressure	55	BD may have critical legal and legislative issues that have complications and limitations due to their sheer scale.	<i>“The policies of all Egyptian banks are derived from the Central Bank’s instructions.” (C10)</i>

2- What is the impact of using BD on the banking sector in Egypt?			
Theme	Frequency	Meaning	Evidence
Improved Customer Services	131	Impact of BD on Business. With the help of BD, banks aim at offering personalised customer services	<i>"Deeper understanding and prediction of customer behaviour." (E02)</i>
Boosting Overall Performance	44	A performance review will measure workers' success by meeting the monthly/quarterly/year goals.	<i>"Improve the performance of employees." (E10)</i>
Enhanced Marketing	40	Better target marketing.	<i>"Designing new, tailored services." (E4)</i>
Competitive advantage	29	BD is the modern field of strategic advantage.	<i>"A bigger picture of the market status." (E01)</i>
Better Decision-Making	25	Studies suggest that companies powered by data make smarter strategic choices and enjoy high operating efficiency.	<i>"We make decisions based on the data provided by the client." (E02)</i>
Efficient Risk Management	10	Predictive models for preventing theft and tracking and interpreting consumer actions for risk control are the most widely used BD technologies.	<i>"Improved risk management." (I05)</i>
More accessible Filing of Regulatory Compliance	9	For the smooth functioning of banks, they need to meet the criteria set by government regulatory authorities. However, it gets complicated because they have thousands of customers to deal with daily and maintain their records.	<i>"Yes, the bank follows the central bank policy regulations." (I06)</i>
Cost Reduction	8	BD aims to provide strategic insight that can decrease costs and increase organisational effectiveness.	<i>"Reducing the cost of operation." (I02)</i>

3- What lessons have been learnt from investment in BD in Egypt's banking sector over the last decade?			
Theme	Frequency	Meaning	Evidence
Higher competition in the market	2	BD modelling may help banks classify customer preferences based on their spending patterns, buying preferences, reward transactions, and personal or financial backgrounds. In achieving customer satisfaction by creating customised banking strategies for them, these details play a crucial role.	<i>"Make new income streams over data-driven proposals, such as personalised recommendations, become more efficient to contest with FinTech businesses, which use cutting-edge expertise to provide clientele with banking and financial services."</i> (I06)
A deeper understanding of customers	1	BD modelling can help banks identify consumer behaviour based on buying habits, purchasing behaviours, buying incentives, and personal or financial history.	<i>"To gain a deeper understanding of customers."</i> (E07)
New services and products	1	A commitment to boosting client awareness by developing products, services, and other approaches suited to their unique needs based on their existing customer profiles is an example of dedication.	<i>"The development and speed of operations within the bank."</i> (E09)

Source: Researcher

4.3 BD and its Role in Banking and Finance

As mentioned in chapter 2, various publications indicate that the world has witnessed a noticeable shift in daily life due to technological advances resulting in a visible impact on businesses and the wider society. The general view amongst the various stakeholders approached for this research was that the banking sector is no different and has undergone regulatory reform on how conventional financial institutions communications have been altered and how this has been changed continuously for the last decade.

Accordingly, part of these changes derives from the developments in financial technologies. Therefore, I sought to understand how participants would explain BD and approached the employees' group (i.e. E01-E09) and asked about BD description and its use in the bank. During their interviews, every interviewee of the above executives' group highlighted how BD reformed the market. They further indicated that many banks are creating innovative financial products and services for their customers. This latest trend is questioning the conventional banking paradigm.

In the interviews, the data reveals that Egypt's banking sector has been a driving source a data-driven sector for several years, four IT group (e.g. I01, I04, I07, and I08) discusses how banks are managing vast amounts of customer data and using data mining in trading in the stock market. In the same vein, two interviewees (I01, I03) drew attention to the bank sector's focus on interpreting the data required to grasp and assess risk effectively. Participant I03 stated that:

“Banks rely on data mining to be able to play their main roles; it is, therefore, safe to assume that this data is a powerful force in the market.”
(I03)

Three IT participants (I01, I04, and I07), however, raised concerns about the increase in the abundance of data coming beyond BD's scope, i.e. vast density, high velocity and a wide range of data opportunities resulting from the emergence of new consumer, industry and regulatory, data from multiple

sources, adding to these challenges is the co-existence of organised and unstructured records.

When asked participants to characterise the bank as a data-driven enterprise, there was a sense of agreement amongst three interviewees from the IT group (I03, I05, I06) that unstructured data of financial services and banking sector could be seen as an arena in which substantial a new market activity is. For example, the interviewee (I08) recognised that much market interest is gained from vast bank documents, primarily in text form, containing details submitted by call centre operators and notes relating to particular claims and events.

A standard view amongst interviewees was that Interviewee I04, database administrator, had sought advice that a value can be derived more reliably from such datasets with the aid of BD technology. However, the use of this form of unstructured data was established to extract easier, more targeted market benefits. Also, participant I04 asserted that:

“Value is an essential aspect of BD in this industry — how does an enterprise not only capture and handle BD but how can value-added data be found. Given that data is the most valuable commodity, this technology is beneficial and differentiates the bank.” (I04)

Talking about the BD potentials to banks, E01, quality control manager, highlighted the importance of BD in knowledge discovery by saying:

“Through exploiting BD, banks and financial services companies would obtain a thorough knowledge of economies, consumers, networks, products, legislation, rivals, suppliers and employees that will make them more competitive. However, to my knowledge, not all banks in Egypt are using BD.” (E01)

The previous quotations showed how BD is a promising market phenomenon and is expected to drive the global BD industry's advancement in financial services. Participant I01, Information security manager, explained in terms of infrastructure management:

“Banks pursue a market-driven approach to BD: first, consumer requirements are identified, and existing internal resources and capabilities are balanced to meet business opportunities when investing in data and network sources.” (I01)

On the other hand, some interviewees (I03, I05, E10) raised their concerns about how Egyptian banks are lag behind their international peers.

Participant I03 highlighted the reason for that is a lack of focus on unstructured data:

“There is a lack of focus on unstructured data is attributed to continuing attempts by banks to consolidate broad data.” (I03)

While participant I05 pointed out:

“Egypt’s banks lag behind their cross-industry peers; within their BD applications, they use more sophisticated data systems. Some of these banks analyse audio data regularly generated in abundance in retail bank call centres. In comparison, the other review social media records.” (I05)

Similarly, participant E10 further argued:

“Not all banks, however, maintain the same pace, some banks are focused on identifying core principles relative, and the rest are either establishing a BD roadmap or already executing BD Pilots.” (E10)

The above quote outlined some of the BD limiting factors, which I will investigate in the next part. First, though, there is a need to address drivers for BD adoption in the banking sector.

4.3.1 Drivers for BD Adoption in Banking

The section below further illustrates BD's role in financial services, and we now turn to BD technology adoption drivers in the financial industry.

When asked about the favourable factors of adopting BD technologies in the financial sector, the following drivers were identified by IT participants (I02, I05):

“The rapid increase in the amount of data generated and government regulations are the main drivers for the implementation of BD analytics in the banking sector.” (I02)

“As technology progresses, the number of smart gadgets users use to facilitate purchases (such as smartphones) is also proliferating, increasing the number of transactions. This exponential growth of data demands improved collection, organisation, integration, and analysis.” (I05)

Interviewees besides I02 and I05 explained BD drivers in the banking sector: Technological advances lead to more significant volumes of input data. Participants (E02, I06) further said:

“Accessibility and availability of electronic financial transfers have contributed to ever-increasing activity and growth of new markets. customers can make more purchases, more often than not, for other forms of transactions, so they can do that by tapping on a button in the privacy of their own homes.” (E02)

“The rise of the Internet of Things (IoT) would also raise user data, leading to new, permanent data sources (even though the consumer does not communicate with the bank or the insurer).” (I06)

Participants (I07, E01) reported the new modern authentication methods on adopting BD in banks and reiterated:

“Biometric authentication and continuous verification (e.g. mouse movements and keyboard rhythm, accelerometer and gyro sensor readings on a mobile phone) will also significantly increase the amount of data to be processed in near-real-time mode.” (I07)

“The development of substantially flexible interfaces (Open APIs) also enables our bank to acquire useful information about our clients from the data obtained by rivals.” (E01)

The previous quotations suggest that technical developments allow vast quantities of diverse and varied data to be processed instantly. Various market drivers are at the centre of this growth and illustrate why BD has grown exponentially to become one of the banking industry's most desired subjects.

Interviewee I04 elaborated on the discussion above:

“The data sets are growing so large and dynamic. Conventional tactics can no longer process such data at a comparatively low cost and within a reasonable timeline. Luckily, the aggregation of new technologies provides a solution to this issue, enabling those data sets to be processed in near-real-time and at a lower cost.” (I04)

Participant E04, a senior teller, had pursued advice: The changes in consumer attitudes and expectations are now reversed. Participant I03, data analyst manager, argued that customers interact with their banks more and more digitally, which minimises their encounters. However, executive participant E04 considered it more advantageous at the same time and further commented:

“Customers now have transient partnerships with several banks. Banks no longer have a full picture of their consumers' perceptions, buying habits, and behaviour. BD innovations thus play a crucial role in facilitating consumer focus in this new paradigm.” (E04)

While IT participant contended:

“It is possible to gather even more customer data in an automatic manner (e.g. browser history, cell phone geolocation data, the abstract timing of transactions) than when the customer visits a store. Such statistics can be used to show the lessened input of the client due to the lack of informal contact.” (I03)

Interviewee E08, business banking officer, demonstrated that people are also now using social networking: while these outlets used to be confined to proprietary private networks for acquaintances, consumers are now using this networking, e.g. to connect with corporations:

“Banks and insurers will communicate further across these networks to deliver resources and obtain insight into their clients.” (E08)

While Participant I01 called attention to consumers data across several channels, expect ever more elevated, minimal prices, and customer-centric service around the clock this to do so:

“An in-depth, comprehensive knowledge of the client is required to deliver such a tailored service. In my view, this can only be done by leveraging all available industry data using BD techniques.” (I01)

For Example, participant I08, IT Manager, referred to the changing business models: motivated by the reasons mentioned above, banks exist in an environment fundamentally diverse from the industry a few years back:

“The implementation of BD analytics is essential to help develop business models for corporate banks aimed at maintaining market share as a result of growing pressure from other sectors.” (I08)

Another participant, R01, legal advisor, also indicated another driver, such as regulatory pressure: The recent surge of new legislation has required banks to report to regulators and central banks more complex and robust data:

“There is an increase in fines due to non-compliance with the CBE regulations. It requires banks to gather more and more data in a controlled manner.” (R01)

Interviewee I05, network engineer, further suggested that:

“It is possible to produce the requisite regulatory records automatically, but also to make all the details accessible to regulators for ad-hoc inquiries.” (I05)

Participant R05, a legal consultant, also stated:

“Egyptian authorities now demand a more open and accurate view of financial and insurance companies, which ensures that reports are no longer needed but raw statistics. Financial firms will need to ensure that their raw data can be analysed at the same level of granularity as regulators.” (R05)

Participant R03, legal advisor, further argued:

“Banking services' primary concern is to ensure that banking services follow all the government's regulatory enforcement standards; BI instruments could further assess and monitor all regulatory specifications by individual customer requests for correct validation.” (R08)

When asked to elaborate on the previous excerpts, regulators participant R04, legal advisor, replied:

“Banking industry is subject to strict regulatory procedures. Banks fail to remain under the rules while raising their earnings. Therefore, the bank needs a high degree of control and reporting and operate within a relatively stable system. This detail is also used for transactions monitoring, which identifies trading patterns.” (R04)

Five employee participants (E01, E03, E05, E06, E10) discussed the pressure to lower fixed costs: Profit margins decline in the financial services industry due to rising demand and low interest rates. For example, E03, branch manager, explained:

“Both banks and insurers are now expected to reduce their operating costs by rising market efficiency. Many of these efficiency gains can then be driven by the information acquired by BD.” (E03)

The quote above by participant E03 also showed it is necessary to create cost-saving processes because it increases the bank's profit by reducing service and product costs.

Two people from IT and employee groups (I01, E07): as bribery and financial fraud grow more common, and banks must safeguard their most important asset, client loyalty. It increases the need for more reliable contact networks and consumer data across various encryption approaches:

Participant I01 further argued that:

“Risk-based authentication is one of the most interesting, where the fraud detection engine analyses the risk profile for each channel request and calculates the required level of security (authentication). This fraud detecting method uses customer insights to spot inconsistencies in the behaviour of the product.” (I01)

Interviewee E07, assistant branch manager, detailed that:

“Not only will banks that do not grow and drive the BD technology be left behind, but they will also become redundant. In deciding the survival of banks in the modern era, the use of BD analytics and other high-tech technologies to change the current banking sector would play a major role.” (E07)

The views above (I01, E07) demonstrated situational awareness skills towards BD's three critical drives in banking: information security, survival, and future potentials.

4.4 The Impact of BD on Banking and Financial Systems

Some interviewees (I02, I08, E04) reflected on the amount of data provided by credit card purchases, tweets, and even every web page opened every day is enormous, and linked these data to several opportunities to leverage the knowledge with the most innovative firms in many sectors, and the banking sector is no different:

Employee participant E04 confirmed that:

“The bank has enough data at hand to become more resourceful, more customer-centric, and, as a result, more profitable.” (E04)

Similarly, IT participant pointed out that:

“Banks and other financial companies can take advantage of advanced analytics in three major areas: customer engagement, organisational optimisation and employees’ engagement.” (I08)

Emerging from the above evidence, the convergence of business cases and technical capacities, which exposes the potential for better business processes, includes finding more places where BD tools can be used most effectively.

4.4.1 Advantages of BD in the Financial Sector

Having defined what is meant by BD's role in the financial sector, I am now moving on to discuss BD's potentials in the financial service industry. When asked if the participants became aware of the present and future advantages offered to the bank by BD solutions, (E04, E06) illustrated knowledge of BD innovations emerging from self-learning via the bank's multiple contact networks. However, other respondents (E03, E05, E9) of the Employees group see BD as traditional data and no new opportunities.

Nevertheless, when asked to indicate the most significant opportunity to use BD in their bank, some executives see BD as a potential business improvement. Quotations by E01 reflected her views of the BD potentials:

“Improved customer services. customer cultivation, turning the bank into a customer-centric enterprise: empowering empowers with common customer experience (i.e. 360 ° degree integrated experience of the consumer), offering a broad, unified view of consumer knowledge.” (E01)

Three people from the executives' group (E02, E03, and E07) highlighted that some essential BD benefits recognise high-value and most lucrative clients:

Participant E03 echoed that:

“The awareness of these customers encourages the bank to offer superior service, i.e. to provide more affordable products and services,

to provide better pricing or to gain insight into how they work, how best they can be treated and what motivates them to buy more.” (E03)

While participant E07 highlighted:

“Enhancing the loyalty of current consumers by personalised next-best-deals, rewards schemes, e.g. focused on card use patterns and collaborations with merchants to deliver discount deals to cardholders using their card outside retail stores.” (E07)

Enhanced customer retention management was also remarked as BD benefits by interviewee E06, director, wealth Management: Adaptive channel interactions based on present and previous consumer activity results:

“Potential consumer actions can be estimated, and when their next most likely step will be taken. The bank uses this information to display dynamic buttons/menu elements (i.e. dynamic screen adaptation) that forward these next actions.” (E06)

When prompted to clarify the previous quotations, increased customer engagement is one of BD's essential potential. E04 claimed that:

“It becomes easier to build stronger, longer-lasting customer relationships with in-depth customer data at the fingertips, fuelling customer engagement.” (E04)

Accordingly, participant E07 asserted that:

“Often, the bank loses out on consumers because they have no personal relation to them. To identify better customer investing preferences, financial and personal backgrounds, and investment motivations, sales agents and relationship managers should use BD analytics to offer personalised investment plans, including deposits, premiums, and loans. Essentially, to ensure that customers trust the bank with their finances, full structural investment strategies.” (E07)

In further elaboration about personalisation services and tailored products, E01 indicated that customer personalisation of service and customer experience tailoring for each user reflects the willingness to understand each prospective customer by designing services and products and other strategies customised to their particular needs based on their current customer information.

Similarly, interviewee E09, customer service manager, commented:

“For all the talk of relationship banking, the banking industry in Egypt is not generally renowned for its high degree of customised assistance. A perspective-driven shift in banking technology and a customised experience are absolute necessities for those banks and credit unions who expect not only to survive but also to grow.” (E09)

Some interviewees (E01, I03) expressed their belief in relying on 360-Degree customer experience: the bank has access to a complete customer profile for each client.

Participant E01 restated:

“The history of sales, the amount of debt, buying patterns, all tell a tale that can help the bank distinguish clients, recognise preferences that reduce the level of churn. It is the foundation of personalisation that drives loyalty.” (E01)

Another interviewee, I03, alluded to the notion of creating a complete customer profile:

“To save any promotional cash, create probabilistic models of interest in a given product based on the lifestyle of the consumer (traveller, parent, and student). It is hard for clients to decide which bank is the best to partner with. In this case, user engagement is now a decisive factor. BD technology offers a personalised report for each customer when optimising their services and offerings.” (I03)

The discussion above by participants E01 and I03 expressed that banks can go beyond only adding a name to a greeting and using recommendation engines to deliver only the most appropriate information to the client.

Similarly, participant I07, project manager, commented on the previous extracts:

“These profiles would account for multiple factors, including demographic buyer, how many accounts they have, which products customers already purchase, which offers have refused in the past, which things they are likely to purchase in the future, major life events, their engagement with their bank's approach to other clients and the industry of financial services as a whole.” (I07)

The responses were varied when asking about the most critical opportunity to use BD in the bank: The previous quotation implied that customer profile has become commonplace in the banking industry. It helps financial institutions to classes their customers into smaller population categories. Conversely, these businesses need to leverage BD in banking to push clustering to the next level by creating comprehensive consumer segmentation.

In the interviews, the data reveal that BD is used for targeted ads, engaging consumers based on their actual spending. When asked to elaborate, I08, IT manager, replied:

“The study of customer behaviour in social networks by sentiment analysis helps the bank establish a credit risk appraisal and deliver customised customer services.” (I08)

Also, E10, the internal auditor manager, recognised another BD potential to improve acquisition efficiency. Mass marketing strategies are expensive and often unsuccessful. Particularly today, when prompted to clarify more, E10 explained:

“Effective marketing tactics will then target the right category of customers, with the right (personalised) advertisements and via the right

platform (direct mail, telephone, online advertisement, social media, TV, radio) as consumers are saturated with marketing promotions through multiple platforms).” (E10)

The previous excerpt by E10 demonstrated that market segmentation allows the best selection of targets for advertising a potential product/service (hyper-targeted marketing) to be chosen.

In the previous quotation, a variety of participants' perspectives was expressed. For example, while participant E03 observed that:

“Evaluation of the required marketing campaign framework based on the insights gained from the selected target sample.” (E03)

Also, participant E10 alleged that:

“In my view, it is important to analyse what customers think about through social media and other intelligence sources, such as call centre records, to have direct feedback on marketing tactics, to adjust existing strategies for future campaigns, and to plan and improve products. Distinguish influential clients, i.e. recognise and involve prominent buyers to enhance word-of-mouth marketing.” (E10)

The participants' discussion reflected that BD helps advertisers present customer-specific information where and when it is most successful in maximising brand recognition online and in-store and recall.

Further discussion by E05, E10, the data revealed competitive advantage theme, for example, discussing the BD benefits to the bank when asked about using BD for competitive advantage in the bank.

A standard view amongst interviewees (E03, E04, E05, and I07) was that understanding the customers' buying behaviour through analysing drives value from almost all consumer-generated data through encounters with sales staff and service agents or purchases.

In a further elaboration, participant I07 explained:

“All forms of consumer data have significant value; transaction-generated data provides banks with a consistent view of their clients’ buying preferences and broader behavioural trends over time.” (I07)

As participant E05, audit manager, commented on the previous quotation:

“This data provides a clear framework for whom the customer is as an employee, meaning that the customer is a comparatively high flexible income earner, has a high credit score, and is responsible for what the customer is.” (E05)

When asked to elaborate on the previous discussion, participant E10 said:

“BD offers a practical way to evaluate the real world and turn this pool of information into valuable insights and observations that facilitate enhanced decision-making, and in the case of businesses, a competitive advantage over competitors because BD strives to provide the means to make the right decision at the right time based on easier, more accurate, more efficient and more successful.” (E10)

The data presented up until this point alluded BD use cases in banking are the same as before banks learned that they could use their massive data stores to build viable insights: track fraud, rationalize and simplify transaction processing, enhance the perception of consumers, optimise the execution of business and eventually succeed on a crowded market by providing a superior experience to customers.

The executives’ group contributors (E01, E02, and E08) maintained that BD could improve decision-making.

Participant E01 demonstrated:

“The data-driven banking sector employs a wide variety of BD analysis tools to promote its activities. The financial industry has emerged as one of the major clients of BD service providers.” (E01)

Similarly, participant E02 further discussed the previous quotation:

“The bank has extensive data volume accessible from various outlets, including payment orders, advertisement reports, inventory tracking, customer expectations, and revenue and financial transactions. Also, to support the banking decision-making cycle, the insights acquired from data analytics are used.” (E02)

When asked to explain how BD is linked to an enhanced decision-making process, E08 replied:

“Such views allow banks to make strategic decisions. Better choices boost customer loyalty and create strategic insights through optimised pricing and developing new models.” (E08)

The excerpts above also illustrate that adopting BD solutions would deliver complex applications such as fraud prevention, risk control, customer competency monitoring, and comprehension. This supports banks to establish an efficient structure for decision-making to deliver high levels of productivity.

Participants positively viewed the cost reduction that can be achieved by adopting BD solutions; E07 directly highlighted cost reduction and other benefits of BD in banking:

“As in any industry, if it provides the potential to cut costs, creativity is much more intriguing. BD has been democratised, and its use has no further financial hurdles. By tracking performance, optimising discounts and pricing offers, saving customer service workers, and also closing down unproductive divisions or branches, it has now crossed the threshold of helping banks save money.” (E07)

The passage above again illustrated a wide range of advantages that could be achieved by deploying BD within the bank.

Emerging from the data, boosting overall performance referred to in the previous quotation was further explained, when asked E01 to explain how BD is changing the bank's approach to performance management, she acknowledged that:

“Build an environment in which employees look forward to working with the use of BD to track performance metrics, measure employee engagement and organisational culture, and evaluate overall employee satisfaction.” (E01)

Also, participant E05 further argued that:

“The staff's progress can be assessed by performance analysis, whether or not they have fulfilled the monthly/quarterly/year targets. BD analytics will find ways to help them increase their size, depending on the statistics generated from the actual revenues of employees. Moreover, it is possible to test banking networks as a whole and see what works and what does not.” (E05)

The preceding two quotations highlighted how BD gives the bank a more in-depth insight into the workforce's experience and recommends the best ways to boost their performance. In addition, it gives people a better sense of control of their jobs and success when they get feedback.

Another significant advantage of BD for (E06, E10) was the effective handling of risks when asked about BD's aids in increasing business value and benefitting the bank.

Participants E06 and I01 provided some examples of BD's advantages:

“Fraud prevention, organisational risk evaluation, and advanced risk management emerged. In real-time, systems that allow BD to recognise fraud signals can further analyse them, using ML to predict unauthorized users and payments accurately, thereby raising an alert flag.” (E06)

“BD helps banks dramatically enhance risk control by better and (more) real-time visibility into consumer conduct.” (I01)

Another participant (I08) recognised the relevance of BD in preventing frauds:

“Investment benefit sources may also detect any unusual activity that could be a form of wrongdoing by analysing the financial records and buying patterns of the consumer. Live actions can prevent fraud before it occurs, such as blocking fraudulent transactions.” (I08)

Interviewees I04 and I05 also talked about his view of the advantages of BD in enhancing the risk management process:

“It is of the utmost importance for financial institutions to develop a credible risk management mechanism, or they will have to rebound from major revenue losses. The bank will continue developing to stay competitive in a dynamic market and raise its profitability as much as possible. The bank will detect risks in real-time and save customers from potential fraud through BD Processing.” (I04)

“Therefore, to identify fraudulent purchases so that they can be avoided, card fraud detection investigates card payment trends (location, timing, number, type of dealer).” (I05)

When asked how BD initiatives success being measured, participant I01, information security manager, replied:

“Identification and avoidance of fraud, using data analytics to feed fraud detecting engines to constantly assess the risk of identity theft and decide if additional compliance measures (e.g. additional authentication methods or access restrictions) are required in almost real-time. Fraud detection is one of BD's most important banking technologies that can be used to separate lawful business transactions from fraudulent transactions.” (I01)

At another point in the interview, two participants (I01, E07) drew attention to credit risk management and how it focuses on customer feedback improves private and business customers' payment profiles, increasing credit ratings in further elaboration:

“I believe that data lets the bank achieve a deeper understanding of incoming and outgoing cash flow, improving the management of liquidity. This approach may be useful for both real money in branches and the bank's overall liquidity management.” (I01)

“These results can be derived from financial statements, historical documentation (e.g. company accounting reports), and these data can also be used to manage mortgage assets, thus minimizing bank default risk.” (E07)

The previous quotations imply that by tracking consumer expenditure habits and detecting suspicious behaviour, BD is used to reduce the risk of fraudulent conduct, which helps banks use comprehensive data to deter theft and make consumers more secure.

Besides BD's use in reducing the risk of fraudulent conduct, regulator participants (R02, R05) highlighted that BD technologies and strategies could help regulators manage vast volumes of data provided by financial institutions for monitoring enforcement:

“BD will also help to define reliably and react to litigation issues that involve significant quantities of data, such as collecting certain information about a legal incident, evaluating conflicts and agreeing on the possibility that the case will lead to legal proceedings, reviewing laws and avoiding fines and sentences.” (R02)

So far, the data shows that financial institutions have quite enough data to represent their working processes, becoming more effective, customer-centric, and profitable. This offers the most forward-looking financial institutions countless ways to take advantage of these data. Emerging from the data, participants are aware of the BD benefits and the roadblocks associated with the scheme. Therefore, a brief report on some of the BD challenges in banking is reported in the next section.

4.4.2 Identifying BD's Challenges in Finance

This section aimed to reflect on BD's main challenges raised by participants and addressed these challenges from a managerial perspective.

I, therefore, raised a question about BD to fit into the organisational culture. According to E01, the hierarchical structure and silos are one of the key factors behind the slower BD acceptance in the banking industry in Egypt; E01 explained her viewpoint as follows:

“Non-technical administrators and senior executives already disregard the need for BD by focusing more on human intuition than on automated targeting instruments offered by the analytics dashboard. BD is not yet seen as a strategic weapon.” (E01)

Participant E01 continued her reflection and said that:

“The consequence is either that the bank does not opt for BD or that the actionable responses from BD applications are side-lined. Culture is a much more significant obstacle to large-scale data delivery.” (E01)

Another interviewee (E05) elaborated on the previous quotations:

“Many Egyptian financial firms are hesitant to implement BD programs because they are unable to comprehend how data analytics will boost their core business.” (E05)

Participant E07 referred to the need for banks to change this attitude by encouraging cross-bank research project teams to create an analytical centre of excellence that provides operational expertise within the organisation and simultaneously raises the potential of new technologies, such as artificial learning cognitive computing:

“Solution providers must explore and incorporate multinational corporate frameworks for the constructive resolution of organisational issues.” (E07)

These previous excerpts reflected the participants' awareness that introducing BD needs a transition of culture. For example, instead of treating information as an IT asset, data control can be transferred to market customers, making it a vital decision-making asset.

When asked about what is the most unusual market challenge with the use of BD. Three IT participants (I01, I03, I08) mentioned that despite having a massive volume of data, the bank could not use it to get valuable input from its customers when asked how the team is prepared with the proper expertise perspective to get the data insights:

Participant I01 claimed that:

“The amount of information produced, stored, analysed and consumed by banks and providers of financial services will increase exponentially year on year.” (I01)

While participant I03 suggested that:

“It needs a large amount of accessible data, automation and scalability processes. To increase precision and efficiency, language identification methods need to be improved.” (I03)

Also, participant I08 emphasised the data quality as a top priority:

“There is no feasible way for the new traditional approach to collect, streamline and produce traceability and linkages. Data quality management must be a top priority, and the more timely, accurate and sufficient the data quality (along with rigorous analysis), the better the estimation of the current financial situation, the better structures are required to identify and maintain data sources of interest, verify, clean, transform, integrate and deduplicate data.” (I08)

When asked to elaborate on the above quotations, participant I06 explained:

“The findings can be distorted by dirty data, data that is faulty, defective, outdated, irrelevant, or obsolete. The majority of the data is manually

inserted, thus increasing the probability of human error. Before introducing new software, the bank must closely review and update its existing data to find and delete instances of dirty data and, in the future, to authenticate input data sources to prevent new instances of dirty data.” (I06)

Similarly, interviewee I05 said:

“Frameworks depend on massive quantities of heterogeneous historical knowledge and live sources of unstructured, semi-ordered and organised data to be obtained and exposed.” (I05)

The previous excerpts reflected the continuing difficulty of converting data into actionable decisions, with a vast volume of data originating from current organised data. The inclination towards unstructured outside data is also on the rise.

When asked about the availability of data itself and the required skills to process it effectively, and what resources are limiting factors, a participant (I08) replied integrating numerous sources of data in software, technology and semantics, by providing interoperability-enabled access devices:

“Usually, data is transmitted through numerous heterogeneous networks with various logical representations (different meanings and semantics of data) but is encapsulated for the end-user into a single, homogeneous database. Integration impulses can be based on political or corporate requirements.” (I08)

Another participant, I02, senior software engineer, recognised the following:

“Data integration is typically not a one-off transition, but a continuing task, so there is an implicit constraint that the chosen solution must be versatile in terms of adaptability, extensibility and scalability.” (I02)

In addition to the previous challenges, I07 highlighted the BD skills shortage:

“The bank has created a shortage of experienced management and talent program to recruit the talent needed due to increased demand for broad data experts in finance.” (I07)

When asked to elaborate on what it means by a shortage of expertise, participant I03 explained that:

“The bank has established the information presented by the evidence; however, there is a shortage of human capital with the proper level of expertise to fill the void between data and prospects. The skills lacking is those of a computer scientist.” (I03)

Interviewee E01 further clarified that the data provided up to this stage related to technological expertise and skills relating to BD:

“The stakeholder participation policy aims to empower people into training and benefit by using BD through.” (E01)

When asked to elaborate, I06 explained, given that BD includes an excessive quantity of information, it does not mean that it is a representative population survey; I06 admitted that:

“There is a possibility of misinterpretation of the generated material, and if this information is used, accountability may occur.” (I06)

The quote above by I06 also enlightened by participant I07:

“Data actionability, or to make high technology workable, is the next substantial obstacle. BD research and statistical tools enable financial services companies to gain more in-depth insight into customer preferences and patterns, but the difficulty remains for firms to take proactive steps based on those data.” (I07)

The previous discussion implied that while the proportion of potentially valuable data is rising, too much useless data is already possible to figure out. The data suggests that banks need to educate themselves to reinforce their strategies

for analysing more data and, if possible, identify the best expertise and new data technologies that have been deemed obsolete. However, financial services providers are still aspiring to provide a single universe of results. More commonly, data in several siloed systems reside because data within these silos is not substantially associated.

When asked customers about providing the necessary information to improve service quality, five customer participants (C01, C03, C04, C05, and C06) have raised data retention and security concerns.

Participant C01 acknowledged that:

“I do not trust any company in Egypt with my data sharing, they will certainly share it with the government and other businesses, and that is happening all the time. There is no regard for our secrecy.” (C01)

Similarly, participant C03 indicated that:

“I know many people who have experienced reputational damage because their information was misused. For this, I prefer the safe option and protect my important data or give old info.” (C03)

On the contrary, participant C05 said:

“Since the gathered data is susceptible, if the bank desires, my activity will be tracked. Perhaps it helps detect illegal activity. Overall, I trust the bank, and I am happy to provide any required data.” (C05)

The previous quotes suggested that some clients do not trust the sharing of their data. This posed a concern about the bank's procedures to allow clients to be aware of the data gathered about them.

According to R03, a legal counsel has already addressed some issues on the enforcement of the use of BD:

“There are many data security and privacy concerns, especially in Egypt, need to be addressed when performing comprehensive data analytics. Regulatory guidelines stipulate that personal data must be processed for

specified and legitimate purposes and that the processing must be appropriate, essential, and not excessive. The influence of these requirements on banks is crucial, with individuals being able to enable banks to remove or refrain from processing their data under these conditions.” (R03)

The above quote illustrates how user data is a recurrent issue. Unfortunately, the new data privacy legislation remains primarily unknown, as the possession and use of user data are inappropriately permissible and unsuitable for swift and rigorous enforcement. Different groups of participants were asked about grappling with privacy and whether their company is pursuing a disclosure policy to educate consumers about the information gathered about them.

Three interviewees from the regulators' group (R01, R03, R05) considered continuous regulatory enforcement with the Egyptian government and risk reduction is the main issue for today's banking sector.

Participant R01 demonstrated that:

“The bank is responsible for dealing with all standards of data security and is responsible for showing compliance as well. The GDPR offers a range of tools for the bank to explain better transparency, some of which must be mandated.” (R01)

While participant R03 suggested that:

“The financial sector needs to ensure that corporate and personal records, particularly online banking and electronic correspondence with personal information and documentation, are accessed, distributed and used for business processes.” (R03)

Moreover, participant R05 argued that:

“The incredibly global complexity and high industry interconnectivity make it important that international data security and privacy rules, from the front to the back, and throughout the whole supply chain, including third parties, be completely complied with.” (R05)

On the other hand, participant I01 stated:

“Information mostly shared with third parties is not necessarily held in-house. The usage of private cloud providers as data storage facilities poses potential privacy and security challenges, as the terms of service for such services are frequently misunderstood.” (I01)

Participant R01 also suggested that sensitive information is likely to be any data belonging to a third party undertaking comprehensive data processing with confidentiality and compliance requirements. Banks have to ensure that they perform their duty and violate their security or regulatory obligations by using such details:

“The flexible requirement structures of banks have timely access to details and adhere to rigorous protection and security requirements. Customer privacy issues, however, are the single most important obstacle to performance for BD.” (R01)

The customers' group views surfaced mainly in what respects privacy, as it has become vital for financial institutions to gain and retain their customers' interest. However, financial companies are not paying attention to customer and government privacy warning signals by updating their practices and adopting a value-based approach to consumer data use.

When asked about how information inside the bank is absorbed, processed, organised, incorporated and consumed, I07 specifically stated that:

“Traditional methods are based on a relational data model where interactions are generated and then evaluated within the structure. For BD, though, it is difficult to establish formal relationships with the range of unstructured data that comes in.” (I07)

Interviewees from the IT group (I03, I05) view that most typical data processing systems view data statically and historically. However, the high price network development holds up BD ventures, allowing the acquisition of potentially tens of millions of data points per day.

“There is an absence of a business disagreement, and the need to merge data sources both preclude BD from being implemented in the bank.” (I03)

Similarly, participant I05 elaborated:

“Although most IT programs have two facets of stability and size control, BD requires exploration, capacity to leverage existing and new data, and agility. Consequently, the bank is reducing the valuation of BD by adopting a conventional IT-based strategy.” (I05)

These earlier extracts represented legacy systems, cultural heritage, and technology that preserve BD plans; many banks still rely on old static IT networks, databases, and many old systems. BD is just an add-on rather than a brand-new stand-alone programme. BD calls for new tools and methods for massively ordered and unstructured data volumes to be stored, handled, and extracted. The criteria for BD are not fulfilled by traditional data processing approaches adopted by banks.

4.5 Investment in BD: Lessons Learnt

4.5.1 Experience of BD within the XYZ Bank

Lessons learnt are lessons from prior experiences and attitudes to be deliberately considered in future decisions and behaviours. In essence, I have tried to define factors related to developments in the banking field, such as regulatory impact, changing business dynamics, related cultural and technical heritage constraints, data privacy and security issues.

When asked about the lessons learned in the financial services sector from engaging in BD, Participants E01 and E09 reflected that BD has now become a core factor in the sustainability and success of this vibrant business environment:

“Following the consolidation of the banking industry and the merger of individual banks in the country, Egypt is seen to be increasingly

implementing these developments into its institutions, including access to modern banking regulations.” (E01)

Similarly, participant E09 highlighted that:

“A change in the maturity of banking services has been seen. With the growth of universal knowledge, in many ways. The organisational framework of the Egyptian banks is centralised, and the initiative has long been authorised.” (E09)

Interviewee R04 had a negative view of applying large-scale data policies and applications for this purpose; banks have changed their work techniques. They continue to deal with this experience in greater detail:

“Banks are under pressure to remain compliant with several laws and regulatory bodies on data.” (R04)

Participants E01, I08 recognised that executives at the bank are competent in gathering, processing, and benchmarking data to deliver new and vital services better, making massive data more accessible and abridging knowledge into actionable market insights:

“By consolidating data traditionally managed in departmental silos with a view to more systemic risk control assessment, compliance with regulatory standards and enterprise-level analysis, the bank investigates some fresh and strategic directions.” (E01)

“The bank claims that the banking industry is wary of transformation, and its careful adoption of BD innovations such as cloud services and Hadoop using the open-source distribution model will be disruptive in many key ways.” (I08)

Emerging from the data presented above, banks that regularly and effectively use market analytics can succeed in today's dynamic and fluctuating markets relative to those unlikely to be pioneers. In terms of advanced analytics, modern computer technologies, such as relational database management systems, find it challenging to process growing data volumes and make them accessible and

responsive to flexible evolving requirements. By preserving a network of storage data, BD technologies that satisfy evolving consumer and regulatory demands may become indispensable in their potential to be used for diverse purposes and respond to any emerging issue.

I then asked participants about corporate performance management programs' business intelligence technology and how they see BD as adding structures to optimise market results. Participants (I01, I02, I04) replied:

Participant I01 pointed out:

“To extract useful information from data, data science goes beyond traditional analytics. It collects not only the kind of information that can be contained in a spreadsheet, but everything from emails, phone calls, text, photographs, video, posting of social media data, internet searches, GPS coordinates, and system logs. Which is not yet seen to be employed in the bank.” (I01)

Furthermore, participant I02 claimed that:

“BD has experienced a decade of success in Egypt's banking industry. As the bank started to digitise its operating procedures, it was important to include multiple ways that could be used to evaluate technology for their business revenues.” (I02)

However, participant I04 argued that:

“Thanks to an increasing proliferation of transactions across various channels, the bank has a wide spectrum of customer data, but still uses a comparatively small proportion to produce information and optimise market service.” (I04)

The data presented in this section shows that the competitive business advantages are possibly accomplished with the existing data outcome, which abridged the considerable assessment of customer data, including personal and security information. The bank's overall operation level has also increased with confidence in technology to increase customer data and other transactions.

The banking sector has improved business productivity and efficacy by accessing and manipulating an extensive array of data.

The data also indicated that banks in Egypt are committed to enhanced quality by better knowing their clients' desires and conduct; the data is growing. When asked Participants (I03, I06, I07) about how the bank meet the customer's needs and provide a data-driven digital banking experience:

According to participant I07:

“Financial data covers operating data such as cashpoints, smartphone and web-based software, call centres, branches, loans, credit cards, and financial market predictions such as regulatory data, trade data, sector data, and reporting, social media.” (I07)

Consequently, interviewee E06 went on to explain:

“Through accessing new business zones and sectors, the bank aims to find new revenue sources. Data collection plays an important role in ensuring that techniques such as development in innovative wealth management, distinguished markets and up-selling and cross-selling ingenuity are effectively implemented.” (E06)

Similarly, participant I03 shared his experience:

“Analysing this massive amount of data generated by different sources required BD solutions to support decision making and support the banking industry achieve their strategies. Nevertheless, they are not good at using these rich data sets because of their silo, product-oriented organisations. Therefore, the bank has been engaging in data technology for over a decade, such as cloud storage, blockchain, AI, ML, API economy, collection, analysis, and banking.” (I03)

Data derived from prior quotes entails giving a complete perspective of customers and the environment in which they utilise resources, effectively interacting with clients about products and services, and delivering a more enhanced consumer experience through data import.

When asked to elaborate on the previous statement, Participants (I07, E08) replied:

“The bank is no longer doubting the BD's potentials, but some voices are standing back as well. Also, the bank is considered an innovator in data analytics to address numerous business challenges such as risk management, fraud detection, and market exploration. At present, though, the volume of data is much bigger and more complicated than ever before.” (I07)

“When the bank initiated the digital transformation processes, it also wanted to have the means for comprehensive technological research. Currently, traditional banking methods are at risk of being obsolete, with customers increasingly gravitating towards electronic banking modes.” (E08)

The participants concluded that the bank has collected vast volumes of data from the previous passages but has not effectively access practical knowledge, keeping it from anticipating and responding to evolving customer preferences and contributing to a loss of opportunities. The banks now claim that BD analytics has a notable competitive edge, and very few Egyptian banks have any fundamental understanding of any live BD structure or method of compliance even then.

4.5.2 Preference for Mode of Data & Information Handling

The findings from the previous discussion indicate that the bank has access to large amounts of customer data and, owing to numerous limitations in the interpretation of the BD, the data has not yet been fully converted into real insights. Therefore, I have addressed how BD's approach to the successful improvement of the bank affects the members.

Indirectly, participant E09 discussed one of the essential advantages of conventional banks: a large amount of financial knowledge they offer to their millions of clients.

Participant E09, customer service manager, explained:

“In the past three years, major growth in the size of our data holdings has occurred. Consumers are more seriously exploring digital platforms, and banks are obtaining more information about how consumers communicate with them as banks seek to engage with customers and help them realise what is going on and acquire insights to operate a successful company and generate some awesome customer experiences.” (E09)

The previous excerpt is indicating that data potentials are being realised across the financial sector. E02, who is a personal financial adviser for seven years, went on to state that:

“Data and analytics applications in banking are boundless. The bank uses data for better-personalised offerings to offer products and services customised in real-time to individual customers.” (E02)

The previous quote is also an example of how the data mining spectrum is used as a surrogate in the financial sector. E03 explained how data had been viewed positively inside the bank:

“We use data to provide real-time services tailored to individual consumers. For starters, the bank offers discount insurance policies to cover certain products while purchasing an international flight or a car. These developments will be extended further in the future.” (E03)

Therefore, I asked participants how the bank gets the most from the data to hold the rivalry up.

Interviewee E08 reiterated:

“The use of comprehensive data has both benefits and drawbacks. While targeted marketing using BD technology makes it easier for the bank to make important business decisions through customer segmentation and profiling, there is concern about privacy and security issues.” (E08)

In a further elaboration, participants E08 stated:

“The bank has to pursue a data-driven approach if it wants to remain competitive to accelerate competition in the financial services industry. Since the prospects of these results for current banks are almost limitless, BD will make a significant difference in the future viability of financial institutions.” (E08)

While participant E02 suggested that:

“Improved measurement of marketing results across all channels simplified customised customer engagement (relevant content per path, dynamic pricing, next-offer) faster sensitivity (seconds rather than hours) to consumer-related purchasing challenges detailed and forward-looking customer support (predictive analysis) Improved customer loyalty (better service).” (E02)

I further asked participant E01 to comment on how the bank has incorporated data-driven strategies but need crucial measures to make them valid and efficient:

“Customer-Centric is one of the bank's main concepts for providing more excellent banking service to customers. To make market segmentation management and product development decisions more efficient and quicker, the bank also recognises accurate and user-friendly BD techniques.” (E01)

Similarly, participant I07 mentioned that decision-makers are expected to obtain proper understanding from such varied and continually evolving information that has already been stated in the previous discussion:

“By extracting insights from the immense amount of data assets accumulated in bank systems, technology has made the bank invest in systems to leverage the data for intelligent decisions.” (I07)

For additional information on identifying the barriers that prevent banks from growing BD, I inquired about any additional restrictions that participants could face.

Participant I08 continued his reflection:

“In my opinion, the use of BD in Egypt's banking industry occurs when the bank is successful in introducing it. Customer data in Egyptian banks was a moderately low priority sector. Most also based their resources on risk control, not using BD to maximize the experience of consumers.”
(I08)

The current situation was summarised by participant E05, who said:

“In my opinion, the bank is failing to take advantage of ever-increasing data volumes, as banks only use a limited percentage of this knowledge to produce insights that maximise the consumer experience. Banks that have action plans, well-defined mission and metrics, would have a favourable condition of exploiting BD.” (E05)

There are many reasons for that, as discussed further by participant I08:

“Owing to the complexity of its processes, redundant structures and data silo is a much more critical challenge than most sectors, and this has proven to be a laborious process. The bank faces major hurdles in recruiting the best-qualified applicants.” (I08)

While interviewee I02 shared his view of the future banking:

“Training ML algorithms that will automate much of their processes is essential for banks to leverage their future data. AI instruments can improve how the bank deals with problems with regulatory compliance. None of this is to say that with the introduction of BD in banking, it has been straightforward, as banks in Egypt are behind the curve.” (I02)

These previous excerpts reflected the participants' awareness of how financial institutions use large-scale data technology; banks are beginning to view large-

scale data as an investment rather than a technical expenditure. BD would allow them to develop and expand their business in the banking sector. The starting of the digital disruption wave will test banks at their very foundation, so it is necessary to harness the total value of BD in banking.

Figure 4-2 demonstrates the model that signifies the substantive theory Harnessing BD in Banking Industry. The one dominant category shapes the model, named the substantive theory, and involves five conditions (Customer Concerns about Privacy, Legacy Infrastructure, Legal and Regulatory, Organisational Mindset Turning Data into Actionable Insights). Three actions (Communication; Stakeholders' involvement (Social, Economic, and Environmental factors) and Results Control), and eight consequences (Better Decision-Making, Boosting Overall Performance, Competitive Advantage, Cost Reduction, Easier Filing of Regulatory Compliance, Efficient Risk Management, Improved Customer Services and Personalised Marketing)

Figure 4-2 Demonstrates the Harnessing BD in Egyptian Banking theory

Source: Researcher

4.6 Summary

The views of stakeholder groups of BD's potentials were presented in this chapter of the underlying results. Banks now have an enormous volume of data and activity history for consumers. Overall, these results indicate that accelerated economic digitisation introduces numerous external data outlets that banks can use, such as telecom carriers, geospatial data, credit bureaus, social networks, and online behaviour.

These results suggest that financial firms can use digital technologies to use data efficiently to turn it into information, make the right business choices, and remain competitive and productive. However, the banking sector faces ever-growing competition from non-traditional companies pursuing successful business growth and cost control tools.

Hence, some banks exploit such data to the best potential, arising from the results, whereas others are still designing the right data strategies. The idea of harnessing BD emerged as the primary concern in the data as it explained why participants performed acts that culminated in harnessing BD being a dominant group in the financial services market.

These results provide important insights into the BD definition developed in Egypt by stakeholders in the banking sector. Simultaneously, the terminology was borrowed to express the substantive theory, the chapter of results rooted the theory in proof through constructivist-based analytical approaches.

Consequently, this chapter presented the core aspects of harnessing BD in the banking industry in Egypt. Having identified the main opportunities and challenges and the participants' roles in deciding to adopt BD in banking, qualitative data analysis allowed the researcher to assess the current situation, define the extent to which stakeholders are concerned with engaging with each other and examine their effect on the use of BD in banks.

The next chapter will record the compilation and interpretation of evidence produced by stakeholder interviews relating to BD's use in various financial activities and synthesize this explanation's results into a new empirical theory.

5 Chapter Five: Analysis and Discussion

5.1 Introduction

This chapter consolidates BD's research findings in the financial services industry and its relevance to Egypt's banking sector. Excerpts from interview transcripts explain and base the concrete underlying theory that resulted from the findings. Therefore, quotes were selected based on relevance, frequency, and idiosyncrasy to show meaning and data variability. Word for word text is the participants' vocabulary subject to minor editing to prevent misunderstanding or duplication.

The study aims to develop insights into the importance of BD in Egypt's banking industry. For that purpose, Constructivist Grounded Theory (CGT) was adopted for this study as the methodology approach. According to Nanda *et al.* (2000), qualitative inquiry aims to define particular concerns, understandable subjects, expressive categories, and new notions of study that facilitate the comprehension of a mechanism or phenomena. Therefore, this chapter's primary purpose is to demonstrate the essence of the qualitative data collection process and the analytical method developed in intensive, semi-structured interviews to enhance the transparency of the data analytics process and the reliability of outcomes.

This chapter reveals that the CGT approach is consistent with the analysis methods by describing the study conduct. The first part details the technique for data processing, and then the second part provides a further exploration of the method of data analysis. Finally, in light of the analytical data gathered from the interviews, the last section provides a thorough discussion.

5.2 Interviews Data Analysis

The recruitment and interviewing of participants are discussed in this section. The theoretical approach informs the CGT data collection of sampling to decide what data to extract from the emerged theory (Charmaz, 2006). In the ethnographic process, the data collection phase was expressed: through going to the field, actively search for rich data, observe participants without

interruption, actively communicate with participants, and gain trust by spending time with participants (Wertz *et al.*, 2011).

Participants' Characteristics: After obtaining the approval of the research ethics committee, the researcher identified the relevant participants for this research. Accordingly, permission was secured to gather the empirical evidence, mainly due to the Quality Manager (E01) at XYZ Bank.

Therefore, the first attempt was to design the questions for each group of stakeholders, receive the permission of the lead supervisor of this study first, send them by email, then make a follow-up call. The author, though, was unable to conduct a pilot study online due to the distance involved. Therefore, the researcher had to go to Egypt's fieldwork to collect the details for the first step.

In this research, inclusion and exclusion constraints were used to ensure that the selection of participants hired was sufficient as a GT study that allows versatility, as well as welcoming various types of participants as the research progressed, in addition to using theoretical sensitivity to guide the sampling process (Wertz *et al.*, 2011). Purposely, the inclusion requirements for participants in the study is extensive, including anyone who works in the banking industry in Egypt or is associated with BD practice in any way. In contrast, the exclusion criteria for participants excluded the other bank employees who are not affected by BD solutions.

The first phase for the data collection was undertaken to collect and analyse the data, following the ongoing theoretical sampling. In this stage, the contact of each participant was collected as a preparation for the second phase. A call for participating was submitted via email, and fortunately, some interviewees came forward to assist. The second phase was to ask more questions that emerged from the analysis and clarify the concepts, categories, and dominant themes. Moreover, this phase was completed using phone calls and online applications.

Participant recruitment started with a random purposive sample. Accordingly, participants in different bank roles were approached, such as Accountant, Database Administrator, Architect, Lawyer, Financial Manager, Quality Control

Manager, Internal Auditor and Branch Manager. Theoretical sampling has continued to establish the evolving theory by adopting questions that concentrate on emerging issues and participants' options that have been placed to provide input on emerging concerns.

Interviews: In this section, the participants' data are relevant to the study's purpose, e.g., investigating BD's emerging role and impact on Egypt's banking sector. Primary data was gathered from 33 respondents from different banking stakeholders. In particular, a detailed analysis, including the demographic profile and the general background of the respondents, was carried out. Subsequently, methodological research was conducted using the CGT methodology. Therefore, to clarify the respondents' demographic specifics, the categorical variables were exposed to descriptive analysis and plotted in a bar map to help visualize the analysis.

Figure 5-1 Summary of the participants' demographic profile

Source: Researcher

The previous graph provides a descriptive study of the demographic characteristics of the respondents. The graph indicates that the per cent of the people were male, i.e. more than 76% of the respondents. Furthermore, 88% of participants are from 30-45 years, and 12% were from the age category of fewer than 30 years.

Concerning experience in the financial services industries, more than 64% of participants had more than five years of continued bank professional experience, of which 36% had fewer than five years of total bank work experience. In particular, respondents work through professions, with the plurality employed in the finance and IT departments, which seem to be the primary roles of financial institutions. A total of 39% worked in the finance department. In comparison, 27% of respondents work in the logistics branch.

Therefore, this study employed 33 participants in the final questionnaire, with a participant number assigned to each name, to hide each participant's identity, as stated in the methodology chapter. All participants came from a range of different identified stakeholders' groups (Customers (C), Executives (E), IT Facilitators (I), and Regulators (R)) who worked on or dealt with the banking industry in Egypt. Of these, ten were bank executives, eight IT facilitators, five regulators and ten customers. The interviews were placed in Cairo, Egypt, face-to-face, semi-structured and open-ended stakeholder interviews were conducted.

The interviews lasted about 45 minutes and concentrated on the participants' perspectives working or interacting with the bank, particularly BD's notion (challenges and opportunities) and its effect on each stakeholder. Although legal questions were included in the interviews, they were dialogue-driven, and the interviewer was personally engaged in the discussion. As the content was processed and new concepts and categories arose, the following interview questions were updated to focus on the emerging code to obtain further insights (Charmaz, 2006).

This subsection seeks to improve data analysis and the results' integrity by presenting the data analysis process's nature. The data interpretation method

explores the data's underlying meanings, reducing information to abstract terms and summarising information. Three primary steps comprise the method of data processing. Step 01, initial coding, put on labels to a large portion of the data. Step 02, Focused coding, choose dominant codes and establish their relation to other codes—step 03, Theoretical Encoding, the generation of relations between categories relating to records.

At the same time, the researcher analysed the collected data during the data collection process. Iterative data collection and interpretation processes optimised new theoretical concepts, which then drive more theoretical sampling. Data processing during the interviews involved the adaptation of questions about the conversation of the participant. The constant comparison also defined progressively abstract ideas by comparing data across consecutively increasing abstraction levels (Strauss and Corbin, 1994).

The continuous comparing approach contrasts new data with emerging data, codes, categories, categories, definitions and concepts, and existing literature theories—the research context and the circumstances. The data implications were analysed in a constructivist manner by establishing a relationship with applicants that enabled the joint development of the material during interviews (Robbins, 2016).

Characteristics of a CGT Approach: The grounded theorist should have no preconceived ideas; in other words, the researcher should bracket any background or prior knowledge (Glaser and Strauss, 1967). For this reason, the study used a data-driven approach and was carried out by performing the theoretical sampling.

Therefore, the researcher used constant comparison, as mentioned before in the methodology chapter. It was essential to writing memos at the research stage in the analysis process, including describing the codes and categories and the principle being created. Data collection was stopped as saturation was reached, achieving a point where new data did not modify the categories.

Memos: Through using memos when evaluating the results, a record of the logical processes was given. The memos provide how data has been coded, classified and how the substantive theory has been established. Therefore, to rationalise the central organising phenomenon and the selected principles, the analysis used analytical memos. Analytical memos were used to explain participants' recruitment (Bryant *et al.*, 2012).

Name	Codes	References
1-3-2020 I organised my research questions and created an anchor code	0	0
15-3-2020 Generate themes to address the research questions.	0	0
17-3-2020 Reading the Literature	0	0
2-3-2020 Conduct data cleaning	0	0
2-3-2020 Upload the data into NVivo	0	0
25-3-2020 Final Step, Reporting	0	0
3-3-2020 Reorganise the data	0	0
4-3-2020 today, I have to decide on what kind of code	0	0
4-3-2020 Conduct data exploration	0	0
5-3-2020 Start coding relevant information in the data (Manually)	0	0

1-3-2020 I organised my resear

1/3/2020: Today, I organised my research questions and created an anchor code for each research question. Those 4 anchor codes are the main themes for my research. This step is a preparation step for tomorrow coding work.

Figure 5-2 The theoretical memos for this study

Source: Researcher

Data Preparation: After the data was collected, a four-step process was conducted to prepare the analysis stage data. Step 01: Conduct data cleaning as data was entered into Microsoft Excel Worksheet (.xlsx) for each stakeholder group. Then step 02: Import the data into the NVivo programme. Step 3: Reorganise data (open-ended responses) into nodes, each participant's information into the case, case classification for (demographic information) and four central nodes (Anchor codes) were created to represent each research question. Step 04: Conduct data exploration to get familiar with the data. Step 05: Code relevant information in the data. Step 06: Generate themes to address the research questions.

Phase 01: Initial Coding: Coding is how marks are applied to the essential portions of the data produced. The method of data processing was driven by CGT coding. According to Charmaz (2006), Coding that identifies, explains and derives meaning from the subject's experiences motivates the investigator to test hidden assumptions.

Name	Files	References
1.The challenges and opportunities of Big Data(RQ 1 Anchor Code)	4	546
2.The impact of using Big Data in an organisation (RQ 2 Anchor Code)	4	233
3.The relevance of Big Data use to organisational performance (RQ 3 Anchor Code)	4	63
4. lessons learned from the past decade of investment in Big Data (RQ 4 Anchor Code)	3	22

Figure 5-3 The references for the coding process

Source: Researcher

The researcher also closely engaged with the evidence by searching for tacit and explicit context and conclusions behind the participants' comments. By carefully arranging the interview data, codes were then used to reflect an abstract interpretation of the data. Hence, the researcher remained open-minded in the coding process about any ideas originating from the results to avoid preconceptions' bias.

Nevertheless, the investigator was potentially receptive to certain principles relevant to BD implementations in the banking industry, as the study suggests. However, the detective used self-awareness and memos to handle pre-existing interpretations.

During the early stages of the data analysis, each line of the interview transcript was marked line-by-line. The line-by-line coding made it easier for the investigator to find minor nuances and effectively communicate with the material. Although codes were in-vivo that retained the original meanings and purposes of the participant's point of view using the participants' language (Wertz *et al.*, 2011), gerunds' use to stress behaviour within social processes was used to communicate specific codes.

The initial coding identified another initial coding technique suggested by Bryant *et al.* (2012); numerous codes were compared to each other and by other

interviews. The goal was to see common notions repeated, identify differences, and categorize which codes are the most critical expression of the participants' interests.

Figure 5-4 The line-by-line coding process

Source: Researcher

As the details began to be scrutinised using the constant comparative process, arranged and progressed by coding each line of the text, identical codes were formed into categories. Then, the principal codes and groups became recognised on the way to the end of the actual coding process. It became clear at this stage that participants developed BD as an asset that can be used to deliver benefits to and stakeholders, but with several obstacles and concerns.

Phase 02: Focused Coding: At this point, the researcher correlated data with data to identify correlations and variances, such as comparing the statements and incidents of interviews within the same interview and comparing statements and incidents from different interviews.

Sequential comparisons often allow the researcher to compare data for the same person in previous and later interviews and then analyse the initial codes created to dominant preference codes and identify their relation with other

codes (Charmaz, 2006). In addition, the investigator was probing for the codes' mathematical properties and the codes-related conclusions. Finally, the codes' sortation was carried out by choosing the dominant codes, creating groups and grouping the remaining codes around the dominant codes.

Therefore, more data generation has been embellished to locate similarities and fill in the gaps in the essential categories. In addition, methodical literature was reviewed for the investigator, not shown previously during the first coding procedure, to become more scientifically adaptable to BD features.

The journal used as logical controls was used in the data only for concepts. Therefore, the nature of the research method was validated by literature, providing that terminology did not force the knowledge to characterise evolving processes. To that stage in the analysis, original coding and memos helped with the abstraction of concepts.

Consequently, using theoretical sampling of the literature focused on the growth of theoretical sensitivity, iterative data generation and analysis processes began. As a result, the coding produced was increasingly concentrated. In comparison, the literature used a sophisticated degree of abstraction to re-examine sets of identical codes. Categories that emerged as the most important in explaining BD in Egypt's banking industry included: corporate mentality, better customer services, translating knowledge into actionable lessons, privacy issues for consumers. The table below shows the increase from the original and cantered coding of new categories.

Table 5-1 Steps to establish emerging categories

Initial Codes	Focused Codes	Category
<p><i>“New strategies may overcome these difficulties.”</i></p> <p><i>“The bank is trying to adopt the development policy.”</i></p> <p><i>“There is not enough confidence in the data.”</i></p> <p><i>“We are adopting new technology.”</i></p> <p><i>“By changing the organisational culture towards using data.”</i></p> <p><i>“The bank does not use BD.”</i></p> <p><i>“The capabilities of BD are not fully understood.”</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • BD is not viewed as a strategic asset. • Dedicating Resources for BD. • Understanding BD capabilities. 	<p><i>Organisational Mindset</i></p> <p>Properties: Most banks are still guided primarily by previous experience, instincts, understanding of SMEs and consumer experience. They need more data excitement, data-driven thinking, and more spending in data collection, storage, and analysis.</p>
<p><i>“Offers me adequate services.”</i></p> <p><i>“Understand my needs better.”</i></p> <p><i>“Improve the services and products provided through the bank.”</i></p> <p><i>“Improve the level of service.”</i></p> <p><i>“Deeper understanding and prediction of customer behaviour.”</i></p> <p><i>“Gain customer trust.”</i></p> <p><i>“Improves the quality of the services customer satisfaction.”</i></p> <p><i>“A deeper understanding of customer problems would take appropriate arrangements to avoid and solve problems that lead to customer loss.”</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Enhancing Customer Satisfaction • Understand the customer's behaviours. • Delivering high-value services • Enhancing customer experience • Improving Customer Retention • Increasing Customer Loyalty • Providing personalised banking solutions 	<p><i>Improved Customer Services</i></p> <p>Properties: BD tends to boost the efficacy of marketing and helps to maximize the value offered to consumers. The BD received from different organised and unstructured data sources promise to improve customer service and boost customer loyalty.</p>

<p><i>"We are designing tailored banking solutions for them."</i></p>		
<p><i>"I do not provide all the data."</i></p> <p><i>"I will give only the unimportant data."</i></p> <p><i>"I will block the critical data."</i></p> <p><i>"To convert this data into something valuable."</i></p> <p><i>"All the required data on the client is collected through direct contact."</i></p> <p><i>"Verify the accuracy of these data."</i></p> <p><i>"I do not think there are the necessary skills to analyse BD."</i></p> <p><i>"Employees may not have the knowledge or capability."</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data Quality challenges • Shortage of skilled people 	<p><i>Turning data into actionable insights</i></p> <p>Properties: Turning digital analytics data into actionable insights for my business</p>
<p><i>"I protect my personal information."</i></p> <p><i>"The litigation process lengthy."</i></p> <p><i>"I do not trust the bank."</i></p> <p><i>"The collection of personal data about me."</i></p> <p><i>"I agree, but not in Egypt."</i></p> <p><i>"My data is shared every day."</i></p> <p><i>"I do not share my essential data."</i></p> <p><i>"The problem of privacy and trust."</i></p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Lack of confidence • Feeling Insecurity 	<p><i>Customer Concerns About Privacy</i></p> <p>Properties: BD provides an outstanding opportunity for banks to take crucial moves forward, but it still has a huge red flag on privacy and interference.</p>

Source: Researcher

Phase 3: Theoretical Coding: This stage integrates the focused coding categories to form an abstraction on an action or event (Abductive inference.) Then the abstract developed into a theory. The original theory is then correlated further with the current data produced by theoretical sampling, while the constant comparison is made before saturation is achieved (Charmaz and Belgrave, 2019).

The core categories retained to resonate with the data from all the participants' first interviews, oriented coding compounded into theoretical coding. When diagramming a possible descriptive, theoretical emerged, an early model of the predicted substantive theory. The substantive theory description outlined in the results chapters ultimately culminated in further amplification of this diagram.

Figure 5-5 Early schematics of the substantive theory

Source: Researcher

Through theoretically sampling literature and early diagram harnessing BD as a critical coordinating phenomenon, advanced data analysis continued. Theory integration then cumulated into the plot, which was already deliberated by the lengthy theoretical memo process. Finally, the iterative sequence of data processing and parallel interviews contributed to theoretical sufficiency, which offered the most logical reason for forming relations between groups related to the data that integrating what was observed and how it was experienced led to the nature of the experience (Creswell, 2014).

Figure 5-6 The research analysis process

Source: Charmaz (2006)

This section described the method of data collection, and interpretation is summarised in the previous diagram. As a consequence, the following section reflects the application of GT.

5.3 Reflection on the Application of CGT to Study

A strong synergy was discovered through this study between the research methodology (CGT) and the research area (BD relevance). There is much cohesion between the two, as both are incremental and iterative. BD has a set of iterations in which the data analytics process develops insignificant amounts of directing the operational data towards discovering the data insights.

Likewise, the GT involves iterative data processing and interpretation circles that bring the researcher a step closer to the study's vital concerns; both stress the individual and social dimensions of data (let the data talk); BD values the relationships between resources and processes individuals. This can also be

achieved by analysing human activity and social interactions across GT concentrations in a defined functional area. In contrast, it makes critics edgy to neglect the rigorous study of literature and confidence in the growth of critical interest, while some scholars doubt having research questions in the conducting process of the GT.

Although the researcher recognises that an interpretative constructivist method would be an appropriate alternative, the author chose the CGT partially for the sake of experimentation. GT's research experience is an example of GT implementation as a tool for understanding BD's role in banking and without initial theory training in GT. Development can occur as long as the method's basic principles are adhered to, and the investigator could use theoretical sampling to continuously relate the focus of the sample to the most relevant question.

As evident from the many issues observed and mentioned in each GT procedure, the application of GT to BD in this research was not straightforward. Nevertheless, approaches that have been found beneficial in overcoming these problems pervade other confidence for comparative research in the future use of GT again. Furthermore, other BD researchers using GT could benefit from representing problems and methods deemed valid in GT implementation.

5.4 Discussion

This study aimed to assess BD's potentials and influence in Egypt's banking business. First, construct a theory to explain the phenomenon and an abstract explanation of how ideas are connected to fill the gaps in the literature mentioned in Chapter 2. The qualitative findings and themes that arose from the analytical method are then presented in Chapter 4.

Consequently, this section deliberates this study's findings, considering the research results and their implications. Moreover, this section contrasts the existing literature with the new substantive theory to reveal its contribution to the current knowledge body.

5.4.1 Unveiling the BD Adoption in Banking

Prior studies noted BD as a common term used to define the substantial growth and distribution of data, both structured and unstructured, as described in the literature review. However, BD is a technology trend in the mid-1980s due to modern computers advancements, improved stored energy and computing capacity (Morabito *et al.*, 2016).

Furthermore, BD technologies enabled new and improved methods to scrutinise the unlimited amount of available data. The empirical evidence denotes that BD is a terminology that refers to the total volume of daily data generated at a speed that exceeds existing databases' capacity within global networks. Akter *et al.* (2019) found that the data's importance was the data analysis speed at which the data had to be interpreted or supplied, not just because of its scale but also because of the range and essence. As Bagha and Madisetti (2019) suggested that, the four Vs (i.e. volume, velocity, variety, and value also help distinct comprehensive from intelligent data, namely:

Volume: Banks generate massive data every day; the amount is the space the data would require storing. The volume of data analysed exceeds the power of modern analytical and mathematical analysis methods. Following the exploding sheer amount of stored data, IBM estimates that 35 zettabytes will be processed by 2020 (Chessell *et al.*, 2018).

Velocity: With the amount of data banks are operating on, dealing with this number of actual transactions is not theoretical. It is the level at which the data is processed. Traditional business intelligence (BI) tools use historical data dating back weeks, months, or thirds is used by traditional business intelligence (BI) tools. Pence (2014) noted that data quality relies not only on the degree of the flow of information but also on the rate at which it is stored, measured, and interpreted.

Variety: Banks have to deal with large amounts of different forms of data regularly. The bank provides a range of customer data from credit ratings to transaction information and risk appraisal records (Glass, 2018). BD explores all manner of data more than what is processed in a data warehouse (DW). It

could also adapt compressed data from external channels, as well as centralised and unstructured data streams. Daniel Puschmann (2017) claimed that the ability to apply advanced algorithms and efficient computers to massive data collections, exposing previously unavailable connections and observations by traditional data storage or BI software, makes BD distinct from merely just data.

Value: The previous 3Vs are worthless if the bank does not have the interest. Value is given to the outcomes of BD in real-time, and management decisions are made. BD flows as defined in White Paper by Douglas Laney (Karthik *et al.*, 2017) as volume, velocity and variety –. Here is how BD contributes to the banks as an asset:

As mentioned in the literature review chapter, more potential for banking emerged from the exponential growth in data volume generated from social networking and online activities. However, several studies suggest that the generated data from these activities is primarily unstructured data used as an asset within corporate banks to develop many strategies, such as cost control prioritisation, different pricing policies, and working capital management (Baabdullah *et al.*, 2019). Moreover, according to Badarau and Lapteacru (2020), financial firms could not take advantage of large amounts of data, and banks only use a limited amount of data to produce customer service information.

Nevertheless, BD offers many potentials that justify the effort. For example, Truong (2016) argues that banks concentrate on risk management instead of paying attention to customer data analytics. However, the same study reveals that banks applying consumer data analytics account for 4 per cent of the lead over banks using conventional data systems, while banks using data analytics accounted for 12 per cent of the lead over banks using traditional data systems.

Furthermore, it is believed that leveraging BD in a cumulative segment of wallet, market share growth, and customer retention could maximise the value of customer data (Tunguz and Bien, 2016; Keighley, 2017; Ghasemaghahi, 2018). Furthermore, BD allows banks to target specific customer micro-segments,

past buying behaviour, sentiment analysis, customer relationship management (CRM), and social media demographics. This advances client experience and loyalty, leading to profitability (Satish and Yusof, 2017; Baabdullah *et al.*, 2019).

In reviewing the literature, Patrizio (2018) estimated 175 zettabytes of data worldwide by 2025; digital banking enables banking to rethink how to get the most out of data to stay ahead of rivalry. Additionally, according to Siddiqui and Qureshi (2017), expenditure in BD technologies is expected to hit USD 260 billion by 2022, though banking is the leading BD investor in all industry fields. Therefore, it is essential to highlight a few of the benefits of BD in the banking industry.

Ultimately, while the primary goal of adopting BD in banking is to improve customer experience, new goals comprise the better-target market, enhance risk management and security, improved performance, making existing processes more efficient and automated (Srivastava and Gopalkrishnan, 2015).

In the context of Egypt, according to Al-Masry (2019), Egypt has over 94 million mobile phone users. By comparison, according to the Ministry of Telecom and Information Technology (2019), only 8.21 million users use landlines, and some 45.67 million users use the Internet (ADSL and mobile internet).

The current study found that even though banks in Egypt have traditionally improved, product-level data analytics, such as mortgages, credit cards, very few have looked across consumer relationships that could create market opportunities. The most exciting finding was that only a tiny percentage of Egyptian banks examine external customer data, such as social media interactions and internet activity. These data have been increased concurrently with Mobile Banking, Credit Card, Net Banking, Debit Card, and Automated Teller Machines.

The findings showed that Egyptian banks should use BD to accomplish the predetermined goals of introducing a new product or service or improving procedures by lowering the time required and reducing costs. Such factors and other variables should eventually lead to better decision making in the bank. In addition, this study shows that any of the above advantages could be reaped

by bank compensation using BD: gain competitive advantage, improved customer services, customised products and customised marketing communication, boosting overall performance, more accessible filing of regulatory compliance, and efficient risk management.

In the empirical study backed by the literature throughout the BD banking industry, the researcher defined the main BD concerns by participants' contributions. This has significant impacts on the introduction of BD in Egypt's bank industry and was addressed internally and externally by the researcher as crucial components.

Therefore, this sub-section addresses the critical aspects of these internal and external contexts critical for BD's use in the Egyptian banking industry. After evaluating significant internal or external factors and their role in their choice to follow BD, the GT data analysis enables the researchers to determine the degree to which these factors impaired one another and assess their impact on BD adoption in the banking field.

“The data usually regulates the bank's culture as an entity, but the BD is still in the area of research, and the security policy of the bank must grasp the BD and then continue to work with it.” (E06)

5.4.2 Connectivity and Access to Digital Technologies for BD

The financial services sector is rapidly transitioning from a conventional paradigm to a sophisticated digital manner of engaging with customers. As a result, a digital transition takes place between the financial service provider and the consumer. For example, the banking business has moved from a newspaper and a leader entry approach to online and offline client-driven data and analysis operations.

Furthermore, digital structural transformation is increasing the strain on traditional banks. In essence, Egyptian banks recognise the significance of digital advancements despite other societal and regulatory obstacles and are working hard on potential solutions and strategies. Many digital advancements

can be felt primarily at the client interface. Given the instability caused by digital interruption, banks need to assess dangers and possibilities and create new choices for business in the future. Our decisions, activities, and simply being in the digital world create data that give enormous possibilities to review existing company processes and techniques. As a result, new ideas that integrate BD Analytics ecosystems are critical (Pappas *et al.*, 2018).

Imminence was a classic example of how technology has improved customer service throughout this investigation in/with the banking industry. Customers may also check account statements, deposit checks, pay bills, and send cash using their cell phones.

The findings suggest that clients' lack of interaction was the fundamental reason Egypt's conventional banks cannot compete with similar global firms. Participants considered BD techniques are so crucial to the banking sector in Egypt. Banks could help understand their consumers' needs by leveraging personal and transactional user knowledge. Therefore, banks would cultivate the value of BD (Akter *et al.*, 2019). The next segment addresses BD's advantage in Egypt's banking industry to explain how banks should take advantage of BD.

The literature review further shows that interest in BD has increased along with the increasing awareness of BD benefits in the banking industry. BD allows the banking industry to please investors, control risk, detect fraud, and more (Srivastava and Gopalkrishnan, 2015; Aljandali, 2016; Glass, 2018; Wei, 2020). This sub-section offers an insight into the banking sector's BD applications.

Scholars trust that taking advantage of BD insights into finance will bring the financial industry into the 21st century because of BD technologies' growth and the large amount of data generated and analysed. However, the discussion in Chapter 3 indicates that BD's misuse in the banking sector remains a substantial concern for senior executives. Moreover, The literature confirms BD's relevance of bank policies and priorities (Amakobe, 2015; Srivastava and Gopalkrishnan, 2015; Moshirpour, Far and Alhajj, 2017).

Some researchers agree that BD is renovating the planet and, with its tremendous advantages, it has left little business unaffected (Mikalef *et al.*, 2018; Yadegaridehkordi *et al.*, 2020). Others claim that BD has been a lifeguard for the banking sector (Moshirpour *et al.*, 2017). BD allows banks in the banking industry to improve management decisions, achieve an edge, cut costs, improve customer services, provide customised marketing, increase the bank's efficiency, mitigate risk, identify fraud and file regulatory enforcement (Aljandali, 2016).

Another remarkable result was that Egypt's XYZ bank would build strategies focused on these indicators: consumer segmentation, cross-selling and up-selling based on customer segmentation, improved customer care based on customer input, the discovery of personalised offering based on spending habits, and healthier compliance with risk assessment and monitoring that helps to control fraud.

Moreover, BD's relevance in financial services has been examined broadly in the literature (Hassani *et al.*, 2018; Shirazi and Mohammadi, 2018). Nonetheless, much of the contributions to the scholarly literature on BD were visionary, while the study focusing on aspects of BD adoption in the banking sector was most frequently analytical.

Better Customer Services: Denoting to the literature (Chapter 2, Section 2.4.2), CRM is an inclusive process and strategy that makes higher value to customers and the bank by acquiring, retaining and associating with discerning customers. Banks sit at the hub of most commercial activity, which generates a complete sort of customer data.

For that, securing, maintaining, and validating data is weighty to banks (Khan *et al.*, 2012; Anshari *et al.*, 2019). BD has been used to improve consumer service. It seeks innovative solutions to generate more value, communicate in an extra-expressive manner, discover new ways of doing things, and provide constructive methods to prevent client turnover and switching.

While there is exponential growth in the sheer amount of data gathered about customers, Mirzaie *et al.* (2019) reported that four out of five customers believe

that sharing their data with their banks will speed and improve services. Accordingly, data insights about customer behaviour could help in optimising the customer experience. Such an approach has been used by American Express that relies on traditional predictive models to stop customer churn (Shirazi and Mohammadi, 2018).

Customer segmentation: Verhoef (2016) reported that banks spend 8% of the overall budget on marketing. Up to 15 to 20 per cent of the marketing budget can be saved by data-driven decisions and. In this context, authors have noted an excellent opportunity to use BD in banking by making profits through highly targeted advertising strategies, identifying difficulties, and finding an excellent way to solve them, improving understanding of client needs.

Furthermore, Patwardhan *et al.* (2018) suggest that it is remarkable for banks to derive valued knowledge from customer behaviour, build up an accurate customer database, have active personalised support, and improve customer loyalty. Verhoef (2016) stated that Barclays uses social listening strategy to collect and analyse customer actionable insights from social networks activity.

In the light of exploring new products, dropping operating costs and improving customer loyalty, the data review indicates that when banks implement BD, they have come to see it as a source of considerable benefit.

“Banks and financial services firms would develop a comprehensive understanding of markets, clients, networks, products, regulations, competitors, vendors and staff by the exploitation of BD, which will make them more competitive.” (E04)

Personalised Marketing: By engaging clients based on purchasing habits, BD is used for targeted messaging. Customer interaction monitoring on social media sites, through sentiment analysis, lets banks provide customised products and services and build credit risk evaluation (Anshari *et al.*, 2019).

“The bank pursues a market-driven BD approach: first, customer needs are identified, and existing internal capabilities and capabilities are balanced to meet business prospects while investing in data and network sources.” (101)

Personalised marketing is moving beyond segment-based marketing. For instance, one marketing campaign targets consumers with typical desires and purchasing habits instead of a generic advertisement. The qualitative interviews found that while much of the data is based on retailer reports analysis, organisations should also go ahead and take data from numerous other outlets to help identify consumer desires, including social media records.

Competitive Advantage: Another critical component of BD benefits is a competitive advantage; It has been suggested that firms emphasise BD processes and get insights about economic value and gain competitive advantage (Del Vecchio *et al.*, 2017).

Using BD to gain a competitive advantage is a common theme throughout the literature. Furthermore, by drawing on the concept of competitive advantage, Alharthi *et al.* (2017) have shown that businesses could build sustainable capabilities to add to their competitive advantage with a proper data-driven strategy.

A business can also launch a secondary source of returns by selling these capabilities to other industries. In terms of sustainable processes as drivers of BD adoption, BD is evident that using measurable statistical models reduces risks (Gandomi and Haider, 2015; Verma and Bhattacharyya, 2017). According to Thirathon *et al.* (2017), BD transformations are a cost-effective means to improve organisational performance.

The researcher focussed on BD managers' support and understanding of the bank's benefits in the field. The study indicates a consensus among interviewees that banks are just another service provider that loses profitability over time without data strategies.

“Continuing the competition involves embracing what is new to satisfy the bank and make a profit and therefore achieve a competitive edge as the Egyptian banking sector still practices the old ways of handling and communicating with clients.” (E06)

The investigator also focused on learning how senior management promoted BD initiatives, finding input into increasing assistance. Inappropriately, senior management cannot grasp what BD is and what it is supposed to do to generate value for the bank; the study results confirm BD's guiding importance is also an obstacle.

“I do not have a good understanding of BD, but as far as I know, some data can be analysed for use in decision-making.” (E09)

Better Decision-Making: The literature supports the view that some researchers have focused on business decisions and how BD can transform banks into proactive strategic businesses. BD solutions advent knowledge about the dynamic business environment through real-time insights, which help augment the decision-making process (Chedrawi *et al.*, 2018).

Additionally, data visualisation allows executives to have real-time access to insights created from BD analytics, allowing them to make improved decisions grounded on data (Cady, 2017). Several studies explored these opportunities (Bhaduri and Fogarty, 2016; Tunguz and Bien, 2016; Dargam *et al.*, 2018). Rumson and Hallett (2019) suggest that corporates base their decisions on verifiable economic transactions through information systems.

The study showed that 96 per cent of interviewees from the executives' group consider conventional consumer data critical in making decisions, primarily on mortgage and credit card choices. However, to be critical, while 3.7% of interview participants believe that BD can be used for better decision making, senior management support traditional data, which is the structured data stored in the banks legacy system.

“BD offers a practical way to evaluate the real world and turn this pool of information into valuable insights and observations that facilitate

enhanced decision-making and, in the case of our bank, a competitive advantage because BD strives to provide the means to make the right decision at the right time based on easier, more accurate, more efficient and more successful.” (E10)

Finally, almost three-quarters said that conventional evidence backed by prior practice was crucial when asked about the critical reasons for improved decision making. Thus, the empirical findings of this research are consistent with those described in the literature review.

“Inside the bank, there is a framework to ensure the consumer data is updated (KYC).” (E07)

Innovative Information with Low Cost: Given that BD is a relatively recent research field in Egypt, it is perhaps typical for banks to ask what advantages its implementation provides and if they can be maintained. Many literature contributions, as examined in this research, have discussed the potentials of BD. Data are shared internally and externally during banking transactions. BD would help banks reveal confidential information and achieve strategic advantages in the modern digital age, resulting in a more outstanding performance, lower operational costs and a more momentous shift in the supply curve.

“Through tracking performance, optimising discounts and pricing offers, saving customer support workers and even closing down unproductive divisions or branches, it has now crossed the threshold of helping banks save money.” (E07)

According to Sarrocco, Morabito and Meyer (2016), in sophisticated data management systems, data has to be extracted, transformed, and loaded into a static model, which is time consuming compared to BD new technology that generates insights at a much lower cost. BD solutions help corporate banking do scenario analysis and generate real-time simulations at a reduced cost, converting them into valuable information for regulatory reporting required by the regulator (Sarrocco *et al.*, 2016).

“For a growing business, BD analytics is an important investment. The bank can gain a strategic edge by introducing BD analytics, reducing running costs and encouraging customer satisfaction. There are numerous consumer knowledge bases that banks can exploit.” (I02)

Efficient BD Risk Management: To remain ahead in the dynamic environment, banks have to continue innovating. In real-time, developing a rigorous risk management framework such as BD will help detect fraud. Banks may evaluate consumer dynamics and raise or reduce prices in that segment (Oracle, 2015; Dawei *et al.*, 2017; Urbinati *et al.*, 2019). BD also offers analytics that classifies future borrowers' risks when sanctioning loans (Joseph *et al.*, 2018). Also, while fraud frequently goes unnoticed before banking institutions' operation is disrupted, BD banks can detect suspicious transactions at the outset.

Better Security and Fraud Detection: Banks are analysing a massive amount of data to disclose possible hazards. Furthermore, while JP Morgan has used AI and BD to identify fraud, Citibank invests in ML and predictive models to reduce financial risk and locate fraudulent online banking actions (BaFin, 2018).

“BD allows banks and insurers to improve risk management by enhanced consumer experiences in real-time dramatically.” (I05)

The qualitative data review results indicate that more than three-quarters of the interviewees recognised BD's successful risk management capacity. Moreover, Business Intelligence (BI) tools can detect possible threats linked to banks' money lending processes. BD analytics help banks evaluate market dynamics and lower or raise interest rates for individuals in different regions (Moshirpour *et al.*, 2017).

“The use of BD would allow the analysis of this unstructured data and improved machine insight that can be used to boost sales efficiency, increase awareness of consumer needs, strengthen the internal risk management mechanism, encourage marketing campaigns and improve fraud detection.” (I02)

Moshirpour *et al.* (2017) has shown that extensive data analytics have been an essential feature of all policies for detecting and stopping finance scam when hackers target multi-channel vulnerabilities that violate information networks. To tackle rising challenges, BD has allowed banks to carry out a large-scale real-time analysis.

Thus, BD holds the secret to optimising its business prospects in the modern, highly competitive financial industry. Moreover, detailed preparation helps banks navigate the increasing enforcement costs and the possibility of non-compliance. However, banks are currently lagging in adopting extensive data analytics methods, suggesting an untapped scope for the banking industry (HK, 2017).

More Accessible Filing of Regulatory Compliance: Most bank workers state that their primary interest in financial services is to ensure that all the government's regulatory enforcement has been fulfilled (Srivastava and Gopalkrishnan, 2015). BD would help scrutinise regulatory criteria, at a glance, from the consumers at each order. In addition, the company rules can be added to BD to verify client requirements as the regulatory enforcement criteria are fed to the analytical dashboard (Stavrakeva, 2020).

“Incident handling, control of corporate continuity, tracking, auditing and checking and international standards enforcement.” (I03)

The majority of bank staff claimed that 92% of bank employees proclaimed that BI software was their main concern with the banking industry by offering correct guidance to each customer request and evaluating and monitoring all regulatory requirements, retaining banking service satisfying all government regulatory compliance criteria.

“BD also would aid to reliably recognise and respond to litigation issues involving important quantities of data, such as gathering any specifics of a legal dispute, assessing incidents and agreeing on the likelihood that the case will lead to court action, tracking laws and avoiding fines and sentences.” (R05)

Through using BD techniques and methods, banks may unleash the power of BD. Henceforth, banks that are capable of calculating BD income will boost revenue and reduce total costs. In addition, banking consumers generate an enormous volume of data every day through tens of millions of additional purchases. The data is put under the umbrella of BD.

IoT's mobile apps made internet resources, chatting, performing bank assignments, researching merchandise and purchasing items more effortless than ever for a customer. These solutions are also used to create customer insights that can map patterns, forecast habits and allow banks better to understand their customers (Rothman, 2018).

Nevertheless, most banks have been reluctant to implement BD because of the proprietary value of data in the banking sector, even though they understand its tremendous benefits. Moreover, implementing BD in banking is in the best interest of the bank. However, it is not without its challenges. Therefore, banks should be aware of them before they proceed with BD. Therefore, the following sub-section discusses those challenges.

5.4.3 Staff Training and Professional Development

As time progresses, there will be a greater need for people who are experienced working on BD. According to Singh Dubey and Tiwari (2020), Data scientists, researchers, and other BD specialists were in great demand in 2021. This is because data will be generated in massive volumes, necessitating sophisticated data analysis techniques. Therefore, it is essential to obtain proper data analytics techniques and tools.

The new technologies would improve the existing structure of data analysis, improved management performance. For example, BD enables real-time data analytics and provides insights about branch performance metrics; in other words, it provides excellent visibility of the bank's daily operations, which provide the aptitude to solve the problem (Wu and Lin, 2017) proactively.

According to Verhoef (2016), BNP Paribas has been using branch performance metrics based on employees' turnover and efficacy, enhancing customer retention and acquisition, and identifying and solving issues quickly and in real-time.

Internal processes optimisation and automation: banks use BD with AI and ML to reduce operating costs and boost performance. If McKinsey & company findings are accurate, 30% of all bank processes can be automated through BD technology, automation eradicating human factors, which resulted in cost savings and reduced failure risk (Lee and Di, 2017).

Moreover, it is believed that automation meaningfully reduces human error. For example, JP Morgan relies on AI and ML to process billions of transactions for enhancing commercial-loan agreements interpretation and algorithmic trading processes that resulted in reducing the document review time, as well as maximise the speed at excellent prices of trading equities, which resulted in significant savings for the corporation (Information Commissioner's Office, 2017; Buchanan, 2019).

The data analysis indicates that through performance tracking, employee's performance may be assessed as to whether they have fulfilled the monthly/quarterly/year objectives or not. In addition, based on the data collected from workers' existing revenues, BD analytics will determine how to make them scale up quicker.

"I think that data lets the bank achieve a deeper understanding of incoming and outgoing cash flow, improving the management of liquidity. This approach may be useful for both real money in branches and the bank's overall liquidity management." (I01)

5.4.4 Implications of BD Technologies for Banking

For stakeholders, the substantive principle of harnessing BD in the banking industry in Egypt has many consequences. The following sections present the complications for administrators, IT-Facilitators, Regulators, and Consumers of this report.

Impact of Digital Technologies on Bankers: BD may appear like a broad environment, but its purpose is to simplify assignments. When the device enters a name or account number, it quickly sifts through all the data and offers only the necessary detail. Banks should, thus, streamline the process and make their work more comfortable and more efficient. To have a significant competitive advantage in the industry, banks have already begun applying insights obtained from BD.

Managers should be aware of their effect on the bank's potential for BD. Therefore, it is essential to understand the advantages and challenges of BD and BD's position and achieve organisational success.

Also, managers should determine whether BD is helpful to their bank. As mentioned in Chapter 2, BD's market drivers can help lead managers in making this decision. Executives may also point out that their dedication to adopting these changes outweighs the rewards of following BD policies primarily in implementations focused on design and architecture or slowly evolving specifications.

Even if a bank upgrades the program, incorrect, incoherent, incomplete, redundant, or obsolete dirty data will bias performance. Before the modern age, specific information was entered manually, and hence the probability of human error was added. Therefore, before moving into a new scheme to identify and delete dirty data instances, banks will closely review and arrange their existing data and authenticate data entry sources in the future to eliminate new instances of dirty data (Côte *et al.*, 2020).

Banks are expected to move from thinking about BD to implementing tools to access transaction data and understand them. So, with that improved intellect, banks may enhance consumer banking experience while increasing their profitability.

Moreover, banks scrap to comply with a rising amount of regulations and regulatory agencies relevant to data. Nevertheless, financial institutions continue to do well to ensure compliance with security and risk management.

“BD will mostly assist to reliably define and react to litigation issues that involve significant quantities of data, such as collecting certain information about a legal incident, evaluating conflicts and agreeing on the possibility that the case will lead to legal proceedings, reviewing laws and avoiding fines and sentences.” (R05)

BI software can help evaluate regulatory requirements by reviewing the customers for each application. Once the regulatory enforcement requirements are fed into the analytical dashboard, the market rules for validating consumer applications can be extended to BD.

Impact of Digital Technologies on Customers: Banks have faced pressure to turn their way of working from product-centric to customer-centric for a long time. One way to do that is by segmenting them to understand their clients better. BD makes it easier for clients to be sorted into separate categories based on profiles, day-to-day transactions, familiarity with online and smartphone users. In addition, banks and credit unions' clients are alerted to the confidentiality of their sensitive records. To resolve industry challenges, banking companies that plan to use BD must implement strict protections such as consumer two-factor authentication, data protection, real-time and permanent masking.

“The incredibly global complexity and high industry interconnectivity make it important that international data security and privacy rules, from the front to the back, and throughout the whole supply chain, including third parties, be completely complied with.” (E01)

While the data collected by BD systems are anonymous at a high level, they can track individual customer's activity patterns if the bank wishes for it. It is helpful to track criminal activity because it is a significant security threat to the consumer if it falls into the wrong hands. There have been already some issues with governments about tracking the use of BD (Hassani, Huang and Silva, 2018).

5.4.5 Challenges in the Use & Reliance of BD Related Technologies

This sub-section discusses some critical challenges experienced by the participants in the banking sector in Egypt. Volume, velocity, and variety are the 3Vs that are defining BD properties. Research from Sheppard *et al.* (2018) indicates that 70% of global banking directors emphasise the importance of a customer-centric approach, which requires a profound understanding of customer requirements. Although 37% of customers feel assured that banks understand their needs, banks are stressed about profiting from data volume. A little part of this data has, however, been used to strengthen customer care.

With a broad range of data generated (structured, semi-structured and unstructured), data becomes more extensive, suggesting that one of the critical problems for banks is managing vast data silos, referred to by the overused and ill-defined term BD (Siddiqui and Qureshi, 2017). According to Côte-Real *et al.* (2019), BD is the next frontier for productivity, innovation, and competition. Therefore, for practical decisions, the Banking industry is moving to use BD.

However, the five principal BD concerns identified in recent research are organisational mindset, Customer concerns about privacy, Legacy infrastructure that needs to be upgraded before integrating BD capabilities, and Banks being subject to more rules and regulations than ever before data into actionable insights. In addition, the complexity of BD presents numerous roadblocks to BD application in banks in Egypt, as detailed below.

The literature suggests that BD's adoption and transition into many banks' current business environment are not feasible. Senior leaders still seem to be aware of crucial BD advantages, but banks often need reassurance about overcoming key BD challenges (Lu *et al.*, 2017; Akter *et al.*, 2019). (HK, 2017). In essence, Whether or not board members are prepared, banking technology is progressing. A crucial indication of successful digital transitions is good leadership. Even though the speed of digital transformation in banking is quickening, bank boardrooms are behind. According to the survey, just a tiny percentage of banking board directors are computer savvy. There are ways that

banks may take to meet this goal sooner. This is crucial if BD is to seize the vast prospects.

Organisational Mindset: BD offers banking the capabilities of transforming it into a more proactive and strategic business. However, many banks struggle to solve a specific business question or problem-driven issue using intuition and experience (Dargam *et al.*, 2018). The broad data pool created and evaluated to make smarter decisions has become the foundation of banking competition. Chedrawi *et al.* (2018) stressed that banks need to apply a paradigm shift to gain a competitive advantage by adopting the data-driven culture and investing more in collecting, storing, and analysing data, particularly in this strict regulatory environment.

Also, by considering data as an advantage, the change in information technology (IT) from a cost centre to a benefits centre will help reach new markets, get new clients or develop new products. Absorptive capacity is believed to be the company's capacity to engage and use emerging technologies to accomplish operational objectives. However, the claim that absorptive ability is positively related to BD adoption is debatable (Dawei *et al.*, 2017; Philip, 2018; Trabucchi and Buganza, 2019).

The data analysis revealed that 47 per cent of stakeholders with 200 sources describes corporate culture as the most prevalent trend. However, banks are unlikely to have in-house BD data specialists, so they must partner with organisations specialising in designing, developing, and distributing BD solutions.

Also, non-technical managers frequently circumvent the need for BD by focusing comparatively more on human judgment than the digital marketing solutions offered by the analytics dashboard. This results in either the bank not selecting BD or side-lined actionable inputs from the BD implementations.

“The corporate culture is focused more on knowledge than evidence, so the challenge is to shift the way workers think to realise the relevance and necessity of BD. It would take time for individuals to adapt and use it to become a business tool, like all modern technology.” (E10)

Many parties dispute the benefits and drawbacks of analysing genetic sequences, social media activity, health data, phone data, government data, and other digital footprints left by people. Given the growing significance of BD as a socio-technical phenomenon, it has been suggested that a critical assessment of underlying assumptions and prejudices is necessary. Boyd and Crawford (2012) proposed six provocations to get people talking about BD, a cultural, technical, and philosophical phenomenon centred on the confluence of technology, analysis, and mythology, which has sparked many utopian and dystopian discussions.

Furthermore, in recent years, interest has grown in BD's adoption in the financial services business. While many banks have tried to implement BD, the advantages of this investment are limited, and companies are struggling to exploit BD's potential fully. Many studies stress that corporate culture plays a crucial part in the success of BD projects and that it is frequently not technology but the primary reason why the BD initiatives fail (Shamim *et al.*, 2019). As a result, the impact of BD investment on Egyptian banks is influenced by cultural issues rather than the BD investment itself, necessitating incorporating business analytics into organisational culture and a favourable attitude toward it among all employees.

The extent to which organisational members (including top-level executives, middle managers, and lower-level employees) make decisions based on data insights defines a data-driven culture. Unfortunately, one of the leading causes of BD initiatives' significant fracture rates is the lack of data-driven culture (Gupta and George, 2016). Therefore, to profit from BD, the XYZ Bank faces the challenges of establishing a data-driven culture that demonstrates that data-based decision-making is helpful to reduce the likelihood of opposition to developing the data-driven culture.

Moreover, for banks to sustain a competitive edge, the capacity to adapt and rearrange their resources is essential. Organisational learning is one element of this skill. Corporate learning refers to the ability of the corporation to study, save, share and use information (Bhatt and Grover, 2005). In addition, banks

face agility and adaptation to the changing market because new technologies, like BD, are quickly changing the market circumstances and innovations.

Banks will need to accept the transition; if they are still not using BD, it is time to put it into action (HK, 2017). Also, banks that focus solely on web creation shall turn around the wheel and indulge in BD analysis services because if they fail to give BD services and solutions, the clients will not be too satisfied (Glass, 2018). So, it is time to brace internally for the BD movement set to change the network environment.

“Non-technical administrators and senior executives already disregard the need for BD by focusing more on human intuition than relying on automated targeting instruments offered by the analytics dashboard. BD is not yet seen as a competitive tool.” (E01)

Turning Data into Actionable Insights: Data quality management: Banks struggle to cope with different types of data volume. Distinct the valued data from the unusable is a challenge. Even though there is a significant growth in the share of potentially valuable data, still there is too much irrelevant data to be sorted. There is also a need for a modern technology framework to exploit technology that has been deemed obsolete (dark data) (Baabdullah *et al.*, 2019; Sharma and Sharma, 2019). On the other hand, data quality is where the utmost influence of BD lies.

Data quality involve characteristics such as validity, accuracy, reasonableness, completeness, and timeliness that are well-defined, recorded, made available, and measured (Financial Stability Board, 2017). However, while BD has brought additional challenges to data quality and integrity, Lewis *et al.* (2018) noted that to capture excellent and reliable data, Banks have to create metadata for data quality, including market guidelines, attributes of data quality, tracking, metrics, controls, cleaning methods, and profiles of data items.

Sarrocchio *et al.* (2016) argue that dealing with this challenge requires strengthening three key data management aspects: data verification, scrutinising the use of this data in decision making, data maintaining and securing.

In essence, Kshetri *et al.* (2017) noted that analysis is complementary to data. Hence, knowing how to manipulate and analyse data is essential to drive value from BD insights (knowledge discovery) that required data skills such as statistical, programming, econometrics, data visualisation skills, and strong business understanding. Nonetheless, there is a significant skill-shortage of these new skill-sets, which require a new workforce management paradigm (Günther *et al.*, 2017).

“Skills and systems are necessary to turn this data into something useful to the bank. There is neither talent nor tech in the current situation.”
(E04)

In comparison, banking system data is hugely diverse and is located in separate divisions. According to its savings, lending, insurance can be distributed across multiple branches and bank units; it is difficult to identify a client based on investment behaviour. To provide correct information, BD should first acquire all these facts.

In the financial sector, every day is a journey of a study led by technological innovation to leverage BD Analytics' potentials in banking. BD and automation combine two models, ML and AI, which improve data and target customers' accuracy, eliminate mistakes, and make grouping and checking customers and product data simpler for banks (Buchanan, 2019).

For example, ML and AI can be introduced in the liquidity risk to help banks target customers quickly. These systems will regularly inspect the bank's financial reports to identify typical data products, such as loan prices, household profile income. The bank can then determine which clients may be the best choice for a new loan or other commodity Banks and credit unions can also use AI and ML to track and classify important influencers behind a customer's decisions (Information Commissioner's Office, 2017).

Furthermore, Jones (2019) stated that large-scale data was not as revolutionary, ubiquitous, or comprehensive as commonly depicted. The repercussions of this dataset reconceptualization are addressed in some detail. There is a distinction between "data in the idea" as documented and "data in

practice" as implemented. The latter, usually a tiny and non-representative fraction of the former, will significantly influence the ramifications.

On the other hand, digital transformation has accelerated in many organisations. As a result, there was never a more prominent requirement for computers with data analysis abilities. Data analysis managers can use and utilise this information in companies that demand particular expertise within the finance function, but the skills are not available to satisfy demand at the moment. Some sectors naturally attract outstanding data skills is a complement to this challenge (Hilbert, 2016).

The candidates may find it more attractive to IT businesses, consultancy firms in particular and consumer sectors. This makes it difficult for other industries to fulfil critical functions. However, this skills shortage represents an opportunity for employees seeking to move up the corporate ladder. It also means companies may want to partner more closely with technology vendors to help bring their data analysis to the next level.

Egypt's educational experience quality is still lacking and unequally distributed despite significant progress in boosting human capital through improved educational institutions. The market for private tutoring has expanded due to a lack of high-quality education at the elementary and secondary levels. Egypt also suffers a lack of trained and semi-skilled workers. Even if high-skilled personnel are available, the training they get is of poor quality. This is primarily an issue for small-medium companies and the public sector in protected domestic markets.

In addition, the quality of instructors in public schools poses a significant challenge for Egyptian education. In ethnographic research by Hartmann (2008), Several Egyptian teachers chose to teach because they had no other options and since the nature of their work did not conflict with the significant role of mothers in terms of gender. In Egypt, low wages are attracted by low-skilled workers by the public education system. The system runs from earlier years to the last courses, overcrowded classrooms, poor attendance and

absence of decent libraries or teacher's office space. If they exist in state schools, computing and science laboratories are regularly revised.

Privacy Concerns: The enormous volume of data being generated needs state-of-the-art technology infrastructure, like the BD. However, the data being processed in conjunction with the BD system needs to be protected, which is one of the problems facing shortly (Siddiqui and Qureshi, 2017).

According to the data analysis, consumer data analytics is a relatively low priority sector for banks. As a result, most companies have concentrated on risk management rather than utilising technology to improve the user experience. Furthermore, due to a lack of trust, which makes data quality more complex, more than 80% of consumers stated that:

“I am not giving any of the data, just providing unimportant data, and blocking essential data.” (C02), “For important information, I do not disclose.” (C09).

Security and Privacy Issues: BD offers banks main steps for advancements, yet, there is significant possible data misuse. However, according to ISACA international (2017), only 38% of businesses globally are prepared to deal with data leakage and security breaches, at a time when cybersecurity remains the further most serious challenge in the banking industry (Karthik *et al.*, 2017).

BD analytics tools and strategies can help banks effectively target resources and provide a better service simultaneously (Emmanuel, 2017). Nonetheless, the privacy issue that emerged from the amount of data that is accumulated and processed by banks about their customers, such as locations, debt, salary, marital status, how many kids, presumably creates for the customer the perception that banks would take advantage of that (Collmann and Matei, 2016; Kshetri, 2016a; Ziegler, 2019).

While the data gathered by BD systems are generally anonymous, the bank can follow individual customer's activity patterns if the bank so desires. It aids in detecting illegal activities since it poses a substantial security risk to

consumers if it falls into the wrong hands. Many concerns have already been raised with the government concerning tracking the use of BD. When it comes to data supply, almost all interviewees think they do not trust the bank.

“Concerning my data, I do not trust the bank as they can share my data with the government and other companies such as telecommunication companies.” (C05)

BD Infrastructure and Legacy Data Systems: According to Ge *et al.* (2018), data management takes approximately 9% of banks' operating income, mainly storing and analysing data in real-time. Although cloud computing technology decreased the cost of storing data, banks still use their legacy data management to store and age customer data dated 20-30 years ago (Kale, 2017).

Furthermore, banks are still using their traditional data management system that struggles to keep up with the growing workload (Siddiqui and Qureshi, 2017). According to Price Waterhouse Coopers (2017), 92% of the world's top banks also rely on IBM mainframes, compared to 8% using FinTech, built on customer-centred and agile systems. Additionally, sophisticated methods like replicated data and the same data to be stored was estimated eight times into a warehouse, which increases the cost of managing the data.

On the other hand, to analyse such data soil, banks have to choose between accessible open sources requiring skill-set to handle or BD management systems high-cost and need skilled data scientists to extract the data value (HK, 2017).

Lastly, more added costs of the high-speed computing systems, velocity is essential, real-time data handling is crucial in digital multichannel customer, real-time offer and pricing required current data feeds with on-time analytics (Rahman and Iverson, 2015; Truong, 2016). Consequently, banking faces the difficulty of either increasing the processing volume or entirely restructuring their schemes to take up the challenge (Akter *et al.*, 2019).

The investigator also claims that many banking networks have not been configured to handle continuous data inflows, a critical condition of BD, considering their conversion to cloud systems. BD introduction requires a comprehensive overhaul for most existing banking systems in conjunction with a BD consultancy firm. It is not easy since the system must continue to be upgraded while the modifications are in place.

“The most important problem is the services and technology used in the bank since primary customer information is hardly investigated for the main reason of delivering customer offers and not for a deeper understanding of the customer.” (E09)

The financial services sector of both the consumer and corporate sides is rapidly moving away from archaic methodologies and advanced digital consumer and business practices. Between the financial service provider and the consumer, digital progress is taking place. For example, banks have shifted away from paper and the entry paradigm favouring data and analysis-driven banking operations that augment online and offline customer behaviour. Furthermore, conventional banks are under pressure, which leads to structural changes in the digital world.

In the same vein, Egyptian banks have recognised the relevance of digital advancements and aggressively work on viable solutions and strategies despite other societal and regulatory difficulties. Many (digital) advancements may be seen mainly on the front end of the customer. As the digital turbulence causes, banks must analyse risks and possibilities and create new business prospects for the future.

New FinTech rivals, shifting business models, growing regulatory and compliance constraints and disruptive technologies are driving significant changes in the banking industry. The same technology that created the disruption could fix these and other financial issues, but transferring old systems to new solutions was not always easy. If banks and credit unions survive and prosper in today's climate, they must accept digital advances.

In upgrading legacy systems, it is vital to emphasise that banks may confront a large and expensive job since they cannot complete their business for months while sorting out outdated systems. Moreover, IT experts cannot discover significant red flags, locate solutions, and patch them up to address the problem without proper testing. The catastrophe of TSB Bank rapidly became one of our worst meltdowns in technology. First, millions of clients were denied access to online banking due to an IT transfer from its old owner, Lloyds Banking Group, to a new digital platform with Spanish bank Sabadell. Then, five months later, TSB CEO Paul Pester resigned.

For example, TSB transitioned from a system run by TSB's former owner, Lloyds Banking Group, to Sabadell of Spain, who purchased the bank in 2017. It appears that the technology was not adequately tested, that a pilot – say, 5% – of consumers should have been moved first, but this did not occur, and mayhem resulted. Many consumers who signed in online found themselves in the account of another customer. One-third of the accounts of the client have been impacted. For up to six weeks, customers could neither make nor receive any payments, and many saw amounts stolen from their accounts. Unfortunately, scammers pretending to be employees of TSB and stole at least 1,300 consumers took advantage of this circumstance (Kerr, 2018).

Legal Regulatory Challenges: The requirements for data security are going to be high. In the United Kingdom, the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR) introduction and the Data Protection Act (DPA) have placed broad restrictions on the worldwide sector. Many banks are now adopting data processing protocols in place with expected results. However, BD is pressured with major regulatory issues (Voigt and Bussche, 2017; Tamò-Larrieux, 2019).

Banks are proceeding judiciously because of risks because of the growing impact of regulations (Group, 2018; Tamò-Larrieux, 2019). Philippon (2016) claimed that regulatory requirements are shaping the banks' data management approach. Notwithstanding that, BaFin (2018) suggests that policymakers ought to evaluate whether the actual comprehension of BD potential for customers' needs alters the current supervisory framework or whether the current one is adequate.

Banks are frequently under pressure to meet with the growing number of data laws and regulatory authorities. As a result, financial institutions have to go further than monitoring and risk management to guarantee compliance. The researcher agrees with the previous statement; however, more than 95% of interviewees understand the proposed law on Egypt's data security.

“There is currently no precise legislation in Egypt governing data security that would require the data subject's permission before processing personal data.” (R03)

Role of Professional Bodies: The Banking Law and associated Executive Regulations govern Egypt's banking sector and operators. The Banking Law designates the Egyptian Central Bank (CBE) as an autonomous regulatory agency monitoring and exercising the rights and functions of the bank sector. Apart from the requirements of banking legislation, the banking industry is controlled by the laws of banking supervision (supervision rules) and regularly released CBE circularise and judgments governing different elements of the banking industry and organisations operating within the sector (CBE, 2019).

The Banking Law states that the CBE has the following significant objectives and functions: to achieve price stability and to ensure a sound banking system; to formulate and implement monetary, lending and banking policies; to issue and to define its names and specifications; to monitor and manage the banking system; (public and private).

According to Mohieldin et al. (2019), Overall, Egypt's financial growth has progressed beyond the functions described above. Nevertheless, Egypt's political and economic instability has impacted the overall and banking sector's performance in recent years. In order to fulfil its job successfully, the financial system must be solid and efficient. For sustainable growing countries, it is vital to have a healthy and stable financial system based on good macro-economic and sensible regulation.

5.5 Summary

This chapter covered the research methods used for theoretical sampling, data collection, and analysis directed by the CGT methodology. The primary data source was random, purposeful sampling and intensive, semi-structured interviews with banking industry participants in Egypt. Initial coding, focused coding and theoretical coding backed by the storyline as an expanded theoretical memo were used in the research process.

Besides, the results of theoretical and empirical studies have been consistent in this chapter. Several themes from the study and current literature, along with BD paradigms around Egypt's banking industry, were explored. This discussion reveals that the banking sector has unresolved prospects for BD.

The data analysis supports the assumption that BD could help banks with better decision making, gain a competitive advantage, reduce costs, improve customer services, personalise marketing, boost the overall performance, ease filing regulation compliance and ensure efficient risk management. However, the results are also indicative of the BD key challenges. The most significant challenges to BD adoption are customer concerns about privacy, legacy infrastructure, legal and regulatory, organisational mindset, and turning data into actionable insights.

This chapter concluded the participants' crucial concerns and described the internal and external influences affecting Egypt's banking industry in light of BD opportunities and challenges, focusing on the theoretical basis provided in Chapter 2. Therefore, the next chapter concludes the study findings and recommendations.

6 Chapter Six: Conclusions

6.1 Introduction and Summary of the Thesis

This chapter begins by bringing the thesis to an end, shows that the research goal and objectives were achieved, addresses the research questions, and concludes. Finally, the main contributions are summarised, the study's limitations and future directions are proposed.

The primary goal of this research is to comprehend BD's function and influence in developing nations' financial sectors, explain the BD phenomenon and bridge the knowledge gaps by building a substantial theory based on the Egyptian banking context. Chapter 2 reviewed the current academic and industry-based literature. Then a CGT account and the procedures used in this study were discussed in Chapter 3. The findings were stated in Chapter 4, and the emerging substantive theory was demonstrated by using BD in the banking industry in Egypt. In Chapter 5, the method of data generation and interpretation was presented in the first section. The second section discussed the results and the relevant literature.

Therefore, this chapter summarises the aim, objectives and research questions given the main findings, section 6.2 evaluation for the substantive theory. Section 6.3 acknowledges the implications of this study and summarises its contributions to knowledge and literature. Section 6.4 describes the study's shortcomings and guidance for overcoming these limitations in the future; in section 6.5, the researcher makes suggestions on potential future contributions of the theory and how it can be researched in other substantive areas of the developing economies. Finally, section 6.6 concludes the observations and remarks on the original goal to summarise the study's successes.

6.1.1 Aim, Objectives and Research Questions Overview

In this part, the research questions are revisited to demonstrate that they have been addressed:

The research aim was by using the Egyptian banking sector as an example, this study aimed to understand BD's role and effect with/in the financial industry

in developed countries, help clarify the BD phenomenon and resolve the gap by generating a substantive theory.

There were three comprehensive research goals:

1. To critically review the academic and industry-based current state of knowledge about the role and impact of BD on the banking and finance sector;
2. To comprehend how BD is constructed by actors of the banking industry of Egypt; and
3. To discuss the lessons learnt from investments in BD in Egypt's banking industry.

Therefore, the aim has been achieved. The literature review recognised a plethora of industry-based and academic contributions that provided several critical factors within the banking industry in Egypt, enabled a review of published studies on BD and provided a methodological and theoretical basis for BD implementation in banking contexts. The study also reveals an appreciation of the different BD themes and drivers that specifically affect its adoption. Figure 4-2, discussed in Chapter 4, reflects the study's conclusions and addresses the participants' crucial concerns about Egypt's banking industry.

6.2 Evaluation for the Substantive Theory

According to Glaser and Strauss (1967), GT can be assessed based on four factors: Fit, Relevance, Workability, and Modifiability. In this section, these four measures, the substantive theory of harnessing BD in Egypt's banking industry, is carried out.

Fit: Many managements shared the new theory, which they considered to be beneficial and vital. For instance, one of the participants in the Executive Interest Group received input on emerging theory:

“The core problems are evident and look good. For executives, ITs and our clients, the substance theory of harnessing BD in the banking industry would be beneficial.” (E01)

Several Egyptian participant groups were presented with the theory. Groups of participants acknowledged their trust in the legitimacy of the theory they constructed and distinguished their views from others.

Relevance: For the evolving theory, the input from the participants offered meaning. After a summary of the results to the field specialists, the technical input arrived. This input became a significant source of proof of the theory's validity (Colker, 2008).

Workability: Codes, principles and standards for BD in the banking industry, constantly evolving, are of primary interest to stakeholders. As a result of many discussions with the participants and the study supervisor, the emergent substantive theory operates well (Charmaz, 2006).

Modifiability: The emerging substantive theory was adaptive, as revealed in the review. A basic understanding of the benefits led to the emergence of the BD variables, which highlighted an essential difficulty (Engward, 2015).

Compared to those parameters, a theory's ability to match the current literature on the issue and expand it also helps assess. Since the preliminary literature review is performed within the same substantive study field, only following established terms and definitions, literature becomes a primary validating source for emerging theory. All significant categories resulting from this GT review were correlated and presented in Chapter 5, part 2, with the literature identified.

6.3 Contributions: Revisiting the Research Questions

A thorough overview of current information and influential research contributions specific to the research field was given by the literature chapter

review (BD in the banking industry). This study aims and objectives were pursued by answering the three research questions referred to in Chapter 1.

1. What is the academic and industry-based current state of knowledge about BD's role and impact on the banking and finance sector?
2. How is BD constructed by stakeholders in the banking sector in Egypt?
3. What lessons have been learnt from investment in BD in Egypt's banking sector over the last decade?

The researcher first identified the key stakeholders, conducted a pilot survey, conducted 33 interviews with the four stakeholders, and examined several BD expectations to answer BD's importance and effect in Egypt's banking sector. The main issue was identified: Harnessing BD in the banking industry arose as a substantive theory introduced in Chapter 4. The author then reviewed the existing literature, as described in Chapter 2.

As a result, this section highlights the study's significant contributions to literature and understanding. The researchers' understanding of the impact of external and internal variables on the execution of BD methods is the first and most significant contribution to the body of knowledge, followed by a thorough review of analytical literature and industry-based field research.

To the best of the researcher's knowledge, this is one of the few studies entirely focused on the banking industry in developing nations that have studied important BD variables that may be harmful to BD acceptability while seeking to rationalise the past decade's growth toward BD (Alber, 2015; Khashaba, 2019; Osman, 2018; Weforum, 2019).

As explained in Chapter 2, this thesis bridged theoretical and methodological gaps in the BD literature that had not been addressed to the best of the researcher's ability in prior investigations, either technically or practically. Thus, this research gives insight into a more in-depth knowledge of BD's position in Egypt's banking industry for the first time. Furthermore, BD Adoption's benefits and obstacles are highlighted by giving a roadmap for accomplishing this. Thus, by employing CGT analytic tools, the study adds to the body of knowledge.

In addition, by developing a substantive theory for Egypt's banking industry, this thesis makes an essential contribution to literature. In several respects, this theory is considered unique, offering a straightforward interpretation of naturally nuanced definitions and categories that would impact banks, all in the sense of successfully implementing BD in Egypt's banking industry.

The theoretical sample chosen for the interviews consisted of 33 interviewees from four categories of stakeholders affected by BD in the banking sector. The perspectives of the key stakeholders representing the bank supported the scientific evidence that resulted from these interviews. Through undertaking this study, the researcher concluded that the substantive theory that emerged is based on a highly personalised model consistent with the bank's framework and strategic goals.

Table 6-1 Summary the critical contributions of this study

Contributions	Description	Chapter/Figure
Literature Review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critically reviewed the current literature of BD • Assessment of academic contributions • Evaluation of empirical contributions • Research gaps (Theoretical, Methodological and empirical) 	Chapter 2
Constructing Substantive Theory	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Critical foundations of BD challenges • Outputs of BD adoption advantages to the banking industry. • This study generated the substantive theory of Harnessing BD in the banking industry in Egypt 	Chapter 4,5 Figure (4-2)
Research Methodology	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research has contributed to the field of methodological literature through the CGT usage account. Methodological contributions CGT 	Chapter 3,4
Empirical Findings	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Qualitative research, Practical Recommendations 	Chapter 4,5
Evaluating the GT	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • GT Evaluation Criteria 	Chapter 3,6

Source: Researcher

Finally, the CGT's comprehensive descriptions of cultural, political, and social contexts are overlooked in this research. Furthermore, because the researcher views the BD region as very diverse, a thorough knowledge of its internal and external settings is required. As a result, several GT techniques collect and analyse this BD study's methodological approach.

6.3.1 Practical Recommendations

The study reveals that the digital economy is making significant disruption and innovative opportunities for Egypt's banking sector. Nevertheless, banks have started grasping the potential of BD. BD is thought to play a critical role in driving profitable growth and success in the banking industry. Therefore, the researcher suggests that banks and financial services providers quickly respond and set up an action plan to recognise the significant opportunities banks can unveil by understanding BD's banking role.

This research reported several potentials of deploying BD in the banking sector, such as improved customer services, enhanced marketing, competitive advantage, better decision-making, cost reduction, boosting overall performance, efficient risk management, and more accessible filing regulation compliance.

Financial firms have adequate knowledge to reconsider their operating methods, become more knowledgeable, and be customer-centric to create sustainable development. The study found many examples of how BD is used in the banking sector. However, as BD is still in its embryonic period, all those attempts have scarcely scratched the surface. It is also important to harness the total capacity of BD in banking. Therefore, banks need to reconsider their activities and follow data-driven strategies to remain relevant and efficient.

Despite the financial services industry's recognition of the relevance of BD, banks have yet to develop a standard data usage strategy. Even though practically no one has invested in utilising data to enhance consumer loyalty on a large scale, most banks have used BD technologies to aid with fraud and risk identification. The survey identified the top five areas in which the banking

industry can improve profits. Banks should do all possible to accelerate the transition to the BD paradigm. It includes, but is not limited to the following:

Modified DIKW Pyramid: The model illustrates the interdependence of data, information, knowledge, and wisdom. It serves as a medium for collecting unstructured data and extracting value from it. Data collection for personal, business, industrial, and other purposes has never been more common or invasive. The data that has been interrogated becomes information, but whether this information is valuable or significant depends on how the data was investigated and how reliable it was.

As a consequence, information can be transformed into knowledge but not necessarily into usable knowledge. While knowledge and wisdom are closely related, wisdom typically requires a sum and longevity of acquired knowledge, as well as an intent. So, this research indicates that the DIKW model can be modified to include purpose knowledge as intelligence.

Paradigm Shift: The banking business tends to be powered primarily by insight, expertise and customer experience. Banks need to promote more data-driven thinking and engage more in collecting, managing, and studying data. Banks that will benefit from BD will have a competitive advantage in this tight regulatory setting.

By embracing a data-driven, creative culture maintained by the quality and consistent data across the enterprise, banks will offer customised services and products in real-time. Therefore, in the management mindset, a cultural change is needed to prioritise investing in BD, thus exploiting the potential of emerging technologies, such as AI and cognitive computing.

Furthermore, more data is produced and gathered than ever before due to technology developments and automation. Simultaneously, financial system stakeholders, including regulators, get high-quality and timely information to help them make decisions. For the industry to play its part, the Bank gets data at the lowest possible cost. As a result, data gathering provides complete and timely insights into emerging threats, allowing the Bank to take early and deliberate action to reduce such risks.

- In terms of leadership, board members constantly learn about new technologies, completely understand current technologies, and empower their workers to find innovative technologies and use them to reinvent the firm from every angle. However, more work is still to be done in the banking industry to enhance technical expertise on boards. As a result, banks may take measures to increase banking board technology competence.
- Board members should be educated on the technologies that are transforming the world. Coach the board members on what these technologies do, how they function, how they will be used, and the hazards regularly.
- Take the time to listen to others: Technology expertise is all around them. Utilize other resources inside the business, such as partners, suppliers, consultants, and unexpected specialists.
- Members with technical backgrounds should be appointed: Technical skills and diversity should be prioritised and strengthened by the current board.
- Investigate how technology can help the business: Understanding technology is crucial, but it is just half the battle. The other half of the team is looking at how technology might help the bank as a whole. This viewpoint must come from the board of directors, who have the business knowledge that IT teams lack.
- Comprehension of the interplay between people and technology: Boards must carefully consider the interaction between technology and people to develop experiences that consumers appreciate and healthy for workers and eventually benefit the bank. Technology's potential is just as broad as its people. Businesses thus need a modern culture of support to recruit and retain the most outstanding employees.

As far as organisational culture is concerned, the conventional corporate structure adheres to banks with hierarchical cultures. Egyptian banks were primarily centred on a transparent chain of command and numerous management levels on internal organisations that divide employees and leadership.

In essence, A culture based on information must be characterised by how organisational members (including senior, middle and lower management) decide upon the information gathered from the data. One fundamental cause for the significant failure rate for BD projects is the lack of data-driven culture. In order to profit from BD, XYZ Bank confronts the problems of establishing a data-oriented culture that shows that a data-oriented decision-making process is helpful to reduce opposition to the development of data-oriented culture. The banks need to preserve a competitive edge to adapt and redefine their resources appropriately.

There, organisational learning is one of the elements which impact this capacity. The ability of the organisation to investigate, conserve, share and use the knowledge refers to organisational learning. By becoming flexible and adapted to the constantly changing markets, banks have challenges because of quickly changing market conditions and new technological advances, such as BD.

Turning Data into Actionable Insights: Data attributes (validity, precision, timeline, reasonability, completeness) are well-defined, registered, and measured to ensure the best data quality. Financial organisations need to develop a data quality metadata policy for BD's quality to advance the data quality management initiative.

Financial services institutions, on the other hand, had a skills shortage. As a result, few individuals have the necessary abilities to analyse and understand all of this BD. Skills shortages are a serious issue. To identify and hire competent data scientists, banks must embrace a new workforce management approach.

Furthermore, as was mentioned in the previous chapter, although there has been tremendous progress in building human capital through better educational institutions, the quality of school experiences remains poor and unchanged. As a result, this research highlighted the relevance of technology in addressing the skills gap. Education is one of the industries that has been dramatically impacted by technology. Everyone may experience the effect of technology,

from schools to colleges to universities. Unstructured and Dark Data may be a significant resource and source of raw data in undergraduate and PhD research. Here are some ideas that technology may improve the academic industry in Egypt:

- Traditional learning might make it more complicated for pupils to grasp a topic. However, Digital simulations and models may assist students in better understanding numerous disciplines and becoming familiar with the marvels of the modern world.
- It has also been demonstrated that technology is helpful to teachers, making it challenging to communicate certain concepts inside physical classrooms. Technically skilled teachers may deliberately organise their lessons by employing various textual forms, engagement models, and student participatory interfaces.
- In the online age, the notion of group study was improvised. Students no longer need to gather physically; online collaboration tools get the job done. Students may not only talk and communicate there, but they can also share papers and notes. If assigned a collaborative assignment, this technique proves to be an excellent choice.
- Another significant benefit that students have gained as a result of educational, technological advancements is self-paced learning. Some individuals learn quickly and adapt quickly, while others take longer to understand a subject. Such kids are lucky to have technology as part of their education; due to a solid understanding of prepared courses and an online curriculum to narrow the BD skills gap, they can easily stay up with their peers.

Customer Concerns about Privacy: Whereas BD gives banks tremendous opportunity, privacy infringement comes with a big red flag. A significant opportunity for data misuse remains. To help deliver quality services and target capital more efficiently, financial institutions can also use BD technology. The use of such data does not result in a breach of their protection or compliance with the regulations. It is also essential to provide users with continuous communication about what information is gathered and improve services and

products. Besides, clients should be in direct charge of their data, ensuring that they order their data to be seen and updated.

Legacy System Modernisation: The legacy framework cannot cope with the growing data workload. Through using obsolete technology, banks gather, store, and interpret data. Legacy systems have many hidden costs, such as maintenance and support, integration and compliance, security, loss of business opportunities, organisational agility and efficiency.

When it comes to BD, legacy systems require modernisation, integration, and compliance. Therefore, it is vital to consider transforming the organisation for the digital future. Banks need to prepare for the digital future through legacy system assessment framework, overcoming resistance to modernization, considering risk and challenges, estimating digital modernisation costs, and defining success criteria.

New FinTech competitors, evolving business models, increased regulatory and compliance requirements, and disruptive technology leads to a fundamental transformation in the banking sector. The technology that has created this upheaval may aid in the resolution of these and other banking-related challenges, but the shift from antiquated methods to new solutions has not always been simple. On the other hand, banks and credit unions must embrace digital transformation to survive and prosper in the new digital economy.

Governance, compliance, transparency, ethics, and security rules in the financial industry must encompass a digital ecosystem and business development. Both the client and the supplier of financial services are undergoing digital changes. The banking sector, in particular, has progressed from a paradigm of journal and ledger entry to one of data-driven and analytics-driven banking operations that encompasses both online and offline consumer behaviour.

Furthermore, the pressure on traditional banks is increasing as a result of digital structural change. Egyptian banks have recognised the relevance of digital advancements despite other societal and regulatory obstacles and are actively developing solutions and strategies. However, many developments are mainly

at the front end of the customer. Given the level of disruption caused by digital disruption, banks need to assess the dangers and possibilities and begin developing new business strategies for the future.

Role of Professional Bodies: More and more accountability is being imposed by legislation. BD has substantial legal and legislative apprehension due to its sheer scale, which has drawbacks and complexities. Many banks now have effective small data scale monitoring and data protection mechanisms in place. However, given the rising impact of regulation, banks are proceeding judiciously. Financial institutions should take into consideration the restrictions of privacy concerns and regulatory requirements. Banks must be ready to provide regulators with a rapid response to regulatory pressure. Therefore, there is a need for adopting innovative technologies that can provide insights into risks.

The CBE's principal aims and functions, as previously stated, are to achieve price stability and ensure the integrity of the banking system. Formulation and implementation of monetary, credit and banking policies; issuance and definition of banknotes, denominations and specifications thereof; banking sector supervision; the management of gold, foreign currency reserves, and the reserve's operation (public and private).

As a result, Egypt's financial progress continues. However, Egypt's recent political and economic instability has impacted the country's economy and the banking sector's operations. In order to perform its functions properly, the financial system must be stable and efficient. Good macroeconomic governance and prudential legislation are based on a sound and stable financial system for long-term growth.

6.4 Limitations

In this study, researchers explored different subject aspects, theoretical contexts, analysis methods, data gathering and evaluation processes, and research samples collection. This section discusses six significant shortcomings that vary based on the researcher's knowledge of the problem

and resources such as time, involvement, and access to information and talents.

Firstly, the empirical research was restricted to the participants having worked for the bank, confining the fieldwork to the banking industry. The researcher has selected senior managers with extensive BD experience for the interview sample to mitigate this constraint's impact. The sample size was limited to 33 interviews. The complexities of the banking sector in which the research was carried out and the interviewees' high profile justify the small sample size.

Given the constraints of this study, fundamental BD ideas and categories related to its successful implementation have been explored. The data analysis helps identify critical patterns and ideas while capturing and verifying crucial BD functions, quirks, and similarities. As a result, the author of this study could not conduct sufficient research on the social, economic, and cultural environment to cover it entirely.

Secondly, some individuals may oppose a constructivist grounded approach to the theory as shortcomings with disputes remaining in CGT literature as an approach and member testing as a system. However, the author did not view and defended CGT's positive features in Chapter 2 (section 3.10). The researcher was reflexively monitoring his biases, bias, and prior information to ensure that they did not unduly influence preconceptions.

According to Wertz *et al.* (2011), the way interviewees and interviewers interpret social truth, GT analysis holds the potential for bias. However, the researcher mitigated the risk of bias before gathering and evaluating evidence, by unbracketing his background and prior experience, without any central literature analysis, thus avoiding bias.

Third, while the study was carried out in the context of the Egyptian banking industry, the researcher believes that the use of BD in the banking sector may be expanded to other sections of the financial services industry (i.e. assuming management recognised the individual, organisational structure and appropriately tailored the system).

Also, qualitative analysis and CGT are not structured to generalize outcomes based on a large, representative sample (Thornberg *et al.*, 2014). Instead, this thesis aimed to produce a theory that could provide more insight and a deeper understanding of BD's topic in the Egyptian banking market. Finally, given the absence of published literature, the researcher acknowledges that the substantive theory offers a tentative reason for BD's role in Egypt's banking industry with space for further development.

Fourthly, the study sought to increase the consistency of this interpretive study by ensuring that four parameters were used to assess the quality of the emerging substantive theory: suit, workability, significance and adaptability. In order to ensure that results are legitimate and credible, the interview manual and the debriefing method defines the tone of the interviews, and the reports need to be checked. The interview schedule was also established on a robust theoretical framework, ensuring that the results were believable and backed up by appropriate data.

Accordingly, the findings' internal validity was also supported by purposeful sampling by coding procedures to optimise survey heterogeneity and ensure detailed analysis of qualitative data sets. Therefore, purposeful sampling enabled pattern recognition across participants, thus enhancing the accuracy of the findings.

Fifthly, the researcher was a novice grounded theorist. The researcher also learned GT analysis during the analysis, as routinely planned and checked for the research production process. When the author wrote the memo and a research journal, it was thoughtfully considered this development. The university methodology workshops and consultations with the lead supervisor culminated in peer support and learning experiences to develop scientific skills.

Sixthly, this research's final potential drawback is that the researcher was worried about the coronavirus's ongoing situation: the lockdown prohibiting face-to-face contact with the project supervisor and the timeframe for this study was consistent. However, the researcher was keen to finish this study as

planned and continue working hard to escape the press, stay concentrated, and speak with the supervisor regularly.

6.5 Future Research

The literature review highlighted a need for more study into BD in the financial services sector by showing that, from a theoretical viewpoint, most published research discusses BD in financial services, unsupported by analytical evidence. Thus, this study's exploratory findings provide a starting point for further studies into many BD-related subjects inside and outside Egypt's banking industry.

The first suggestion is that potential studies, in a case study of an airline, industrial enterprise, media industry or telecommunications sector, should explore the acceptance and application of BD in a sector other than banking. The importance of such a study is that it would include details about how BD implementation could differ across sectors. It will also help consider the degree of precise operational variables disrupting the BD methods in many internal and external contexts.

The study should also examine whether the theory retains workability and modifiability in the substantive areas of financial services outside the banking sector in terms of fit and importance. For instance, a theory may be carried out in various specialities in banking, investment banks, credit unions, and credit card firms. A formal theory of BD use in financial services could be developed if the theory's extension also works beyond the context of other fields to bring about a more abstract of terms and definitions. It was beyond the doctoral program's reach to develop a formal theory, so it is a prospect to explore for the future.

For future studies, the second suggestion may be the quantitative approach in future BD research with a broad sampling population to obtain a greater generalisation of the data. Also, it could result in visually structural model representations.

The third suggestion, the researcher agrees that future studies should concentrate on BD characteristics that are important in decision-making on BD adoption, such as establishing a coherent shift in corporate culture or examining how harnessing BD theory can add value to the bank. As the BD area is increasingly evolving, new relevant elements and contexts of current BD information should also continue to be pursued by researchers.

It is further recommended to measure the importance, ability, difficulties, and shortcomings of BD facets. BD study in the banking industry has been emphasised as essential by Egyptian banks, the department, or the importance of research and development. Investigating how BD can boost efficiency, including cost-effectiveness, is a focus for the banking sector. As a detailed survey on BD's prospects, Work on cognitive banking and how AI and ML can be used has also been suggested to energize BD in the banking sector to discover potential prospects.

6.6 Summary

In conclusion, this study aimed to develop a concrete explanatory theory for BD's banking sector application in Egypt. This aim was justified by the apparent lack of a research-based explanation of how stakeholders in the banking industry construct the concept of BD; and what social structures were for the BD to be part of the banking culture.

The underlying strategy and methods of study used to address the research questions are explored in this thesis. Therefore, the research's conclusions were presented using a series of interviews and memos from the study. In addition, a detailed analysis studied how the CGT emerged from this data, among other literature. Also expressed were the consequences for the implementations and future architectures of the substantive GT.

The central concern of Egypt's banking industry participants regarding the use of BD was the common theme in the study, namely that bank data processing is currently being used in a way that is not feasible for the future. BD is a significant asset that could improve performance in the banking industry, the thesis argued. Executives, IT facilitators, regulators and researchers may now

use this theory to frame measures and ensure that BD is harnessed in the banking sector. BD should be encouraged to ensure that banks achieve holistic compliance with legislation, competitive advantage and customer satisfaction to enhance the overall performance.

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8 Appendix A: Ethics Approval

05/07/2019

Dear Mr Tharwat Khalil,

Your application 8219: Comprehending the role of Big Data in the banking industry in Egypt, submission 6881, has been approved by the Business and Enterprise SEC . You may now proceed with your study. If you wish to make any significant changes to the study you must seek the committee's approval before actioning them.

Good luck with your research.

Mr D McFadzean

9 Appendix B: Participant Information

Participant Information Sheet

Overview of the Participant Information Sheet

This information sheet will provide you with brief and summary information on the essential elements of the specific study: what the research is about, the condition or treatment under study, the voluntary nature of involvement, what will happen during and after the research has taken place, the participants' responsibilities, and the potential inconvenience.

Study Title

Comprehending the role of Big Data in developing countries financial industry: The case of banking sector in Egypt

Invitation paragraph

I would like to invite you to take part in a research study. Before you decide, you need to understand why the research is being done and what it would involve for you. Please take time to read the following information carefully. Ask questions if anything you read is not clear or would like more information. Take time to decide whether or not to take part in this study.

What is the purpose of the study?

This study is being conducted as an integral part of the completion of the research degree 'Doctor of Business Administration' (DBA) at the University of the West of Scotland.

Why have I been invited?

You have been chosen to be a participant in this study because you have significant experience in the banking industry in Egypt.

Do I have to take part?

It is up to you to decide. We will describe the study and go through the information sheet, which we will give to you. We will then ask you to sign a consent form to show you agreed to take part. You are free to withdraw at any time, without giving a reason.

What will happen to me if I take part?

If you decided to be part of this study, then:

- The data collection should last 30-45 minutes.
- You will be asked to attend an interview;
- You will be only expected to answer a specific number of questions related to your experience in the banking industry.

For interviews, the dialogue will be voice recorded to analyse the data strictly, taking into consideration the issue of confidentiality, and maintaining the anonymity of the interviewee. Only the researcher and the director of studies will have access to these recordings and will be deleted once the data analysis is completed.

What will you have to do?

Your main contribution would be to answer the questions outlined in the interviews as transparently and to the best of your ability.

What are the possible disadvantages and risks of taking part?

The researcher understands the complexity, and the difficulty of conveying the personal experience is not easy and straightforward, and the researcher is aware of this situation. However, the researcher guarantees that all answers will remain confidential and stored in a safe place. Moreover, the researcher will not exhibit any judgment or give a personal opinion on the experience, remaining as neutral and objective as possible.

What are the possible benefits of taking part?

We cannot promise the study will help you, but the information we get from the study will help to increase the understanding of the role of Big Data in the banking industry in Egypt, thus providing a better understanding and solid ground to improve organisation performance.

What if there is a problem?

If you have a concern about any aspect of this study, you should ask to speak to the researcher who will do his best to answer your questions (email: [REDACTED])

For official complaints, please send your complaint to my director of studies, Professor Amare Desta (email: [REDACTED])

Will my taking part in the study be kept confidential?

According to the Data Protection Act 1998:

- The data will be collected through questionnaire and interviews
- The data will be stored safely as such:
 - ✓ Individual participant research data, such as questionnaires and interviews, will be anonymous and given a research code, known only to the researcher;
 - ✓ A master list identifying participants to the research codes data will be held on a password-protected computer accessed only by the researcher;
 - ✓ Hard paper/taped data will be stored in a locked cabinet, within a locked office, accessed only by the researcher;
 - ✓ Electronic data will be stored on a password-protected computer known only by the researcher.
- The data will be strictly used for the research degree (academic purpose).
- Only the researcher and the director of studies will have access to the data.
- The data will be stored for three years, and then will be deleted permanently (according to RGCE).

What will happen if I do not carry on with the study?

If you withdraw from the study, we will destroy all your recorded questionnaire and interviews, but we will need to use the data collected up to your withdrawal.

What will happen to the results of the research study?

The research upon its completion will be stored in the university directory, as well as other universities repositories across the UK. The respondents may have access to the comprehensive research if they place a formal request for a copy, either before or after collecting the data.

Who is organising or sponsoring the research?

The academic institution (the University of the West of Scotland) is the main sponsor of the research.

Thank you for reading this information sheet and considering whether or not to take part in the study.

10 Appendix C: Participant Consent Form

Research Consent Form

For (THE NAME OF THE PARTICIPANT)

Name of department: School of Business and Creative Industries

Title of the study:

**Comprehending the role of Big Data in developing countries financial industry: The case of
*banking sector in Egypt***

I confirm that I have read and understood the information about the project as provided in the Participant Information Sheet.

I confirm that I have had the opportunity to ask questions, and the researcher has answered any questions about the study to my satisfaction.

I understand that my participation is voluntary and that I am free to withdraw from the project at any time, without having to give a reason and without any consequences.

I understand that I can withdraw my data from the study at any time.

I understand that any information recorded in the investigation will remain confidential, and no information that identifies me will be made publicly available.

I consent to use of the data in research, publications, sharing and archiving as explained in the Participant Information Sheet.

I consent to be audio/ video/ interviews being recorded as part of the project Yes/ No

I agree/do not agree to take part in the above study.

Name of Participant

Date

Signature

Researcher

Date

Signature

Please retain one copy of the Consent Form for the Participant and one for the Researcher

11 Appendix D: Questionnaire

Executives Group

Banking industry typically has data warehouses and business intelligence tools for reporting on and analysing customer behaviour for better anticipate their needs, and for optimising operations. By deploying Big Data, more significant benefits in these areas can be achieved as the business gains more predictive capabilities and become more agile. The addition of Big Data systems enables organisations to enables more effective decision making.

1. How would you describe Big Data?
2. How would you describe the access to relevant, accurate and timely data in your bank today?
3. To what extent would you describe your organisation as already being a data-driven organisation?
4. Does your organisation work with Big Data? Please explain your answer?
5. How does Big Data fit into your organisational culture?
6. How have you and your colleagues become aware of the potential opportunities and benefits offered for the business by Big Data solutions?
7. What do you think is the most significant opportunity for using Big Data in your organisation?
8. Does your business use Big Data for competitive advantage? Please explain your answer?
9. What data challenges are you addressing with Big Data?
10. When considering your bank's strategic needs as a data-driven organisation, for example, the availability of data itself and the required skills to process it effectively, what resources are limiting factors?
11. What plans and processes will your bank consider putting in place to address the challenges in your previous answer?
12. What do you think is the most significant business challenge for using Big Data?
13. How do you describe your team is equipped with the right skills and perspective to get the data insights you seek?
14. How do you see Big Data changing your approach to performance management in your bank?
15. Do you trust evidence coming only from data when you make a decision? Please explain your answer?
16. What would you do if the data challenges your intuitions and experience in a particular situation?
17. In what ways do you plan to measure the success of your Big Data initiatives?
18. How are Big Data solutions helpful in increasing business revenue?
19. How will you operationalise your vision of Big Data?
20. What lessons have been learnt from the past about investment in using Big Data in the financial services industry?
21. How do you deal with the privacy issue, would your organisation follow a transparency strategy to acknowledge the customer of which data has been collected about them?

IT Group

Banking industry typically has data warehouses and business intelligence tools for reporting on and analysing customer behaviour for better anticipate their needs, and for optimising operations. By deploying Big Data, more significant benefits in these areas can be achieved as the business gains more predictive capabilities and become more agile. The addition of Big Data systems enables organisations to enables more effective decision making.

1. How does your business define & manage trusted data?
2. What kind of data does your business have?
3. How would you define the access to relevant, accurate and timely data in your organisation today?
4. What type of data does your business need?
5. What type of data do you think is the best starting point for using Big Data in your bank?
6. In what ways and to what extent would you describe your organisation as already being a data-driven organisation?
7. What objectives do you hope to attain with your Big Data initiatives?
8. Does your organisation have the exact processes and individuals to deliver your data strategy? Please explain/elaborate on your answer?
9. What data challenges are you addressing with Big Data?
10. What plans is your bank considering to address the challenges in your previous answer?
11. What types of analytics products are you using or considering in using Big Data?
12. What will your guidelines and necessities be for global managing, securing, and governing the data?
13. How do you describe your team equipped with the right skills and perspective to get the insights you seek?
14. What procedures is your organisation use to allow the customers to be aware of the collected data about them?
15. How do you measure the success of the Big Data initiatives?
16. How challenging to source IT Data management skills in general, and Big Data skills in particular?
17. How would you level your organisation on the ability, by the senior management and business leaders, to use Big Data insights to improve or transform the business?
18. How is data ingested, stored, arranged, integrated and consumed within your organisation?
19. Business intelligence technologies are currently the base of business performance management systems. How do you see Big Data as contributing to business performance management systems?
20. What is your thought process about Big Data concerning, organisational performance?
21. What lessons have been learned from the past of investment in using Big Data in the financial services industry?

Regulators Group

Banking industry typically has data warehouses and business intelligence tools for reporting on and analysing customer behaviour for better anticipate their needs, and for optimising operations. By deploying Big Data, more significant benefits in these areas can be achieved as the business gains more predictive capabilities and become more agile. The addition of Big Data systems enables organisations to enables more effective decision making.

1. How would you describe Big Data?
2. What law protects personal information?
3. What information is protected by the Privacy Act?
4. Is it illegal to share someone's personal information? Please explain your answer?
5. What is the scope of Big Data?
6. What are the hazards of Big Data?
7. How should the responsibilities of Big Database distribute?
8. Are the current laws and regulations valid to Big Data? Please explain your answer?
9. Is there a necessity for new legislation for Big Data in Egypt? Please describe your answer?
10. What notion should be fundamental to Big Data regulation in Egypt?

Customers Group

Banking industry typically has data warehouses and business intelligence tools for reporting on and analysing customer behaviour for better anticipate their needs, and for optimising operations. By deploying Big Data, more significant benefits in these areas can be achieved as the business gains more predictive capabilities and become more agile. The addition of Big Data systems enables organisations to enables more effective decision making.

The primary priority for banks is collecting customer data, as advanced programs analyse and draw insights from data to improve customer satisfaction to gain competitive advantage.

1. Do you see that collecting data about you is a potential threat to your privacy? Please explain your answer?
2. How do you protect your personal information?
3. Can you sue someone for sharing personal information? Please describe your answer?
4. Are you aware of the Big Data benefits? Please explain your answer?
5. Will you be able to provide the necessary information when it is needed to improve the quality of service?
6. What could an organisation do to help you understand the added-value of using Big Data in your daily banking?
7. Do you agree that Big Data allows a company to target your interests and deliver personalised offers for products and services to you with almost accurate precision? Please explain your answer?